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Göran Fahlström

THE GLENOHUMERAL JOINT IN MAN

An Anatomic-Experimental and Archaeo-Osteological
Study on Joint Function

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MORS MAGISTER VITAE

THE GLENOHUMERAL JOINT IN MAN

An Anatomic-Experimental and Archaeo-Osteological Study on Joint Function

OSSA

ABSTRACT

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The Glenohumeral Joint in Man. OSSA, Volume 8, 1981, supplement 1, 0–154 pp. Helsingborg. ISBN 91-7146-309-7.

The study aims at a more accurate comprehension of joint function by analysing the effects of two humeroscapular muscles. The role of the skeleton in the application of mechanics and the interpretation of the mechanism of the joint is pointed out by means of:

(1) A two-dimensional approach to forces and loads acting upon the skeleton to create motion and movements; the loads exerting their effects upon the tendon insertion, giving rise to degenerations (3).

(2) Analysing the mechanism of the glenohumeral joint by utilizing recent findings of the author about the end positions of skeletal origin, important to the ergonomics of the joint.

During the past century the axis of motion for joints has been considered to be an imaginary pin. In the light of experimental findings in this study it is corresponding to something real – the contact between the joint surfaces; the contact point. Forces working on the inner lever, loading the insertion have been calculated to be 1–300 kgf at high abduction-elevation degree, outer load being 1–3 kg – in addition to the weight of the arm. This is valid for the short abductors of the glenohumeral joint (the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus) whose transmission ratio for just the humerus as an outer lever is 1:10 at the most.

Skeletal end positions are defined by angular values for the inclination of the humeral shaft versus the tangential plane of the glenoid cavity. The skeletal end positions are of ergonomic importance due to the locking of the humerus with the scapula, for example at javelin throwing, whereby the muscles of the trunk by their strength added, support the forward movement. And note, the difference between subjects is so small that the conclusion is drawn that the angular values represent a mechanism.

The patho-morphic changes of degenerative character, caused by tractional load, are of evidential interest and conclusive for the precise location of the tendon insertion. The importance of the rotational position is illustrated by the distribution of degenerative changes to commonly and/or heavily loaded parts of the tendon insertion area. A very specific example is a type glenohumeral pitting which occurs almost exclusively in the male sex.

The results enable the development of a more accurate understanding of joint function as they are adaptable on other skeletal joints. An axis of motion located in the moving body has to be abandoned as far as joints are concerned.

The axis of motion for a joint is situated where the joint surfaces meet – at the contact point.

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PREFACE

The specificity of the linkage between the upper extremity and the trunk in man is obvious. It is distinguished from the anthropoid's, which maybe possesses greater mobility and even more alternative skeletal end positions, but less stability and less specificity. The uniqueness of the linkage is not limited to the glenohumeral joint, but mostly located in it, and bound to the form of the upper humerus and the glenoid cavity, especially the edges. The glenohumeral joint in man is differentiated by velocity, precision, and to a lesser degree force.

The main task for the arm is to carry the hand, to bring it into position for its performances. There are, however, functions where the hand is merely a grip organ, and the arm, or rather the glenohumeral joint and the muscles from the trunk are responsible for the function. This mechanism and these "sport functions" are specific to the species *Homo sapiens*, and so, consequently, is the javelin throwing.

Spear (javelin) throwing was with certainty practised by the Cro-Magnon people in the department of Dordogne, France, where their remains and paintings have been found together with some tools and weapons, including spear heads. These spears used by our ancestors in France must have been small, like a javelin, perhaps even smaller than the javelin used at athletic contests today, and doubtless a missile weapon. This judged by the size of the spear heads, the paintings, and the fact that the Cro-Magnons were *Homo sapiens*, and consequently possessed the skeletal-anatomical prerequisites for spear throwing.

Interest in hunting and martial procedures and performances seems to predominate over household activities and agriculture, already in pre-historic man. Information is more easily obtainable also, because weapons are made of stone or metal, and consequently have survived better than wood. Throughout human history information seems more accessible on the above mentioned practices of hunting and the use of weapons than on cooking and harvesting. We shall find this also to be true of the medieval material to be explored in this study, although for more specific reasons, namely the traumatic changes in the cranial and postcranial skeletons of the male inhabitants of Westerhus in Jämtland – and the degenerative changes in a defined part of the tendon insertion for the short abductors.

The mechanical evolution was made possible by the combined function of the arm and the hand, though not as in sport functions but more as in the craftsman's work of fabricating tools and weapons to make life easier and safer. Hence the mechanical, hunting, and martial procedures have become easier (less weighty), and more dangerous to man himself. Some industrial work, household work, and sport performances, furthermore many daily routines, have not become easier. The human arm will always have to carry its own weight, and to do so against gravity, even if the movement only is to scratch the head.

In medieval times there was certainly a much higher percentage of the population carrying out really heavy work in a rural community, than in our days and urban households. Therefore the degenerative changes can be expected to be more distinct and to occur more frequently in medieval humeri than in the humeri from our time. Furthermore, the fact of specific act(s) being performed by males or females, slaves or warriors of the higher classes may possibly have given rise to some specific change(s). The difficulty seems to be to find out and explore the working positions and postures carefully enough – and to find out exactly what the relative specific movements were like, how frequently they occurred, how heavy the load was, etc.

This specific linkage of man, the upper extremity's connection with the trunk, constituted by the shoulder joint, specifically the glenohumeral

joint (the small shoulder), is in constant use during lifetime. This joint is not infrequently diseased, and when it is, load, and especially load and speedy movements together, increase the symptoms. Velocity will give a high load intrinsically because of the kinetic energy released by the muscles for the sake of speed; just the arm's weight without any outer load will give an overload in movements of very high velocity. Because of the hitherto related facts, and the fact of the load being calculated to be very high on the insertion in question, it is relevant to look for some signs of wear and tear on the proximal humerus, in the bone, even medieval bones, as they are like ours though the load on medieval insertion might have been higher, which should make the degenerative changes more distinct. These degenerations will be related in part III.

The Westerhus material is distinguished by its magnitude and the population being a relative genetic isolate: for centuries they interred their dead round the little church, evidently according to sex and social status – following Norse Ecclesiastical Laws (Gejvall 1960). The location of Westerhus parish (on the island of Frösö in Jämtland, Sweden) probably contributed to the possible inbreeding as indicated by extremely high frequency of metopic frontal suture, which has been demonstrated by Gejvall (op.cit.). Other non-metrical characteristics, discrete traits, should then also occur. The future possibilities of hereditary studies on this material are predictable. They were stated by Gejvall in his thesis: Westerhus, Medieval Population and Church in the Light of Skeletal Remains.

The probable inbreeding must certainly to some extent have tended to make the skeletal shape in the population more uniform, which could be of importance to this study of skeletal shape and its influence on the mechanics and the mechanism of the joint. It was unpredictable in 1960 that this material would be used in 1980 concerning the application of mechanics to joints and revelations concerning the skeletal end positions, previously only partly described (no ergonomic aspects etc). We were also unable to predict this at the time when this study was started in 1975-76.

My own "dualism" between the practical-theoretical and the clinical-osteological has already been shown, and will soon be obvious. This dualism is easy to understand, considering my background: some twenty years of clinical practice, and five years of scientific-osteological work.

The clinical treatment of tendinitis implied some returning events, too constant to be just overlooked – they induced me to perform this study. The inducements shall be related in the Clinical Prologue, to follow, applications of the findings in the study will be accounted for in the Clinical Epilogue. Applications to every day activities, sport functions, etc. will be found in each of parts I-III. Some examples from the animal kingdom will be found in Comments.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The dedication of this work was first planned to be: "To Them, from Whom I have learned", referring to the members of the early medieval population in Westerhus parish on Frösö island in Jämtland, Sweden, during the 12th, 13th, and 14th centuries. They themselves could of course not have foreseen their contribution to this study of joint function, nevertheless the Norse English, medieval "to them" should be appropriate, considering the early medieval times they lived in.

Most of those to whom my thanks are due, from which I have learned, however, are contemporary, so the dedication chosen was: MORS MAGISTER VITAE, to be combined with the general invocation (to avoid too many words). This Latin sentence is found over the entrance door to the Anatomical Department in Lund, where the late Professor Carl-Herman Hjortsjö had his chair, from whom I have learned so many valuable things reading his monographs, and in conversation on joint function.

Professor Nils-Gustaf Gejvall, who originally described the Westerhus material in his thesis (1960), and who approved the use of its humeri and scapulae, hereby made this study possible. He also introduced me to the relative scientific work and techniques, furthermore he guided me through the entire study, but above all he gladly accepted my possibly not always quite orthodox methods and findings. Last but not least, he gave me confidence.

Professor Harald Brodin, my clinical teacher, encouraged me throughout the time-consuming work, from its clinical start. He has used my preliminary results, and advised me on the clinical measuring of the end positions of skeletal origin. He put me in touch with Professor Gejvall, a very fruitful contact. Last but not least, he gave me confidence.

Professor Torstein Sjøvold watched and guided me and the study from its inception at the Osteological Laboratory. His experience and views on comparative osteology, mathematics, and statistics have been very valuable. He also revealed a new, skeletal end position at adduction where the lesser tubercle constitutes the skeletal part engaged in the locking, at the posture where a sword is drawn out of its sheath. And last but not least, we solved together the problems I could not solve alone, he trusted and supported me, thereby facilitating my own solutions, providing confidence and faith.

I am glad for this opportunity to express my gratitude to these gentlemen.

I would like to express my sincere thanks to Professor M.A. MacConaill, Dublin, for his kind and supportive answer to a letter in 1979.

The statistician Staffan Ekblom, who once taught me statistics was now able to give some advice on analysis of variance, regarding the many angular values, defining the skeletal end position, which led to a recommendation to use the one-way analyses of variance, as recommended by Professor Sjøvold from the beginning.

The language has been supervised by an American journalist, Karl la Corbiniere, in the initial phase (to the Introduction) – and later on in toto by the translator Roger Tanner, reconciling the different languages used in the final script in due time for printing. Karl la Corbiniere really took part in the study and learned enough to apply it on a sport function (the metallic shotput). To be able to do so, he really had to know the mechanism. To reconcile the language, I think, would be impossible without knowing a lot of the mechanisms in this work, and about the English language. I am very grateful to both translators.

The photographer Lars Wiklund used a lot of skill and knowledge to make the pictures surpass reality (at least in original). I am very grateful for his help in both taking new pictures and making something out of old ones.

Many others have taken part in this study in different ways and to different extents; so have Professor Sven Carlsöö, Assistant Professor Jan Roslund, and many colleagues and friends.

They have all been very helpful and inspiring, as have my patients, who became my friends (some of them) – just as friends became patients (some of them). They were all very cooperative and allowed me to perform my tests and examinations, tape bandages, and injections, telling me their stories. Thus they have all been my teachers. I express my warm gratitude to all of them.

My five children – Per, Åsa, Anna, Erik, and Eva – have contributed by watching during a sequence of years how the project progressed, and by listening to my presumably most boring talk about joint function. My mother has contributed by presenting a three weeks old supraspinatus tendinitis, which I was able to cure by one single injection (see Clinical Epilogue p. 110 as to the duration of symptoms).

The skilful craftsman and mechanic Thure Wikbom, who built the experimental model, must not be forgotten. I am very grateful for his help after office hours in both designing and building the model to my specifications.

CLINICAL PROLOGUE

More than five years ago – at the close of some twenty years of clinical-orthopedical-surgical practice during which the skeleton, the joints, and the glenohumeral joint in particular had been my chief interests – I was still mystified by some returning occurrences in the clinical manifestation of "periarthritis humeroscapularis" (Duplay 1872), a clinical syndrome implying pain and stiffness of the shoulder, more exactly the glenohumeral joint. Duplay says: "L'affection sur laquelle je désire appeler l'attention des chirurgiens est extrêmement commune ..." ("the disease I want to draw the attention of the surgeons to, is extremely common ..."). The clinical phenomena just mentioned occurred far too often and systematically to be overlooked, and engaged some physical laws and sciences as well, such as gravitation, applied mechanics, osteology, ergonomics, etc.

From the beginning, then, of the theoretical, per se exhaustive study on the glenohumeral joint in man, I bore a few preformulated questions in mind. It was evident that I had to involve osteology, mechanics, physics, and mathematics to make any progress in the treatment of shoulder tendinitis. It is equally evident that the clinical practice and experience supplied the reasons and the ability to pose the questions.

Load on the insertion of the short abductors (part of the tendineous rotator cuff) obviously prevented the healing of tendinitis. It was impossible to find a method of calculating the load on the tendon insertion, of deciding which posture was the least loaded at the abducent arc. A pilot study involving electromyographic investigation had to be halted because of the regularly occurring deteriorations after EMG with resistance to abduction. The clinical investigation continued with ultrasonic treatment, injections, and load relief methods.

The muscles studied in the EMG investigation were the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus, in addition the deltoid; the infraspinatus was not examined in the cases of supraspinatus tendinitis, but the deltoid was as a control (Fahlström and Knutsson 1976).

The most reliable and effective diagnostic test was abduction at a defined plane, and defined rotational position. If the arm is abducted with the thumb upwards, then the supraspinatus will be loaded. If the arm is abducted with the little finger upwards, then the infraspinatus will receive the load. This test can be emphasized by resistance to the movement, which is usually not necessary, and might be very painful and cause damage if repeated (cf. to the EMG). See Fig. 1 and Fig. 2.

This test is described in the literature (the abducent test, MacLaughlin 1947). It is performed at the same plane as the experimental model of part I was built in, and will be referred to in the Clinical Epilogue p. 111, later on. The test is very useful clinically, and when it is realized that the distribution of load according to the rotational position is of paramount importance for the understanding of the function of the glenohumeral joint, and for the comprehension of the genesis of the degenerative changes – especially the extreme glenohumeral pitting. The principle for the test shall be explained, detailing the function of each muscle involved, and its function, which must not be confused with the position in which, regarding rotation, the humerus is held and at which the movement is performed. (Fig. 1-2)

The load relief method chosen was tape bandage, which hindered movements and was worn over night. Nearly all patients, some in spite of cutaneous lesions from the tape, admitted preferring the tape bandage. Injection of local anaesthesia and Depomedrone 40 mg/ml, 0.5 to 1 ml in the tender part of the insertion seemed to have an effect, curing 70% of 60 patients in 6-8 weeks. In some cases the cure was complete in one day's time, after a single injection. It was obvious that load caused deterioration. The problem persisted, however, how to find the position

in which to keep the arm for the most effective relief of load. (Fig. 3) Another interesting phenomenon was the deleterious effects of speedy movements, compared to slow in tendinitis. In other words: defined high velocity movements such as regaining balance in a suddenly stopping bus, or catching a falling object were more often the probable causes of deterioration. The short abductors, with short levers, are prone to be prime movers at high velocity movements. Incidentally there is no information available about the inner lever or speedy movements in the glenohumeral joint in the literature. I had to pursue them myself.

Fig. 1-2 The MacLaughlin abductions test (1947).
Outwards rotated position: supraspinatus – inwards rotated position: infraspinatus; or: supination, supraspinatus – pronation, infraspinatus. Thumb up = supination. Little finger up = inwards rotated, pronated.
Note! Supinated position, pronated position, not the movements.

Some clues to the secrets of the glenohumeral joint of man were given by clinical experience and the returning events in the clinical course of tendinitis. The things of interest, then, were the inner lever, and the tendon insertion. The location of the tendon insertion, naturally is of the greatest interest and importance to clinical therapy, as well as its construction is for the application of the principles of mechanics. The discussion of the principles of mechanics, the principles for a solution of the problem to adapt them on a skeletal joint, axis of motion, tendon insertion, levers, etc. will be given in the next part of the study, Introduction – where the axis of motion is the most important item.

Fig. 3 The tape bandage as used at the Karolinska sjukhuset 1974-1977 (still in use).

INTRODUCTION

As human beings we should all know, and have all experienced, the great mobility of the glenohumeral joint. We can scratch our backs, put our hands on our necks by flexion at neutral rotation – or in the outwards rotated position (supinated). If we want, however, to put the arm behind the neck from say 90° of abduction at the abductional arc, then we have to supine the arm to succeed. Similarly a pronated position will make us unable to reach the neck in flexion as well as by abduction from 90° . It is as if an irregular shape of the joint prevented some combinations in this elementary example. Obviously the rotational position of the arm determines one's ability to put one's hand on one's neck.

Fig. 4 Sketch from Benninghoff, 1949, Urban & Schwarzenberg Verlag, Berlin-München. Pronation and supination, in- and outwards rotation of the arm. Note that the rotation of the arm is accomplished by rotation in the elbow, and in the glenohumeral joint, approximately 90° each.
(The humeral head added by the author)

It is necessary to imagine the conditions for motion in the glenohumeral joint in three dimensions, which seems to be troublesome for the human mind and imagination. It is much easier to imagine and to realize the function of a jumping jack, mechanically – and perhaps even in the three-dimensional doll made of celluloid, with a central string to fasten arms and legs, and the circular ridge to hinder all gliding (grinding, sliding) making it totally unlike a human skeletal joint of the ball and socket type.

A multitude of factors are existant in and around a joint and are directly relevant to the joint function mechanically, e.g. muscle, tendon, capsula, and ligament. Furthermore the skeletal shape is designed for its purpose – and a very important determinant of the joint function, motion in the joint, and movement in the extremity.

The glenohumeral joint, then, is not freely movable as an ideal, spherical ball and socket joint should be. Motion in the joint takes place as a rotation of the ball, or a gliding down in the socket, as for example at

Fig. 5 Lateral, two-dimensional projection of the knee joint. It is easily understood that the dislocation of the evoluta will be much larger in the knee joint, than in the glenohumeral joint with an almost circular lateral, two-dimensional projection of the humeral head.

Fig. 6 The glenohumeral mobility in a two-dimensional projection – no rotation of the humerus!

Benninghoff (1949).

abduction of the arm. As the caput is far from spherical the gliding down cannot occur round a central axis without any dislocation of this axis spatially. This dislocation is very small in the glenohumeral joint, much larger, for example, at the knee joint. The two-dimensional dislocation (its projection) of the central axis of motion is called the evoluta. Fig. 5, above.

The two-dimensional projection of the glenohumeral joint has been the image studied to interpret the mechanics of the joint in this study and previous literature, the image used in all textbooks of anatomy, and joint mechanics, biomechanics, etc. There certainly exist three-dimensional attempts too. The two-dimensional image with a central axis of motion, where the central axis of motion is the central, and important thing (imaginary), emanates from a few German authors, 1904-1911 (Strasser, Fischer, Fick, to be mentioned below). This axis, however, whether it has two dimensions or three, is imaginary, existing only on paper. To be real this axis would have to be replaced by a pin (jumping jack), and fixed as to its position in a skeletal joint for at least each abductions level. The idea of a central pin is to be regarded as a rough simplification of motion in a joint. Most anatomy books (textbooks) contain these ideas and, in addition, an illustration in a two-dimensional projection of the spatial dislocation of the distal humerus at maximal excursions (seemingly without any simultaneous rotation of the humeral shaft); describing some kind of figure as a projection in two dimensions and compared to a big circle having its centre in the glenohumeral joint; see Fig. 6 above. This linear, two-dimensional image of glenohumeral mobility resembles a flat, thick pear. The relative similarity to the classical picture of the glenoid cavity is striking. And note well, there should be a similarity as the edge of the cavity is limiting the free movement of the joint (by the greater tubercle hitting, and bracing). See Fig. 6 above and Fig. 7 page 11.

Fig. 7 The pear shape of the glenoid cavity from Benninghoff (1949). Note also the labium articulare.

There are three degrees of freedom in an ideal ball and socket joint, as in the glenohumeral; as already stated the motion in the joint, however, is not free as could be expected if it were an ideal, spherical joint. The humeral head has its two protuberances – the greater tubercle and the lesser tubercle – and in addition the humeral shaft intruding the spherical path of mobility. That is why the image of the spatial dislocation of the distal humerus (without any simultaneous rotation) describes some kind of figure as a projection in two dimensions and compared to a big circle is so much less than half the big circle with its centre in the glenohumeral joint. Fig. 6 page 16.

Some mechanical principles, functional anatomy, anatomic considerations, and literature reviewing the most important issues of this study, namely the skeletal end positions, and the degenerative changes of a special type from tractional load, will be quoted. An example of the central question on the axis of motion will be given in a quotation from Hjortsjö. The intimate relations between the three parts of the study, and the paramount importance of the rotational position, will be stressed again and again.

In the concept of functional anatomy, it is possible to apply the principles of mechanics, as far as a joint is concerned. As information in the current literature and all previous literature failed to function in the calculation of forces and loads in the glenohumeral joint, it was necessary to construct an experimental model and try to find out what the functional anatomy was like.

The study concentrates on the short abductors, their function in abduction movement, their insertion on the greater tubercle, and the pawl function of the greater tubercle. In other words the magnitude of the load on the insertion, where it is located, possible relief of load – and the degenerative results of the load. The entire study is in consideration of tendinitis of the shoulder (Duplay 1872).

Overloading of insertions and attachments, as well as origins of muscles, may cause small ruptures in the insertion areas. Thus ruptures in turn can cause microhemorrhages, giving small hematomas, which intrinsically are the same cysts that cause clinical tendinitis, and the specific, small-cystic degeneration osteologically. These cysts are brought on by load, but not just any load – a certain magnitude of load is certainly required, as well as velocity of the movement, and some repetition, the last mentioned not being necessary to create a singular hemorrhagic cyst in the soft tissues. The rotational position will decide where in the insertion the singular cyst will appear. It seems reasonable to consider a number of soft tissue cysts as being necessary to create one skeletal

cyst, the changes and the cysts migrating into the bone tissue eventually.

As for the application of the principles of mechanics to joints, there exists but one, particular theory, founded at the end of the 19th century, and maintained to the 20th. This solitaire is the German theory of joint mechanics, utilizing a central, imaginary axis of motion in the convex skeletal member of the joint, and propagated by Fischer (1907), Strasser (1908), and Fick (1911). This old German theory was still being propounded in a course for orthopedic surgeons, held as late as 1979 in Gothenburg, Sweden. The course was held by Y. Chao from the Mayo Clinic, New York, U.S.A.

The German school, consequently, prevails in the field of joint mechanics and has done so for almost 100 years. The authors mentioned are the most important, often quoted, speaking in favour of the central, imaginary axis of motion in the male part of the joint. They have been referred to ever since, and they have hereby, involuntarily, overshadowed any new view on this subject by their authority. According to the German authors the inner force was to be calculated from the cut muscle surface multiplying by a constant.

Apparently the shape of the skeletal parts and their importance have not been appreciated for their value to the mechanics of the joint. Since the application of the principles of mechanics requires the existence of a defined lever in the joint, and one outside the joint, and as the skeleton supplies them, it seems necessary to study the skeleton. The axis of motion and the point of attack are very important items for the application of the mechanical principles, as they determine the length of levers and angular relations in the parallelogram of forces.

Fischer (1907) obviously considered the form of joint surfaces, and their importance for movements, and quotes in the first chapter as a subtitle: "Ueber die Formen der Gelenkflächen und die aus denselben sich ergebenden möglichen Arten der Gelenkbewegungen" ("On the shape of joint surfaces, and their importance to possible motion in joints"). The locking mechanism at 90° of abduction at a defined plane and neutral rotational position, described by Henke (1863), is a good example of the importance of skeletal shape for joint motion. It was described by Henke as the greater tubercle meeting the edge of the glenoid cavity, and bracing.

The point of attack, where the forces are applied in a system of at least one moving body, is almost as important as the axis of motion, as this point determines the length of the inner lever. The tendon insertion is usually said to be located on the facet's surface, corresponding to the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus, on the top of the greater tubercle. The facets, however, are totally smooth (if not marked by degenerations). This anatomical description is found in the textbooks of anatomy and joint function, as well as in monographs and illustrations herein (Basmaijan & MacConaill 1969, note cover illustration). The related description of the tendon insertion being localized to the facets is found in Poirier & Charpy (1911). Beninghoff (1949), Rauber-Kopsch (1946), and Gray (1973). This location has always been used as an illustration. Some micro-photographs, not intended to show precisely this relation, seem to indicate a broader attachment of the tendon (see Fig. 8 page 13).

The experimental investigation in this study is performed at a defined plane of the glenohumeral joint, where the plane is chosen perpendicular to the tangential plane of the glenoid cavity, hereby representing the antigravitational abduction, provided the position of the body is upright. It is the same plane that was defined by Henke: all abduction movement will stop at 90° of abduction, provided the rotational position is neutral and the skeleton of normal shape.

Fig. 8 Microphotograph of the glenohumeral joint (section), Fick (1904). Note the broad insertion.

The one muscle of the two short abductors will be the supraspinatus, and possibly some fibres of the infraspinatus as well. The anatomical names, however, are not essential to the functional anatomy or for the understanding of the function. The short abductors are in this study considered as a functional unit, of which the parts creating the muscle resultant in the actual situation are the important thing – and not the names. Likewise the insertion of the short abductors is considered common. The rotational position decides which part is going to be loaded. The most medial and the most lateral parts of the greater tubercle are 3-4 cm apart. Their topographical, spatial position, as well as the function of each are possible to separate.

Attempts have been made to calculate the forces affecting the skeletal joint in three dimensions, with a central axis of motion in the male part of the joint (Cooney et al. 1977), cf. Fischer (1907), Strasser (1908), and Fick (1911), the classical German authors.

The experiments in the present study were performed in two dimensions, regarding the parallelogram of forces, and the fact that the orthogonal vector quantity is a one-dimensional problem. It seems superfluous, then, even to try to solve it in three dimensions. The axle-axis seems to belong to the joint space, and will in this study be supposed to be located at the contact point, between the two joint surfaces (except when the central axis is used for checking the classical theory in part I).

An axis of motion, not only eccentric, but situated at the spatial limit of the moving body (the humerus), is the most important feature subject of this study. It is intimately linked to the innovation of spatial thinking being introduced, and a prerequisite of the application of the principles of mechanics. It is connected with the acceptance of the contact point as an axis of motion for a joint. However, the resemblance between the old-fashioned drawbridge and a joint mechanically is striking, as is the dissimilarity between the joint and a wheel. Nature did not use either as a type when creating the joint – at the time of creation there were no drawbridges, and no wheels.

Tracing the axis of motion in his monograph *Motion and Movements* (1964), Hjortsjö actually hits the bull's eye in the comparison between the

joints of a jumping jack and a skeletal joint, but he returns to the linear, central axis of motion (classical, German type).

Hjortsjö writes:

"I would like to start with a simple model, an ordinary jumping jack. Even he lacking all mechanical sense can here easily see how arms and legs will move when one pulls the cord. Consciously or unconsciously, conclusions are based upon how the cords pass in relation to the pins (axles) by means of which the extremities are secured to the trunk."

Hjortsjö continues:

"We can thus, in conclusion, establish that the type of movement produced, irrespective of what we call it, is altogether due to the location and orientation of the axis of motion in question and to the course of the muscle resultant in relation to it. More exactly expressed, the purpose of the analysis of joints is to establish as carefully as possible the location of these axes of motion for every special joint connection."

Hjortsjö summarizes:

"Finally, all findings must be considered against the background of the anatomical structure of the capsular and ligamental mechanism. Investigations of this nature are extremely exacting and, moreover, they have hitherto been carried out very modestly."

Hjortsjö did not mention the skeleton nor the skeletal shape in the quoted lines. Obviously he believes in the German type of application of the principles of mechanics.

Additively to Hjortsjö, the skeletal shape in this study is considered to be the primary factor; the soft tissues being regarded as of secondary importance, and their function presupposed to be in coordination with the lines and limits directed by the form of the skeleton. According to these theories, the soft tissues merely stabilize, rather than direct movements. Muscles of course give the direction of movements as well as the force. But as we shall see, more muscles are recruited for certain movements because of the skeletal shape, and some movements have to be performed at specific posture positions, where this extra force is available.

It is hard to imagine how the smooth movements of a joint could be served by linear axes, working in one plane at a time, actually imaginary (as their presence should make all function impossible), and not being able to serve either caput rotation at flexion, or "pure rotation" (caput and shaft coinciding), without a considerable dislocation in space.

Note well, presuming the axis of motion to be linear, it will inevitably lead to shortcomings in the understanding. Further, if the axis of motion is assumed to be located in the humeral head, then the whole business of applying the principles of mechanics becomes incomprehensible and impossible. On the other hand, presuming the axis of motion to be almost punctual, located in the joint (contact point), and movable, suggests another view, and presents a possibility to apply the principles of mechanics to this joint, as well as to other joints.

The late German authors Fischer (1907), Strasser (1908), and Fick (1911) in their writings and those applying their theories, all calculated with a central axis in the humeral head, actually an imaginary measuring device. The inner force (as already was pointed out) was calculated by multiplying the "cut muscle surface" by a constant. The outer force was calculated from the centre of the male part of the joint (the imaginary centre). This axis is imaginary without any definable correspondence in

reality. The axis of motion is of the greatest importance for the calculations because it represents both levers and decides their length. It therefore has to correspond to something real, certainly more than "imaginary".

A few authors, e.g. Saha (1961), and Pieron (1973), have discussed the contact point, but neither has used it for calculations. The intra-articular contact point is issued for the first time in this study as the axis of motion for a joint. The central axis of motion, in the centre of the convex skeletal member, appearing together with a three-dimensional approach, has previously been used, instead of the two-dimensional approach and the punctual, real axis of motion – the contact point, which both have been used in this study.

Some anatomical description will be given in the respective parts; a review of the functional anatomy and some literature references will be given here. The study is constructed to concentrate on functional details, as the procedure to enhance projecting mechanical aspects. Stress has been laid, and will be laid, upon the skeletal shape, and the soft tissues will be regarded as necessary for cohesion, but not as deciding the form and the length of movements, nor as stopping them at defined positions (as for the glenohumeral joint). The study is primarily concerned with the greater tubercle and the bicipital groove (sulcus intertubercularis), where the degenerative changes are located. For purposes of measurement, analysis, explanation, and discussion, the scapula is taken to stand still (or made to stand still on examination). The anatomy of the greater tubercle and the glenoid cavity will be explained together, explaining the pawl function at the skeletal end positions. The scapular movement, for example, will be taken into account to explain the mechanical, ergonomic effects of the skeletal locking. Muscles other than the short abductors are thought to exist, and will be mentioned in the appropriate context.

End positions, even skeletal end positions, are described in literature as the abduction stop at 90° , at a defined plane, and neutral rotational position – as described by Henke in 1863. Seldom, if ever, is there any reference to Henke, however. Other end positions are described, explained, and maybe defined as skeletal end positions of the glenohumeral joint. The explanations, though, are undoubtedly incomplete in regard to the skeletal mechanism. In the 1930s, Henke's statement seems to have been ignored. Granted, the abduction stop was recognized, the rotational position discussed, but the mechanical stop was thought to be the meeting between the greater tubercle and the acromion (Ohnsorge 1932, Martin 1932, and MacGregor 1936). Contrarily Saha pointed out the abduction stop to be present after acromionectomy, hereby supporting Henke's theory that the stop is caused by the meeting of the greater tubercle and the edge of the glenoid cavity.

The three end positions of skeletal origin covered by this study are:

- (1) abduction stop at 90° of abduction in the abduction arc,
- (2) spear (javelin) throwing, the acceleration phase,
- (3) forehand drive in tennis, the stroke-hit.

The two last mentioned have not been fully recognized as skeletal end positions. They are, however, and according to the same definition essentially similar to the abduction stop: a meeting between the greater tubercle with the edge of the glenoid cavity and bracing; or the greater tubercle functions as a pawl against the edge of the glenoid cavity, hindering further motion in the joint at defined posture positions. Different parts of facets' surface as well as of the cavity's edge are involved at different skeletal end positions; even the lesser tubercle may be involved, for example in adduction at forward conduction – the sword draught position.

In literature these three end positions are mentioned, but the two last definitely not as skeletal end positions, and not with the definition as

Henke offered in 1863. They have been mentioned as end or stop positions, but not analysed as to the reason for the stop. This is valid for the tennis position (forehand drive), described by many authors in various writings, most clearly by Hjortsjö (1964).

He writes: "A further example of circumduction ... Standing with arm extended horizontally sideways, the subject moves his hand and arm in a small half-circle somewhat downwards forwards and forwards-upwards. In the initial position the palm of the hand must be directed dorsad. While moving in a quarter-circle path downwards-forwards the palm will successively be downwards directed and during a quarter-circle path forwards-upwards becomes directed ventrad. It is obvious that the arm here describes in space one half of a cone having its apex in the caput humeri. (Note, not in the joint, comment by the present author.) The movement described is a pure circumduction movement."

Two things are to be commented here and now:

1. The rotation of the arm is discussed by Hjortsjö, i.e. during the circular or semi-circular movement of the hand (circumductional). This rotation (around the long axis of the arm) will be discussed in the second part. Suffice it to say here that the circular path will be interrupted and stopped by the mechanism of the skeletal end positions, only if the palm of the hand is directed ventrad at the end of the movement, and dorsad from the start of it, as stated by Hjortsjö. The possible rotation of the arm, the parts rotating, and in which case they rotate, will be discussed later.

2. The abduction level for circumduction of the arm is free, from 20 to 90° of abduction in the glenohumeral joint. The circular movement has to be clockwise as described by Hjortsjö. The possible rotation of the arm varies somewhat at different abduction levels. This will be discussed in Part II (p. 51, near bottom). Hjortsjö describes the circumduction at 90° (extended horizontally sideways) abducted position. In this study the circumduction shall be referred to at an abduction level of 50°, because of the forehand drive occurring at this level.

One more end position covered by this study and also of skeletal origin has been described by MacConaill (1969) as "the close packed position" of the glenohumeral joint. It corresponds exactly to the spear throwing position of this study. The close packed position, however, is considered to be caused by a congruence of the joint surfaces. This study offers another and different explanation which is more in line with the theory concerning the skeletal end position of circumduction. This theory emphasizes the importance of the greater tubercle in relation to the edge of the glenoid cavity.

The objective is to point out the two new end positions to be described, explained, and defined as of great importance to joint function for the shoulder and for the glenohumeral joint in sports as well as in routines of daily life. MacConaill's close packed position (somewhat skeletal), which corresponds to spear throwing; and the end position of circumduction as described by Hjortsjö, but at 50° of abduction, which is identical with the forehand drive position in tennis, are the two most commonly used locking conditions of the glenohumeral joint of skeletal origin. This means that they are used not only in hitting tennis balls, and throwing spears, but also in casting, heavy pushing, and particular forms of carrying. Relative examples are: throwing a metallic shotput, pushing heavy objects such as a bookshelf (facing with elbows behind the body); or carrying-delivering a child from hip to hip-level surface.

The positions covered by this study do not make a complete list of skeletal end positions of the glenohumeral joint of man. The skeletal end positions of this species are about a dozen, involving also the lesser tubercle. To be as clear and short as possible, however, I chose to study and relate just the three of them: Henke's abduction stop, spear throwing, and the forehand drive in tennis. They are the most common and distinct end positions, the latter two occurring in the backwards conducted position.

The analysis of the end positions was performed in three dimensions, because there are three degrees of freedom of movement in a ball and socket joint. The angular measuring values are abduction, backwards conduction, and rotation. The abduction stop occurs in forward conducted position. The plan was to make six measurements at each position on skeletal preparations, and four for each position clinically, to get a routine, to obtain enough numerical values for statistical analysis, and to allow for the virginity of the subject.

The examination of the tendon insertion, whose function is shared by the two short abductors, namely the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus on the greater tubercle, is an examination of degenerative changes brought about by tractional load.

References were made to these changes by Angel (1969), Gejvall (1970), Swedborg (1974), Ullrich (1975), and Gejvall again (1982). The degenerative signs consist of smaller and larger cysts in the cortical bone, caused by minor hemorrhages in connection with partial ruptures in the attachments of tendons and ligaments as well as joint capsulae and origins of muscles.

Gejvall discovered some large cysts at the origin of the medial gastrocnemius muscle's head in mesolithic fishermen from the isle of Gotland, Sweden, for which he coined the term popliteal pitting (Janzon 1974, pp. 165-166). Other findings are cystical changes in the pelvic bones of females who have given birth to several children. These cysts are located to insertions, attachments, origins, etc. They have been used for sex determination and are fairly well-known. The popliteal pitting has been found also in Peru in a limited number of knee joints from hunters and fishermen from the coast land, Catalogue of the HRDLICKA, Paleopathology Collection, edited by Rose A. Tyson et al. (1980).

There are possibilities of similar changes being present on the greater tubercle, in the insertion area of the short abductors, since equivalent prerequisites are fulfilled. The mechanical transmission of the glenohumeral joint implies very high loads on the insertion of the short abductors, especially at certain posture positions. For theoretical reasons, mechanical reasons, and teleological reasons considering the function of the joint, high velocity, highly elevated, and weighty movements are the most heavily loaded for the insertion. Such movements are: regaining balance in a bus, catching a falling object, fighting with a sword, etc. - to be explained in Part III (p. 89).

The location of the tendon insertion is manifested by the distribution of the degenerative changes, the signs of wear and tear, and their spread during a life-span. The distribution varies with sex and age. Males have a specific degenerative mark, which does not occur in females, or usually not, and certainly not to the same extent as in males.

The posture, abduction level, and direction of movements are of great importance for the magnitude of the load; where the load is to be distributed, medially or laterally in the insertion, is determined by the rotational position. Regarding load, velocity, and specificity of posture there are two outstanding movements, covered by this study: the parry position pertaining to sword fighting, and timber cutting.

The references are few, but extremely relevant, in fact the research was to part III and partly in toto initiated by the information in the

literature about the cystic degeneration from tractional load. As the loads were high, experimentally calculated on the insertion of the short abductors, such changes could be expected to occur on the greater tubercle.

As to the axis of motion the literature is repetitive – which is valid for the application of the principles of mechanics – reverting to the central axis of motion, which shall be critically analysed as will other entities like the rotation during circumduction.

For the end positions of skeletal origin, the mechanism of the glenohumeral joint, Saha's statement that the abduction stop is present also after acromionectomy is of the utmost importance, telling us that the acromion is not responsible for the skeletal stop at abduction 90° . It also confirms Henke's original theory about the stop being caused by a meeting of the greater tubercle and the edge of the glenoid cavity. These definitions and their confirmation are the basis for the theory of the skeletal end positions.

Hjortsjö's Motion and Movements (1964) is the most valuable reference where the comparison between the joints of a jumping jack and a skeletal joint is found together with other valuable considerations such as the circumduction movement, and the axis of motion.

The contact point, mentioned not more than skin-deep and not used for measuring or calculation by Saha (1961), and Pieron (1973), is a central issue of this study.

The following topics will be considered:

1. Two-dimensional experiments to find out the forces and loads affecting the insertion of the short abductors, abduction at a defined plane and rotational position. Comparison between loading curves for contact point method and central axle (pin) method.

2. Skeletal end positions, locking conditions between the greater tubercle and the edge of the glenoid cavity. Paramount importance of the rotational position of the humeral shaft and caput. Ergonomic importance by locking of the humerus with the scapula at forward conduction. Abduction to 90° , Henke (1863), and two locking conditions in backwards conducted position are defined, namely spear throwing, and the forehand drive position in tennis.

3. Degenerative changes in the insertion area of the insertion for the short abductors caused by tractional load. Location of the tendon insertion is manifested by the degenerative changes. An extreme example and evidence of the importance of the rotational position is glenohumeral pitting, a most distinct degenerative sign.

MATERIAL

Westerhus, Medieval Population and Church in the Light of Skeletal Remains is the title of Professor N.-G. Gejvall's thesis (1960) about the inhabitants of Westerhus, mentioned in the PREFACE of this study. In the Westerhus study all the cranial and postcranial metrical values are listed, together with age and sex for more than 200 individuals. Westerhus is situated 65.12° north, and 14.24° east, on Frösö island in Jämtland, Sweden. The subjects lived 1100 to 1300 A.D. over a period of 2-300 years, and were consequently interred at various depths. In Gejvall's work there are many photos, showing every skull, some pathological and traumatological states of bone such as dystrophies, inflammations, and blunt traumata as well as fresh and healed skeletal wounds from edged weapons.

In the present scientific work on forces and loads, end positions of skeletal origin, and degenerative changes revealed in the insertion region of the short abductors, the traumatology is of special interest. Some details of skeletal traumatology will be dealt with, and also sexual segregation, and social stratification; some degenerative changes revealed in this work will be mentioned only here, as they are no more than a systematic observation, and not qualified to take any space in the specific part on the degeneration in the insertion area of the short abductors.

Little is known about medieval life in a small parish of the size and type of Westerhus. Even Westerhus and its inhabitants, of which we know so much "in the light of skeletal remains", are in many detailed respects totally unknown. The details we don't know about are referable to the soft tissue and its diseases and possible traumatology, the habits of the isolated people as regarding ploughing, harvesting, cooking, etc. We may assume that they needed timber and wood for building houses and for firewood. The ergonomics of harvesting can be estimated, of course, like most daily routines, being similar to the same routines in modern time. The highest and most specific lift occurring was the parry movement per se, the parrying to ward off an offensive thrust (armed or unarmed). The specific thing about these movements is the pronated position (inwards rotated) at which the arm is necessarily held. As far as we have been able to deduce there is one performance beyond the parry movement pertaining to sword fighting executed in maximal pronation, namely timber cutting. These movements will be analysed more in detail in part III on the degenerative changes. Here will follow a review of what we do know about the medieval Westerhus people.

Some traumatological details are to be presented now as they are correlated to ergonomic details to be discussed, as will the sexual segregation of the same cause, and the social stratification; segregation and stratification regarding the location in the cemetery of the buried bodies. These data will be extracted from the rich sources of knowledge found in the already mentioned work on Westerhus. The limitations of the title should be observed: "in the light of skeletal remains", the Westerhus skeletons are true witnesses - if we only can put the right questions, and interpret the answers correctly.

Males were buried south, and females north of the church (with few exceptions). Tall females were interred near the church, as were males (in the south area of the church yard) who had evidently died in battle, or carried skeletal wounds from edged weapons. It is to be observed, however, that the correlation here might be: high social status, fighting battles, getting wounded. Seemingly both causes could have influenced the burial place, as some heavily wounded males were buried very close to the church. No female skeletons carried any marks from edged weapons, but 10-15% of the adult males did (including males from adult and upwards among the 50 individuals constituting this material). According to

burial place near the church (with the above reservation), there seems to be a social status in being killed or wounded by the sword. Likewise there were a few females interred south-east, or even south of the church, tall, with degenerative changes in their tendon insertion of the short abductors, proximally on the right humerus, suggesting that they might have used the sword in their lifetimes, or alternatively cut timber.

During the examination of proximal humeri, I found some tendon insertions other than the one of the short abductors to be apparently damaged by heavy loads, i.e. hard work. This is valid for the deltoid, the pectorales, and the latissimus dorsi, inserting on the tuberositas deltoidea (the deltoid), the coracoid, and the crista tuberculi majoris (the pectorales), crista tuberculi minoris (teres major, and the latissimus dorsi); the teres minor inserts dorsolatero-caudally on the greater tubercle, behind and below the glenohumeral pitting and functions together with the infraspinatus supinating (outwards rotating). These skeletons had been far from the church, the owners of the skeletons probably having been slaves, or so called freedmen, or simply peasants. The degenerative changes found in these hypothetical slave skeletons correspond to findings in neolithic material, according to results obtained in collaboration with Düring (1980). No degenerative changes specific to medieval times were found in the short abductors insertion in the neolithic material; the above mentioned changes confined to the pectorales etc. were contrarily existing in the neolithic material, which was limited. The degenerative change intended to be characteristic for medieval times, then, should be the specific type of glenohumeral pitting to be described in part III.

There was an intermediate burial zone, where, according to the degenerative changes on the proximal humerus, the persons buried might have been both slaves and warriors, as shown by their degenerations judged according to my theories.

According to the Borgarthing's Ecclesiastical Laws, containing rules for church building and the social stratification in a churchyard for the region concerned at the time concerned, the following rules could have been valid for just this cemetery: "Länder-men shall be buried east of the church and in the ground to the south of its eavesdrip. If they own no share in the churchyard, they shall lie in the peasants area. Thereafter shall be buried the hölder-men and the hölder-men's children, and thereafter the freedmen and the freedmen's children. Up against the churchyard shall be buried slaves and men who have been cast up on the sea shore and have their hair cut in the fashion of the Norsemen." (op.cit. pp. 120-121).

The same rules are found in the early Eidsivating's Ecclesiastical Law, the preamble of which lays down: "Men shall lie south of, and women north of (the church)". This preamble to §50 of the quoted law had obviously been adopted in Westerhus (op.cit.). These pages as well as the whole book is recommended to anybody interested in the Westerhus skeletons and what is known about them.

Still there were no rules laid down that the warriors should be interred close to the church, to my knowledge – and maybe there was no practice of doing so either. It is certain that the males of higher classes were honoured by a burial location near the church. It is also probable that the males of the higher classes were joining the front line in a possible war, therefore getting most blows, including the fatal ones. It is probable too that the warriors killed were honoured by burial close to the church, regardless of social status. It is impossible, however, to conclude from available data which theory is true.

The degenerative changes in the insertion of the short abductors, and those limited to the dorsocaudal part, occurring in the male sex, and best explained ergonomically by the parry movement pertaining to sword

fighting – in this study denoted glenohumeral pitting – all are to be described, defined, explained, and exemplified in Part III, which deals with the degenerative changes on the greater tubercle. As the parry movement pertaining to sword fighting is a most specific movement, as to posture and height of load – as well as to velocity and height of the lifting and in addition of special interest and importance to this study, the traumatologic evidence in Gejvall's work that sword fighting existed in Westerhus is necessary for the discussion to come. It is to be noted that the load in timber cutting will exert its effects on the same posterocaudal part of the insertion. Either of these performances, sword fighting or timber cutting, could have caused glenohumeral pitting, the most distinct degenerative sign on the greater tubercle in this early medieval material. And note well, as Gejvall's title implies: the skeletal remains are the only witnesses, though silent. It is our task to interpret the signs of wear and tear.

The 56 complete pairs of glenohumeral joints, constituting the material for the skeletal examination of angular values (measuring) for skeletal end positions were collected out of the skeletal material from Westerhus, representing all undamaged pairs of glenohumeral joints. The Westerhus material is at present stored in boxes at the Osteological Research Laboratory, Ulriksdal.

Almost twice as many humeri were found undamaged, possible to examine, namely 91 pairs of humeri, 41 female, and 50 male. They were examined for degenerative changes proximally (on the greater tubercle). To exclude the effects of left-handedness they were evaluated as pairs.

From the 46 complete pairs with scapulae, 30 individuals were picked out of age and sex to match the clinical material for angular measuring. Age in both materials, then, 20-70 years, 30 individuals or 60 joints in skeletal, and in clinical material.

Some further details, concerning the reason for not using all the 46 pairs, functional anatomy, size of materials, age grouping, number of measurements, etc. will be explained in parts II-III. The skeletal end position, besides, should be even more similar in different subjects if we can assume an unusual similarity of this skeletal material.

PART ONE

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APPLICATION OF THE PRINCIPLES OF MECHANICS

To be able to apply the theories of mechanics it is necessary to know two things: 1) the principles of mechanics, and 2) the entity they are intended to be applied to. This part therefore starts with the definition of the principles of mechanics, and applied anatomy.

The mechanical principles are known by everyone, but have been partly forgotten by some of us. The application requires imagination and perhaps it takes a specific sense, mentioned by Hjortsjö (1964), to realize the spatial relationships especially in movements, not least to differ motion in the joint from movement of the extremity. Some mechanical principles must have been ignored by Fischer (1907), Strasser (1908), and Fick (1911). Perhaps there is some lack of imagination in the German theory, though it seems to be correct, and really is imaginative with its imaginary axis of motion.

It is necessary to get rid of some classical and strictly theoretical ideas about mechanics, or the application of its principles (such as the linear axis of motion), to forget about the wheels and the jumping jack, i.e. central axles. One has to look for other examples of applied mechanics and try their respective solutions of application, to see if they fit our example. Therefore the solution will be approached by means of relating some examples of applied mechanics.

1. The seesaw (swing-board), a very common and well-known arrangement mostly for children's play. There is a fulcrum or support somewhere near the middle of the board. Depending on body weight it is necessary for one of the children to approach or withdraw from the axis of motion situated between the board and the fulcrum. This axis of motion is extracorporeal, situated not in the board, and not in the fulcrum, but at the point of contact between the two – or along the contact line.

2. The old-fashioned drawbridge (from medieval times) is a very good and very interesting example with regard to joints. The construction is a flap, movable by two ropes fastened at the middle of the flap or at the opposite end. The axis of motion is extracorporeal at one end of the flap, motion is concentric round the axis, which is fixed in the ground. Further details are of no interest for the principles. The axis of motion (and the axle for the movement) is situated between the flap and its "joint socket" in the ground. The most primitive drawbridges consisted of a flap with a rounded end to fit a hole or furrow in the ground. This is another example of the contact line (or at least two contact points, one at each end) for a rigid concentric movement of the flap, which is directly comparable to an extremity bone. The ropes, then, correspond to the tendon. Modern drawbridges are too sophisticated to be suitable examples, note well: old-fashioned, primitive, constructed as a one armed lever.

3. The kind of old-fashioned well illustrated below gives us a two armed system of levers, just as the seesaw gives a two armed system, and with an extracorporeal axis-axle. The ancient drawbridge, however, is the best example and most similar to the glenohumeral joint, because there is only one lever – even if the distance or proportions of distance from joint to insertion not is the same, and the joint is two armed.

Fig. 9 Seesaw: the heavier child will lift the less weighty, but the principle intended for illustration is the axis of motion, situated extracorporeally.

Fig. 10 Drawbridge: the ropes pull, the flap moves in the cavity, axis outside the flap.

Fig. 11 The old-fashioned well.

Fig. 12 The glenohumeral joint: the cuff pulls, humerus moves, axis (axle) outside the bone.

So far, and having exhausted my imaginative examples, I move towards the skeletal joint. Here I will start with a few examples, mentioned above where extra corporeal axes are working, and move towards the application of the principles of mechanics according to the contact point theory. First, however, the sketches of seesaw, drawbridge, old-fashioned well and joint, four constructions with extracorporeal axes of motion (as well as axles, above).

No joints, and especially not a ball and socket joint like the glenohumeral, function by a broad contact between the joint surfaces (Pieron 1973); the contact surface is very small, more like a point, a restricted area of contact that the ball is gliding at, the contact point. This contact point moves upwards on the caput, and upwards in the cavity during abduction. The lever becomes shorter, it is about 5 cm at 0° of abduction, and 2.5 cm at 90° of the abduction arc.

The contact point was discussed by Saha (1961), and Pieron (1973), but not used to decide the levers' lengths or to compute forces. The fact that the socket's radius is greater than the ball supports the contact point theory. According to this theory, the axis of motion is situated in the joint space, and almost punctual. Movements are possible in all direc-

tions, also rotational, as well as simultaneous gliding and rotation. It is impossible to imagine, in a ball and socket joint, with not exactly spherical parts, these motions to occur without using the contact point theory for the understanding, or to understand how a function should be possible, but according to this theory. A linear axis-axle would have to move very fast from gliding to rotation – or a number of separate axes-axles should be necessary.

For the study of the function of the glenohumeral joint the following items are prerequisite. The knowledge of these items as to spatial location and magnitude will make it possible to apply the principles of mechanics, and to calculate forces and loads, for example at equilibrium, and preferably in two dimensions.

The items are all necessary, if we miss the axis of motion, then the levers cannot be measured.

1. Axis of motion
2. Inner lever
3. Outer lever
4. Tendon insertion (point of attack)
5. Forces

The anatomy, then, to which the principles of mechanics are going to be applied, is of the utmost importance. However, the soft tissues only support the mechanical function, directed by the skeletal parts. These skeletal parts really support the soft tissues as the origin and insertion of muscles, for example. The form of the joint surfaces designs the motion and the movements; the shape of the skeleton juxta-articularly is capable of stopping the motion in the joint, and consequently the movement of the extremity. But above all, the skeleton is the steady and firm centre to which the principles of mechanics must be applied. The skeleton supplies the axis of motion, the levers, and the point of attack, all the mechanical items mentioned, except the forces.

For details about the soft tissues, the reader is referred to any textbook of anatomy, e.g. Gray (1973). The same is, I am afraid, also valid for the gross anatomy of the skeleton, except the few specific details considered especially in this study. Here follows an anatomical description, concentrated to functional details, and just like the mechanical introduction not consisting in a lot of names and terms, but in sketches, photos, and short descriptions that will be more explanative and comprehensible. The exact application and its anatomical details will be related in more detail in Experimental Model, but some general principles belong here, introductorily.

The point is that, during the work at the research laboratory, we have chosen to look at the whole complex situation from the skeletal point of view, as the skeleton undeniably gives the stability and carries the bedding for the mechanical properties. Certainly the soft tissues give cohesion, support, and muscular power, but mechanically – of interest for the application of the principles of mechanics – the skeleton is of the greatest importance. The male and female skeletal parts of the joint supply the axis of motion, which gives the levers' lengths. What remains of the prerequisite items for the application of mechanics is the point of attack (tendon insertion). Illustrations consider only the contact point theory, as an imaginary axis could not be illustrated by a photograph.

The tendon insertion belongs to Part II-III pp. 55 and 86, but will nevertheless be described here, as is necessary for the application of mechanical principles. The insertion is found to be located over the total surface of the greater tubercle, laterally, on the facets to the articular cartilage, and in the bicipital groove. The insertion is thus given an Y-shaped attachment area, and the conclusion is drawn that the resultant point of attack is located where the two branches of the Y meet. This rule is more likely to be valid inside the abduction arcs plane than outside it. The rule certainly not is without exceptions, but it is pro-

bable, reasonable, and useful, as it gives a defined location of the point of attack, which is needed for the measurements and the calculations. The length of the inner lever will change during movement, as will that of the outer lever to some extent. The non-spherical form of the caput will give somewhat different length of inner lever for different rotational positions (pronated or supinated).

The anatomical details of interest for this study are: the two muscles, the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus, which are pictured in the illustration below of the shoulder from behind with its muscles. The tendon insertion is related in detail in part III, as well as the glenoid cavity will be in chapter II, and the form of the cavity in Introduction, especially regarding its function, pp. 16-17. The anatomical relation of the greater tubercle to the cavity is essential for the end positions of skeletal origin. The form of the caput humeri and the fossa glenoidalis in relation to each other is essential to the entire function of the glenohumeral joint in man, and for the application of the principles of mechanics.

The difference in length between the short abductors and other muscles, such as the trapezius, the pectoralis major on the anterior side, the deltoid etc. is evident when looking at Figs. 13 and 14. Also the serrati and the rhomboids are longer and broader than the short abductors.

The mechanical relations are better displayed in the more schematic sketch, Fig. 15, where the classical axis of motion is also indicated. The difference as to the distance from insertion to classical axis and to the contact point is obvious. The same muscles are pictured. It is possible to compare length of the triceps brachii with the short abductors.

The skeletal form is best illustrated by some pictures taken by the author during the work at the Osteological Research Laboratory. These pictures illustrate the shape, the locking function, and the shape of the skeleton.

superficial layer of
dorsal muscles

Fig. 13 Superficial layer of long muscles to the scapula and the humerus.

Fig. 14 Deep layer of the short muscles, scapulo-humeral.

From Benninghoff (1949)

Fig. 15 Sketch of the relevant anatomy from Benninghoff (1949). Note the imaginary axis, centrally. The supraspinatus and in this position also part of the infraspinatus are above the imaginary axis. The real axis is situated cranially to the central, imaginary.

Fig. 16 Photo of a cut caput humerus in its cavity. Note the almost punctual contact, and the prominent greater tubercle, prone to engage with the meeting with the edge of the glenoid cavity. Tendon insertion on the lateral aspect, facet free, intra-articularly situated.

Fig. 17 Scapula and humerus with capsula and ligaments from the anterior.

These are the basic facts about the glenohumeral joint – if the shoulder joint is to be concerned, then we have to consider the mobility of the scapula which will be done, describing the skeletal end positions, where the scapular movement is an important issue for the ergonomics. In glenohumeral mobility and function, however, we are not entitled to mix in the thoracoscapular mobility or function. There is a difference, and the distinction should be maintained, otherwise the whole thing deteriorates and becomes incomprehensible. In the experiments to follow, the scapula always stands still as the function studied is the function of the glenohumeral joint. Regarding this joint two different axes at a defined plane, and rotational position are studied. That leaves no place for extra dimensions, or more than one joint. The muscles certainly are two but have the same function, depending on the rotational position.

A Chinese proverb tells: You can paint a flower, but never catch its scent. That might be true about painting in China, but in the western countries and regarding scientific abstraction it is both true and not true. The scent is perhaps not essential to the painting at all. To the scientific abstraction to be used in this study, a concretized abstraction in profiled steel of the idea of the glenohumeral joint, mechanically, no scent, no three dimensions, and no mobility of the scapula are necessary; on the contrary, these qualities would make the solution of the problem impossible. The whole thing is a question of priority for mechanically relevant and necessary items. These have been listed introductorily in this chapter. There is no point in utilizing three dimensions, and the incorrect axis of motion, or to mix in the scapulohumeral mobility if we are supposed to study the glenohumeral joint. We have to concentrate on the problem we want to solve.

The Experimental Model

After these additional anatomical elucidations we now are ready to approach the above mentioned application of mechanics to the anatomy just described. And note well, we are going to work in two dimensions, one joint and one muscle resultant. The experimental model is built in profiled steel, and will have the already mentioned dissimilarities compared to reality, and a few more, to be mentioned. The model will satisfy the listed prerequisites for the application of mechanics, however.

The skeletal reality we have to work with, then, is the glenoid cavity, the humerus and that is all. But in addition we have the soft tissues, primarily the labium glenoidale. These soft tissues certainly do have their importance for the function. Assume, for example, that the labium is a soft tissue structure round the glenoid cavity; it is much softer than bone, and will probably give at the skeletal end positions. The parts functioning from a mechanical point of view are the skeletal parts. The muscles, of course are of interest, and will certainly be related too. But if I had to give priority to some structure out of theoretical, mechanical point of view, then I would prefer the bone. The skeleton and its shape are given that priority, both in the approach to the application of the principles of mechanics, and regarding the skeletal end positions.

The humeral bone is rather special in *Homo sapiens*, with its torsion and general design. Its impressive features are both ends, the proximal with the caput and the tubercles and the rather big and somewhat irregular surface. The distal part impresses one by its delicate hinge joint with the trochlea and the capitulum. The epicondylar plane is chosen to represent the line of load, regarding combined functions of the humerus and the antebrachium.

The glenoid cavity is very small, but with a radius larger than that of the caput. The form of the glenoid cavity is excavated, its lateral pro-

Fig. 18 Scapula and caput from a 19-year-old male. The central, caudal part of the cavitas is circular, a corresponding circle has been drawn on the top of the caput humeri – to indicate the contact at "pure rotation" (simultaneous for shaft and caput).

jection being somewhat pear shaped. The caudal, central part of the cavitas is circular, the top of it, the stalk of the pear, is thinner; the circular part functions in "central movements", i.e. just about $30-60^{\circ}$ of abduction, where, ergonomically the force is best. Rotation will be "pure", i.e. shaft rotation and caput rotation will coincide within these circles too, if we include a corresponding circle on the top of the caput. Many movements take place outside these central circular zones – regarding the movement of the contact point, but many still occur within the circle in the cavity. To get the caput circle function, the arm will have to be abducted laterally. The above photo illustrates this, the circles were marked by the author (Fig. 18).

The premises, consequently, are settled: a punctual contact is supposed to exist between the caput and the glenoid cavity. According to this hypothesis of the existence of the contact point it is possible to apply the principles of mechanics. To check the classical theory, it is necessary to concretize the imaginary pin, as an imaginary device will give no information on the lever's length etc. The model was constructed with this possibility in mind, to allow experiments: 1) with the contact point as an axis, and 2) with a central axle (pin). From the methods and results that follow, the construction of the experimental model and the results will become apparent. As stated earlier, it was considered necessary to leave the three dimensions, to concentrate on one joint, and one muscle resultant, in order to make the calculation possible.

The materials are the experimental model, and the numerical values for forces at equilibrium, regarding different abduction levels of the abduction arc. Methods, then, will be the way to operate the model, obtain the numerical values – including the elaboration of the physical formulas, according to the parallelogram of forces. Eventually a method

for comparison of the different axes, and different levels, which proved to be effective to compare the two, was found in the loading curves.

1. The experimental model was constructed precisely for the above mentioned comparisons of axes: central versus intra-articular, and the load at different levels of the abduction arc. To construct it was somehow "the art of the possible" as a word for word translation of a Swedish expression for keeping within the bounds of possibility. With the aid of a skilful craftsman and mechanic the task was not too complicated. What I had to do was to use the craniophor and the diagraph, to get the silhouette or the form in two dimensions on the plane intended. Thereafter a few hours' work, and some experimenting together with the craftsman were needed, also deciding the length of the outer lever, the lever for application of the outer force, the abduction levels to be indicated $0-15-30-45-60-75-90^{\circ}$, and some arrangement for the application of the dynamometers, including the inner load.

2. The numerical values followed as a result of the work applying
3. The formulas for calculation of the loads, hereby practising
4. The operation of the experimental model

The experimental model was constructed to reflex the abduction arc, i.e. the abduction plane, orthogonal to the glenoid cavity, and the humerus moving two-dimensionally in a neutral position as to rotation. This means that the height of the facet area, the ridge between the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus area points cranially in the experimental plane, and the line between the epicondylae will be 10° supinated (outwards rotated). This outwards rotation is due to the humeral torsion. The abduction plane, consequently, is the plane intended by Henke, where the abduction stop occurs. The possible levels, then, will be those just mentioned. The aim was to find out the least loaded, and to compare the different axes of motion. To perform that comparison experimentally, they both have to be real - therefore the central, imaginary axis was represented by a pin in the experiments, central in what corresponded to the humeral head in the model. The deviation caused by not considering the evoluta was estimated to be very small in this joint. The practical difficulties involved by having a movable axle, however, would

Fig. 19-20 Photos 0° and 90° respectively, skeletal preparation of mature male subject, cleavage of the upper humerus in the plane of the abduction arc. The length of the levers, and the difference $90-0^{\circ}$ can be clearly seen. (The locking mechanism is obvious at 90° abduction.)

have been very great. If the contact point theory is used, the axle is the joint socket. The contact point is movable, length of inner lever changing from 5.0 to 2.5 cm in abduction from 0 to 90°, regarding the actual length, i.e. 100% increasing by lowering the arm from 90 to 0°. This is an important difference between the two theories of the axis of motion; according to the classical theory it is necessary to plant a pin in the centre, according to the contact point theory nothing has to be added, as the joint socket is already there (Fig. 19-20-21, pp. 36-37).

The experimental model fulfilled the functions I planned for it, in two dimensions, for one joint, and one muscular resultant, exactly as I learned in the course of mechanics in 1979 (Y. Chao). The model was built in profiled steel with a caput joint surface of PTFE (teflon), to reduce the friction, which was otherwise disregarded. The attributes were as simple as possible – ordinary dynamometers, fastenings with a screw and a loop respectively corresponding to the insertion for the short abductors – and the epicondylar plane was chosen as it represents the load line according to the contact point theory. Just the humeri length represented the outer lever, which was about 30 cm. The inner lever was changing according to the contact point theory, and fixed at 3 cm according to the classical theory. The angle of outer lever to outer load was chosen to be close to 90°, otherwise the model would have had to be very much larger. This is a deviation from reality, but it will be the same for

Fig. 21 The experimental model.

both axes. When the model was there I needed the formulae, which I had to deduce myself. Getting some values, and thinking the experimental situation over carefully was all that was needed. Some adjustments of the original model were necessary: a natural direction of the inner force is essential for the quotients, i.e. the loading curve. The photograph presents the principles for the construction of the model. The formulae for the calculation probably speak a clearer and more explanatory language than I could. They are commented, explained, and illustrated.

The formulae should compose the forces creating the inner momentum, and compare to the outer momentum. The factors in each momentum were: force, angle to lever, lever, and the same factors on the other side. In equilibrium these products should be of the same magnitude within 50 grams, which is about one per cent of the largest force (the inner, tractional load).

The formulae are (symbols will be explained in the figure below):

$$T \times \sin \alpha \times a = M = G \times \sin \delta \times OL \times \sin \beta$$

The contact point and the inner lever were chosen to be fix, other forces, and the outer lever were made orthogonal according to this fix centre, consecutively.

T = inner force (traction)

α = inner angle to a (inner lever)

G = outer force (gravity)

β = outer angle to a

a = inner lever

δ = outer force to outer lever

OL = outer lever

M = momentum

The same formulae are valid as principally the same relations exist, and the symbols are the same for central pin and contact point. Namely:

$$T \times \sin \alpha \times a = M = G \times \sin \delta \times OL \times \sin \beta$$

Fig. 22 The forces, levers, angles, etc. in the different methods for calculation of momenta in the model of the glenohumeral joint of man. It is to be noted, that the central pin method was pictured at 90° of abduction, the contact point method at about 60° of abduction, where the inner lever already has gained about 50% in length, compared to 90° abduction.

The levers and forces are arranged in relation to the inner lever which is not changed. This will give an orthogonal system where the parallelogram of forces is adapted. The system will permit a comparison of the momenta, as the forces, levers, and angles are known after measurements.

The work of measuring and calculating the forces and loads on the insertion of the short abductors was somewhat exacting. It was done once in 1979, and repeated in 1982. About the same results were obtained, though the method and the aids varied a little (the angle delta, and a more capable calculator in 1982). The difficulty in measurements was to define the contact point (movable), and consequently the length of the levers using this method. Otherwise there were no special difficulties, and the result soon proved to be quite reasonable.

The loading curve was needed to be able to compare different abduction degrees by their quotients. These quotients of outer to inner force could be plotted to make a curve, the loading curve. These curves for the different methods could be compared, which will be done in tables and diagrams. This comparison turned out in favour of the contact point theory and method.

The curves from 1982 will be shown last among the tables in this part. The best values are from 1982, when the outer angle was not standardized to 90° (orthogonal), but measured, though it was very close to 90° . There is only one series of measurements from 0 to 90 degrees for each curve, as too large loads were impossible using the contact point; a few kg as outer load would mean, say 30 kgf for the inner force. At such loads the caput of the experimental model had a tendency to luxate. Some higher loads were checked, and showed the same relation of 1:10 at the most for the transmission ratio, quotient outer to inner force. So, just a line of values of comparatively low load were considered enough to show, and to prove the relations of load at the abduction arc; and to give material for a definite comparison between the central pin method, and the contact pin method.

It is to be noted that the extremity's length is just the humerus; no friction and no kinetic energy are being regarded, and the outer angle (OL to outer force) is not natural, as it should follow gravity, i.e. the vertical line. Still, we consider these values to be more natural than any previously computed, which is valid for the contact point method. The outer force could just be decomposed, the calculations were, however,

Fig. 23 Sketches of the central pin method, and the contact point method, values for calculation at 90° and 60° of abduction, respectively.

troublesome enough without that "extra". To perform the experiments directly with a vertical force, a much larger model would be needed.

So the values will be presented the way they were calculated according to the description given. They will be presented in the order central pin - contact point measurements, calculated values for M according to the above formulae and definitions, loading curves and short discussion.

Results of the application of mechanics

Measurements for the central pin method

The values measured are length of levers, and the angles for forces and levers as already has been related. It is only the angle for the inner lever that changes, according to this method, so the values will be fairly uniform for all the others, as the pin is fixed.

TABLE 1. Metrical and angular values, according to the pin method, corresponding to the imaginary axis and the German, classical theory for the application of joint mechanics

Abd.	δ	OL (outer lever)	β	a (inner lever)	α
90°	90°	30.75	110°	3.0 cm	105°
75°	87°	—	—	—	85°
60°	—	—	—	—	75°
45°	—	—	—	—	60°
30°	—	—	—	—	50°
15°	—	—	—	—	40°
0°	90°	—	—	—	30°

TABLE 2. Calculations according to the formula $T \times \sin \alpha \times a = M = G \times \sin \delta \times OL \times \sin \beta$, and with the above values. As the values are constant, mostly constants were used for calculation. Constant₀ = 28.895; constant₁ = 28.856; the results are M; diff is the difference between M:s (allowed to be 1% of inner force), and the quotient outer force to inner force, the transmission ratio G:T

Abd.	G	Outer M	T	α	Inner M	Diff	G:T
90°	const ₀ x 190 = 5490.2;	1900 x 3 x sin	105° = 5505.8		18.9	0.10	
75°	const ₁ x 240 = 6925.4;	2225 x 3 x sin	85° = 6649.6		12.7	0.11	
60°	const ₁ x 275 = 7935.4;	2750 x 3 x sin	75° = 7968.9		33.5	0.10	
45°	const ₁ x 280 = 8079.7;	3100 x 3 x sin	60° = 8054.0		25.7	0.09	
30°	const ₁ x 280 = 5490.2;	3500 x 3 x sin	50° = 8043.5		36.2	0.08	
15°	const ₁ x 250 = 5490.2;	3750 x 3 x sin	40° = 7231.4		17.4	0.07	
0°	const ₀ x 210 = 5490.2;	4050 x 3 x sin	30° = 6075.0		7.1	0.05	

Note that the quotient G:T is highest at 90-60 degrees. This means that the transmission ratio is mechanically most forceful and gives the highest force for a constant load on the tendon insertion. Heavy work, consequently, should be performed at this level for ergonomic reasons, according to the central pin calculations. This will be discussed later on.

It is to be noted that a low transmission ratio means a low load (lowest possible for a certain force), and that a high transmission ratio (high gear) will mean high load, and high velocity, whereas the low ratio and low load mean low speed (as with a car). Conversely, the quotients defined by me will be high for a low load, and low for a high load, I found it more convenient to use quotients below 1.

It is at about this level (45°) that the load gets high according to the central pin experiments. At 0° the load is twice what it was at 90° . With a constant force the arm would accelerate in force during abduction, and the maximum force should exist at the highest abduction, 90° at the arc of abduction.

Measurements and calculation for the contact point method

The values measured are length of levers, and the angles for forces and levers, as related. All the values are changing from one abductions level to another. The contact point is constantly moving during motion in the joint.

The symbols have been related, and are the same as for the central pin method.

TABLE 3. Metrical and angular values according to the contact point method introduced in this study. It is considered to supersede the classical. Differences to the central pin values are given + and -.

Abd	δ	Diff	OL (outer lever)	Diff	β	a (inner lever)	Diff	α	Diff
90°	90°	0	32.5 cm	+1.75	65°	2.3 cm	-0.7	55°	50
75°	87°	0	32.4 cm	+1.65	70°	3.4 cm	+0.4	52°	33
60°	85°	-2	32.3 cm	+1.55	80°	4.2 cm	+1.2	49°	26
45°	83°	-4	32.2 cm	+1.45	85°	4.5 cm	+1.5	45°	15
30°	81°	-6	32.0 cm	+1.25	87°	4.9 cm	+1.9	40°	10
15°	83°	-4	31.5 cm	+0.75	90°	5.1 cm	+2.1	29°	11
0°	95°	+5	31.0 cm	+0.25	95°	5.3 cm	+2.3	21°	09

TABLE 4. Calculations according to the formula $T \times \sin \alpha \times a = M = G \times \sin \delta \times OL \times \sin \beta$, and with the above values. The same rules for difference have been adopted as used in the table for the central pin method; it should be less than 1% of the inner force. The quotient G:T denotes outer load : inner load; consequently it is below 1.

Abd	Outer M Inner M	Diff	G:T
90°	$\sin 90^\circ \times 270 \times 32.5 \times \sin 65^\circ = 7952.9$ $4200 \times 2.3 \times \sin 55^\circ = 5652.1$	39.9	0.06
75°	$\sin 87^\circ \times 290 \times 32.4 \times \sin 70^\circ = 8817.3$ $3300 \times 3.4 \times \sin 52^\circ = 8841.5$	24.2	0.09
60°	$\sin 85^\circ \times 280 \times 32.3 \times \sin 80^\circ = 8872.7$ $2800 \times 4.2 \times \sin 49^\circ = 8875.4$	2.7	0.10 Note!
45°	$\sin 83^\circ \times 380 \times 32.2 \times \sin 85^\circ = 12098.6$ $3800 \times 4.5 \times \sin 45^\circ = 12091.5$	7.1	0.1 --
30°	$\sin 81^\circ \times 620 \times 32.0 \times \sin 90^\circ = 19595.7$ $6200 \times 4.9 \times \sin 40^\circ = 19568.3$	27.4	0.1 --
15°	$\sin 83^\circ \times 300 \times 31.5 \times \sin 90^\circ = 9379.6$ $3800 \times 5.1 \times \sin 29^\circ = 9395.6$	16.0	0.08
0°	$\sin 95^\circ \times 250 \times 31.0 \times \sin 95^\circ = 7691.1$ $4050 \times 5.3 \times \sin 21^\circ = 7692.4$	1.3	0.06

Note that the quotient G:T is highest at 30-60 degrees. This means that the transmission is most forceful mechanically and gives the highest force for a given load, or lowest load on the insertion for a given outer load. Heavy work, consequently, should be performed at this level for ergonomic reasons, according to the contact point method. This will be discussed later on.

It is to be noted that a low transmission ratio means a high speed of the movement, and a high transmission ratio means a forceful movement, and relatively lower load on the insertion. It seems reasonable to expect a higher speed at high (and low) levels, and more force in the 30-60° sector, where the bench work is performed.

It is below this level that the load starts getting low according to the contact point theory, and the results of the experiments. At 30-60° the G:T quotient is 0.1 which is the highest value. With a constant inner force the arm would be more forceful at 30-60°, and more speedy at 0-30°, and 60-90°. Highest load and speed at 90°.

Experimental loading curves

I. The central, imaginary axis II. The contact point method

Values for G:T = outer load to inner load, that is transmission ratio, have been listed. Values were obtained by using the experimental model just described, and the related formulae for calculation of momenta. The direct visible values for related forces (or loads) represent the numerical values used for calculation of the quotient G:T (before orthogonalizing the system).

I. Loading curve for the experiments utilizing the imaginary pin method. The imaginary pin concretized by a pin of metal centrally in the head.

II. Loading curve for the experiments according to the contact point method, axis for motion, and axle, fulcrum in the joint socket.

The diagrams intend to demonstrate where the load is high-low at the abducent arc, which sector that has the highest-lowest load. They are, as to low load, high force ergonomically: 1. 60-90° for the imaginary pin, 2. 30-60° for the contact point. A high numerical value for G:T (0.1) is indicating a low load, according to the argument in the text before this.

Discussion

To start with, the classical theory of the application of mechanics should be scrutinized, not to criticise what might be wrong, but to find out with greater certainty what is right, and not only in the classical theory. The important insufficiency of the classical theory utilizing the central, imaginary axis, is that the axle, and consequently the inner lever are missing. It is not satisfactory to have to calculate with a cut muscle surface instead of a force and a lever when applying the principles of mechanics. The operation plane to approach and hopefully solve the problem of the axis of motion, was not theorizing about missing axles and cut muscle surfaces, but using experimental approach. This set-up was described fairly well in the description of the model. Here I would just like to point out once more: the model was constructed to give an exact answer to the difference between the classical, central, imaginary axis of motion on one hand, and on the other hand the new axis of motion for a joint, the contact point, previously discussed by Saha (1958), and Pieron (1973), but never actually used for measurements or calculations.

Some snags did exist, exemplified by the difficulty of arranging the outer load vertically, since the model would have been taking up too much space, and another rather ticklish measurement would have been brought in. Another example is the impossibility of considering the evoluta experimentally. The evoluta, then, is the dislocation in space of the imaginary axis during motion in the joint, because of the form of the joint surfaces. The evoluta does not deviate much in the glenohumeral joint, the central axis of which is almost fixed. Experimentally the axis had to be fixed for practical reasons, that is the axle, or central pin was not movable, which ought not reasonably to influence the calculations much, as the dislocation of the evoluta could be 1-3 mm, and the lever was 3 cm when the central axis of motion theory was used. The contact point moves automatically in the joint socket, and at the surface of caput, resulting in a length of inner lever from 2.5 cm at 90° of abduction to 5 cm at 0° of abduction. With a two-dimensional anatomical model of a section through the glenohumeral joint, there is no need for an extra axle or fulcrum; the joint socket is the fulcrum, the contact point is the axis of motion, and they both exist.

The principal theoretical difficulty with the experimental model is that it concretizes an abstract idea about the most important, and (for the application of the principles of mechanics) most relevant characteristics of the joint in question. To look at, the model is not much like a glenohumeral joint, nor do its functions seem to be so. It must be looked upon as a concretized abstraction of the most important functions of the joint, important for the application of the principles of mechanics. There is one joint, one muscle force and there are two dimensions. There is a possibility of adapting the outer force, and finding the equilibrium, where the forces should be equal.

There is no study in the previous literature comparable to this, as the axis of motion and the inner lever have not been defined earlier. The outer force has been calculated, but not the inner force – at least not according to the method now described. Consequently the imaginary pin method and the contact point method have not been compared either. Since no comparison can be made with earlier experiments, the thing to do is to get as much as possible out of the experiments and the comparisons in them, by establishing the loading curves and interpreting the values, comparing their effects and their respective level for maximal effect. The aim of the experimental model being just such comparisons, it was very stimulating to find out already in 1979 a clear tendency in both curves, and practically the opposite in that the load was low $30-60^{\circ}$ with the contact point, and $60-90^{\circ}$ with the imaginary pin.

The implication of this distribution of load in the respective curves for the two methods is that heavy work should, according to the imaginary pin theory, be performed just at 60-90 degrees of abduction at the abduction arc's plane, and most probably most other planes. According to the contact point method the sector of abduction suitable for heavy work should be 30-60°, where according to experience heavy work is carried out. If we believe in these arguments and calculations above, then it is very clear that the result of the loading curve, indicating 30-60 degrees as the ergonomically most favourable level for heavy work, tells us that this method of calculating loads must be the best of the two experimentally explored.

The practical consequences are ergonomical as to working positions, height of benches, etc. Another application will be in clinical therapy, to arrange a suitable bandage for shoulder tendinitis (see Clinical Epilogue for details, pp. 110-111). It is very lucky that the differences are as distinct as they really are, so that there will be no doubt as to the interpretation. In other words: it is totally impossible that the results of the calculation according to the imaginary pin could show the function of the joint. In that case all benches should be very high, about 1.5 to 1.75 meters which is advantageous for our backs but not realistic, as we would not be able to see the workpiece. The force is better utilized and supported by body-weight if we direct it downwards. From all points of view, teleological, ergonomical, mechanical, etc., the result that forces are best at higher levels of abduction at the abduction arc is unrealistic. The result 30-60°, contrarily, does not need explanation or argumentation. We all know: That's the way it is.

There is not much to be said about the calculations. The results were accepted with a difference of up to 50 grams, that is 1% of the inner force, and consequently up to 10% of the outer. Considering the premises, one could not demand that the momenta should be exactly similar; that would have been too exacting. According to the tables of results, however, the difference is mostly below 20, which is a bit better than the postulated demand for exactness. Within these limits the results are astonishingly precise, considering the difficulties involved in taking the measurements. Long plastic rulers, angular calipers were used. The point of attack was located over the edge laterally of the facets (explained already, see pp. 31-32). The contact point might be difficult to find exactly, as it was movable, and under certain conditions the caput could slide down too far in the fossa.

The calculation of static forces at equilibrium means that the kinetic energy is disregarded. The kinetic forces are in fact important, especially when they come below 30° or above 60°, where they often occur. I am thinking of a suddenly stopping bus where either the extremely high or the extremely low levels are loaded; these levels are aimed for high velocity (low G:T quotient). What I am thinking of, then, is the load on the insertion. More muscular force will be needed, and a higher load on the tendon insertion implied in action out of the sector 30-60°. The muscular force may be utilized as kinetic energy, or work - or both. At the high and low levels there will be more muscular force needed than in 30-60°. The load, consequently, will be higher on the insertion - and the risk for some kind of rupture increased.

The interesting thing to watch in the results is how the lever, the angles, and the relative forces change during abduction, and how differently they do it according to the different methods of calculating. The differences have been put in the table for the contact point, regarding the difference from imaginary pin values, excluding β values being almost constant. It is also interesting to see how few values change in the imaginary pin table, and almost fascinating to consider how the changes of levers, angles, and relative forces together create the loading curves.

Especially interesting and fascinating, then, is the contact point curve, pointing out its most plausible, and relevant facts.

Of possible loading curves I could imagine one having the low working load at $0-30^{\circ}$, and then increasing to 90° . Another one would be the opposite: high load at 0° , and low load at 90° , that is almost the imaginary pin's curve. The most ingenious, and practical seems to be the contact point curve, as the lowest load (most power) is in the middle of the abduction arc, where it is useful, i.e. the forces are needed for work – not so much for velocity. A working position with the arm close to the body would be no good. Teleologically the contact point curve is the best possible.

Practically, then, all this means that we have the greatest force $30-60^{\circ}$, and a given work will need less force at this level than below 30° , or above 60° . The tendon insertion, consequently, will receive the least load possible for any activity in this sector, work or rest. On the other hand, the velocity will be lower at $30-60^{\circ}$ of the abduction arc than at any other level, higher or lower. A given force by muscle contraction will give more dislocation in space, and consequently more speed at any other level. It is evident that the higher speed may be very advantageous at low level, starting the movement, and accelerating to grip something, etc. Likewise, it is obvious that velocity could be of use at high elevation for different purposes, such as catching a ball, to quote one example. In sword fighting, velocity is needed, and it is available to quote this high transmission ratio (cf. the car), corresponding to a low quotient G:T. Also in timber cutting velocity is essential. During the last mentioned performances we are out of the abduction plane. The same mechanical rules, however, are claimed to hold good in other abduction planes and rotational positions, even if the quotient should be clearly different from what it is in the abduction plane. The quotient is supposed to be higher, because of higher elevation, and different shape of the caput in these planes out of the abduction plane. The caput is, so to speak "highest" on the abduction arc's plane, in the neutral rotational position. At pronation the lever will most probably be shorter, and the load consequently higher. These things, however, will have to be studied in detail in a future, considering different planes and rotational positions. According to the methods described, it is necessary to study one plane and one position at the time; planes and positions are endless.

What has been found in this study, then, is that the previously almost cursorily mentioned contact point actually corresponds to the physiological axis of motion for the experimentally explored glenohumeral joint, and that it seems likely a counterpart will be found in other joints. This mechanical interpretation is most likely, in view of the experimental exploration, comparison between the classical theories, and the new contact point theory.

The fact that the quotient G:T is the same for $30-60^{\circ}$ seems reasonable. It is advantageous to have access to a sector of ergonomically favourable conditions before a narrow level, functionally. The decrease of the quotient G:T, and the increase of load and velocity, are gradual down to 0° , and up to 90° .

There is no need for three dimensions in calculations like those just accounted for. The parallelogram of forces is two-dimensional, and the orthogonal vector quantity actually one-dimensional. Compare the outboard motor and its starting string. It is always possible to put the string in a plane, and in that plane the string will be a line, one-dimensional. Accordingly, the three dimensions may advantageously be reduced to two for these calculations, which should be very complicated in three. Furthermore it is not necessary – or might even be wrong – to try to perform them in three dimensions. Summing up, what is needed is the forces, the

point of attack, the inner lever, the outer lever, and the axis of motion which is also needed for deciding the levers. This axis is necessarily situated outside the humerus.

Conclusions

1. The axis of motion for a joint is located between the joint surfaces, in the joint – at the contact point.
2. Three-dimensional methods for the application of mechanics to joints are possible, but will have to wait until we master the techniques in two dimensions better.
3. The axis of motion is the most important issue for the application of the mechanical principles. The axis of motion can preferably be studied in two dimensions – be placed wrong or right in a two-dimensional image of the joint.
4. The loading curves exhibit a definite dissimilarity for the two methods: central, imaginary axis, or contact point method. The results are most plausible when using the contact point method, according to what is to be expected from experience, for mechanical, and teleological reasons.
5. It was possible to perform a "pilot study" on the application of mechanics, and to compare the imaginary axis (classical, German) to the contact point method, utilizing the joint socket as a fulcrum. The central, imaginary axis was in the experiments represented by a metallic pin.
6. The classical, central, imaginary axis of motion is superseded by the contact point theory, implying an intra-articular axis of motion for a joint.
7. Thanks to the experimental model, it was possible to perform the pilot study, and to obtain the values which made it possible to calculate the loading curves.
8. The principles used, and the procedures and routines utilized to study the function of the glenohumeral joint and compute its values, are presented and explained. These principles, procedures, and routines can certainly be used on other skeletal joints as well, to compute the forces and loads on their respective tendon insertions.

PART TWO

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SKELETAL END POSITIONS

A movement of an extremity or the motion in a joint does not correspond to the ideal capacity valid e.g. for the hinge joint or the ball and socket joint, according to a mechanical hinge, or a complete spherical ball. It is obvious that the olecranon stops the extension at the elbow joint. It is equally evident that no skeletal structure could cause a direct stop for the motion in the knee joint at straight leg position; this has to be done by soft tissues. The posterior capsula is known to stabilize the knee joint more than any other structure, the skeletal shape could not possibly cause the stop at straight leg, or any other position in the knee joint. This implies that

1. there are skeletal end positions as well as soft tissue end positions,
2. there is a difference between the glenohumeral joint and the hip joint, as well as between the elbow joint and the knee joint in the occurrence and the cause of end positions.

The glenohumeral joint has more mobility, but also more skeletal lockings than the hip joint. They are both ball and socket joints. The femur's greater trochanter is 10-15 cm from the joint, whereas the humerus in the glenohumeral joint has its tubercles just at the edge of the joint. The total range of motion may still be larger in the glenohumeral joint, but more end positions (skeletal) occur because of its skeletal shape. Principally the hip will be stopped skeletally only by the collum; the glenohumeral joint, on the other hand, by its tubercles hitting the edge of the cavity, and bracing, which is called the pawl function of the tubercles in this study.

Of pathological stops for the motion in a joint, those induced by the soft tissue definitely predominate. In manual medicine, different kinds of end feeling are spoken of. The stop might be skeletal – or due to a torn meniscus in the knee joint, for example. Other possible stops, such as shrinkage of the fibrous capsula or a contract muscle, are all pathological. There are, however, also physiological soft tissue end positions. The pathological skeletal end positions are very few; they could possibly occur after severe fractures and mal-union with dislocation, or in very pronounced osteo-arthritis. In moderate to severe arthritis the glenohumeral joint, for example, seems to rebuild, presenting the same skeletal end positions as any healthy joint.

Considering from now on just the physiological, skeletal end positions, these have been cursorily mentioned in previous literature, with one important exception: Henke (1863), describing and defining, and furthermore explaining one skeletal end position of the glenohumeral joint, the abduction stop at 90° in the abduction arc's defined plane, in a defined rotational position. These facts are necessary for describing and defining a skeletal end position as to the principle – for a more precise definition, angular measuring of more than one joint is needed. Henke stated clearly that the stop was caused by a meeting between the greater tubercle and the edge of the glenoid cavity. His statement, however, seems to have been ignored in the 1930s. There is seldom, if ever, a

reference to Henke (1863) in the literature. He seems to have been forgotten. As nobody but Henke obviously was aware of the skeletal end positions, or possibly could be, as the acromion has been held to be the skeletal part that the greater tubercle braces against, their ergonomic consequences for the joint could hardly even have been suspected.

More recently, MacConaill (1969) discussed the skeletal origin of end positions. His theory implies a congruence between the joint surfaces, causing a stop for motion in the joint any further in that direction in which the stop was arrived at. He coined the denotation "close packed position", which was already defined for several joints according to this theory before (1969). The close packed position for the glenohumeral joint corresponds exactly to the spear throwing position of the glenohumeral joint of this study, i.e. supinated (outwards rotated) position, $80-90^{\circ}$ of abduction, and backwards conduction to the stop. This tells us that two persons, independently, have found the same skeletal locking position, be its cause congruence or incongruence.

End of circumduction - a skeletal end position

In the literature there are apparently no other skeletal end positions described, or more correctly: defined. The end position of circumduction, however, has been related in various writings. The most complete description was given by Hjortsjö (1964) - quoted in the introduction, see p. 22. It is to be noted that if the circumductional movement shall stop at the end, at half a cone of circular movement of the hand, consequently half-circular, it is necessary to start with the palm of the hand dorsally and to end the movement with the palm of the hand directed ventrally. This corresponds to a clock-wise semicircular movement, and a rotation of the hand of 180° , also clock-wise. The implication must be that, during the semicircular movement of the hand in the air, the palm of the hand and the whole extremity in its joints have rotated 180° . Here follows a really difficult part of Hjortsjö's text: "The movement produced is a pure circumduction movement" (Fig. 24a, p. 52). "In that connection, however, a rotation can also occur about the long axis of the arm so that the palm throughout the course, remains directed dorsad" (Fig. 24b, p. 52).

Both circumduction, and longitudinal rotation about the axis of the extremity are clock-wise. If rotation occurs clock-wise about the long axis, simultaneously with the circumduction movement, when the hand describes a semicircle in the air (half the base of a cone), also clock-wise, then the locking will occur. If the rotation of the extremity does not occur, then it will be possible to circle the hand in the air in a complete circle. So, without rotation of the arm, there will be no locking at the end position. The supination (outwards rotation) is prerequisite for the locking. What actually happens will be discussed later on. Suffice it to say here once more that the supination is prerequisite for the locking, and that 90° is carried out in the elbow joint, and 90° in the glenohumeral joint. The humerus has then arrived at a $80-90^{\circ}$ supinated position, bringing the greater tubercle in position for bracing.

The anti-clockwise rotation described by Hjortsjö is very interesting, as it seems to be a consequence of using the idea of an intracorporeal axis of motion, in the centre of the convex skeletal part. Where the apex of the cone is located, according to my theories, should not be too hard to understand. It has to move, however, and I would rather not discuss exactly how. Maybe the caput only rotates, or moves in a small circle. According to the imaginary axis theory, however, there will necessarily be a noticeable rotation of the point where the elongation of the extremity's long axis meets the cavity - almost circular dislocation, and anti-clockwise.

Circumduction - skeletal end position - forehand drive position

What circumduction is, what happens during circumduction movement, and how it looks will be made clear in the following text. The illustrations from Hjortsjö's Motion and Movement (1964) explain the situation stereogeometrically. The sketches and photos are to explain the exterior, and just indicate the skeletal anatomy. It has to be pointed out, that the circumductional movement will be easier for the reader to understand if he does some experiments with his own arm. The illustrations will be found after the introductory text.

Primarily, the rotation is clock-wise; the movement of circumduction is already marked as clock-wise in Hjortsjö's sketch. The type of movement is possible in all ball and sockets joints, as a rotation of the extremity is needed according to definition. The circumduction movement, actually, is when the extremity describes a cone with its apex in the joint. For the arm that means that the hand will describe a circle in the air. During this circling the arm is free to rotate or not. If it rotates 80° , the movement stops at half a circle, at the skeletal end position of circumduction, which is identical with the forehand drive position of this study (if circumduction is performed at 50° of abduction).

Precisely this fact, that the end position of circumduction at 50° is the forehand drive position, aroused my interest in this position, and how it was arrived at. The function will be described as to the rotation, abduction, and backwards conduction, which are the three positions defining the spatial position of the arm.

It is totally clear that the palm of the hand and the humerus rotate simultaneously, and that they rotate if the movement stops after half a circle of circumduction, or better: the circumductional movement stops if the arm and the hand rotate; the rotation and the circumduction are both clock-wise. The movement starts with the palm of the hand dorsad, and ends with the palm ventrad, as stated by Hjortsjö. That is 180 degrees of clock-wise rotation.

The rotation of the hand is accomplished by rotation in the glenohumeral joint, and rotation in the elbow joint, about 90° each. This can be checked by palpation of the greater tubercle moving, and the capitulum radii rotating, both movements being recognizable as outwards rotation (supination). If the rotation exceeds 180 degrees this can be due to a start before zero (palm in the vertical plane) by pronated position (too much inwards rotated) of the arm-hand at start (which is always possible), or at the other end of the movement: an extreme supination of the elbow joint. Females are prone to surpass males regarding this rotation, as well as the more proximal rotation in the glenohumeral joint, which may be a few degrees more in females, restricted, however, by the following reasoning. The skeletal end position puts a stop not only to the backwards conduction, but also to the outwards rotation. Circumduction can be performed at different abductional levels. The possible supination varies between 0 - 45 - 90 degrees of abduction. More supination is possible at 0° , and 90° than at 50° abducted position, due to the skeletal shape's fit. The broadest contact is at 90° of abduction, and 45° backwards conduction, the forehand drive position. The outwards rotation, then, is 90° at 0 and 90 degrees of abduction, but just 80° at 50 degrees of abduction. Note well, thumb upwards = supinated position; little finger upwards = pronation (thumb down).

The rotation during circumduction - direction and importance

Concerning the theory that no rotation of the extremity per se should occur in the circumduction to an end position, and that an anti-clockwise

rotation should have to occur to prevent the clock-wise rotation, it is to be stated that a clock-wise circling in the air of the hand creates the circumduction. Herein the arm is free to rotate round its own axis – or not. If the arm rotates fully, and clock-wise, the stop occurs, otherwise not. If there is no supination (outwards rotation) during the circumduction, the arm will continue, and the hand describes a complete circle (base in a cone) in the air. The greater tubercle will not be in position for the pawl function if no rotation occurs. The supination brings the greater tubercle in a position where it will meet the edge of the cavity by backwards conduction. Movements have to be carried out fully, which implies a rotation of 80° outwards (at 50° of abduction), otherwise the hand will go on in circles.

The circumductional movement and its end position, the forehand drive position, are very important, and occur commonly – not only in tennis. The same is true of spear throwing. These end positions are used in heavy pushing, and towing as well.

Fig. 10. Schematic reproduction of the circumduction movement.

a. Pure circumduction movement. The movable disc moves in a circular path as a result of rotary movement about axle B. Thus an axle A at right-angles to the disc, but running obliquely to axle B, describes in space the surface of a cone (see text). b. Circumduction movement as in example a. Also a rotary movement about axle A (see text).

Fig. 24 a - b. Circumduction movement, from Hjortsjö (1964). The motion in the joint will be anti-clockwise only in case of central axis of motion.

Fig. 25 Photo (Lars Wiklund). The sword draught position (discovered by Sjøvold 1979). This end position is very clearly seen, as there are no skeletal parts hindering the view.

Fig. 26 The sword draught approaching the end position in a skeletal preparation. Note the lesser tubercle and the groove between the circular part and the stalk of the pear.

Fig. 27 Abduction 90° . Henke, approaching in the craniophor.

Fig. 28 The skeletal end position. Abduction 90° . Note ridge of supra-infraspinatus towards the top of the glenoid cavity. Skeletal preparation in the craniophor. Photo by the author.

Anatomy

It might be appropriate, and maybe of value, to discuss the anatomy before the results and the discussion.

We now know that skeletal end positions exist, manifesting themselves in some specific movements and sport functions. The basic example chosen is that of the forehand drive position; we know by now how this movement is performed – and how it is arrived at without playing tennis. It is the end position of circumduction; we just have to circumduct the arm to behind the body in a supinated position, at an abductational level of just above 50° . If we hereby simultaneously rotate the arm and hand outwards, then we arrive at a locking at about 45° backwards conduction. That is the forehand drive position. The reader is recommended to check

the scapula so that it does not move, to keep the other arm's hand steady on the acromion; that will make the whole scapula stand still. Make a circle in the air with the hand and rotate 180° from a start, palm dorsad to an end position with the palm ventrad. Rotation occurs in the elbow joint and the glenohumeral joint, the humerus will rotate 80° and the missing 100° or so are to be found in the elbow joint.

The principle idea of this study about the end positions is that the greater tubercle hits the edge of the glenoid cavity, and functions as a pawl; there is a bracing, and a locking. The end position is rather firm, and has to be unlocked just the way it was arrived at.

The anatomical features, consequently, are the greater tubercle and the edge of the glenoid cavity. They are well-known, but will nevertheless be briefly described, perhaps adding new points of view. It is totally clear that Henke's description from 1863 is complete and correct. It is obvious that other locking conditions occur in the glenohumeral joint, and they are fairly easy to observe – when sitting with a preparation, testing where the greater tubercle hits the edge of the glenoid cavity. From the top of the cavity, and the dorsal part of its edge occurs the skeletal locking in spear throwing and the forehand drive position, which are lockings in backwards conducted positions. Supination is necessary to bring the tubercle in position (by outwards rotation). Pronation and forward conduction bring different skeletal end positions. The various skeletal end positions have different parts of the top of tubercle as their pawl. For example the ridge between supraspinatus and infraspinatus constitutes the pawl at the abduction stop (Henke, 1863), as well as the larger infraspinatus facet meets the circular part of the fossa glenoidalis in the forehand drive position.

The lesser tubercle really fits in a groove at the edge of the cavity (see Fig. 25-26 p. 53) between the stalk of the pear, and the circular part. More end positions of skeletal origin were not considered, as the ones at backwards conduction seemed most clear, and most important; important by giving extra force to the forward conduction, which is a more useful movement than the backwards conduction. The addition of force to forward conduction is also easier to study and confirm by experimenting and watching, for example a game of tennis.

The soft tissues have been stated to be of secondary importance to the mechanism of the joint. They are still of enormous significance for its function. Considering the skeletal end positions, I had to convince myself that the soft tissues would permit the assumed function. This should mean that the facets could function as pawls and tendon insertion. From a skeletal point of view there was no objection. A check had to be made to see whether there was any obstruction from the soft tissues. This was done by a dissection at the section table (autopsy). The result of the dissection should be clear from the photographs on page 56, but will nevertheless be related in the text.

The incision is a sabre cut (classical incision) from above, dividing the collum acromion, opening the capsula, and entering the joint. The short abductors constituting the roof of the joint have been divided, as has the teres minor partly. The protuberances of the greater tubercle's facets can be seen, covered by soft tissues such as the shining serous capsula. They are intra-articularly located, which means that they are free to meet the edge of the glenoid cavity. The next step was to try to loosen the fibrous capsula, tendon, and ligamental tissue from the surface of the facets. This was impossible. The tissues in question, somehow meniscus-like in consistency and located in the joint, could not be freed with a large section knife, they were really adherent. This must be interpreted in favour of the assumed functions of tendon insertion and pawl in the mechanism of the skeletal end positions.

Fig. 29-30 Section preparations of the left glenohumeral joint of a 40-year-old male.

Fig. 29 The joint opened as described in text, the shining surface of the serous capsula covering the facets (greater tubercle) is visible.

Fig. 30 The attempt to remove the soft tissue from the facets' surfaces.

The result of this investigation is interpreted as clear evidence of the existence of functions assumed to exist and prerequisite for the mechanism of the skeletal end positions. The study of the distribution of degenerative marks is certainly better performed with the aid of dry, macerated bones (rather than fresh bone).

The soft tissue anatomy of importance for this investigation is that just related. All juxta-articularly located soft tissue structures such as the labium glenoidales, other insertions such as the subscapularis, the long triceps, etc., have not been examined. This would go too far, and the study concentrates on the short abductors, the greater tubercle, and the bicipital groove where the degenerative changes are located, being the aim of the investigation in Part III.

Very important – and more important than the stop and locking of the backwards conduction – is the locking of the humerus with the scapula at forward conduction as a consequence of the locking at the backwards conduction. This locking certainly has an enormous significance for the ergonomics of the glenohumeral joint. It supplies the capacity for spear throwing and other forward directed movements adaptable on heavy pushing and towing, as it increases the stability and the force.

It is difficult to evaluate how much the force increases for the specific movement by this mechanism. The mass of the muscles propelling the movements, however, is more than doubled by adding, for example the pectoralis major and the thoracoscapular muscles in spear throwing. Even if the subscapularis is added to the short abductors, the relation should be at least 1:2. The value of this mechanism could hardly be overestimated. The sword draught would not have much force, compared to what it now has, if this mechanism did not function (even if it is a somewhat reversed function compared to spear throwing), and consequently the latissimus dorsi, etc. could not give their forces to this movement. There are several skeletal end positions giving stability and force to different movements of the arm. Of these positions only two have been described, related and defined, besides the original abduction stop. These two are in backwards conduction: spear throwing and the forehand drive in tennis. There are no measurements of the relative forces available for the forward conduction with and without this mechanism of the skeletal end positions, as the mechanism is introduced with this study; besides it was considered to be beyond the scope of it, just to try to measure the relative forces, which must be quite an undertaking. This study will relate some of the most common skeletal end positions, and define them by their angular values.

It will be for another study to relate and measure the relative forces. So much can be said, however, that the difference is very noticeable without this mechanism, for example at the forehand stroke. It is the backhand stroke, as we all know, that is sometimes performed with two hands. Also, the backhand has a possible skeletal support, but in the same position as where a sword is drawn, at maximal adduction. This skeletal support evidently cannot follow the movement far enough forward, which is why the backhand is often supported by the other hand. Note well, this support is reversed in that the scapula leads. The longer muscles, such as the deltoid, teres major, etc. can certainly stabilize the position, which, however, is not as stable as the locking in forward conduction, where the humerus leads the movement.

Spear throwing would be impossible without the locking mechanism. Imagine the complete rotator cuff (short abductors and subscapularis), and compare with the pectoralis, the serrati, and the trapezius added. The position at which this locking occurs is fairly fixed as to rotation, 90° , and backwards conduction, 10° – but varies from 70° to over 90° considering the abduction degree. Throwing, for example the throwing of a stone, is performed at a lower abduction degree than the throwing of a spear. That is to be remembered when measuring the abduction levels for just spear (javelin) throwing. Throwing a spear is, according to my theories, a certain criterion of the creature doing so belonging to the species *Homo sapiens*, provided the throwing is performed somehow like the javelin throwing in an athletic contest. The gorilla and the chimpanzee, for example, have four facets on their tuberculi, and no distinct edge as human tubercular facet surfaces have.

The extra force achieved by the mechanism of the skeletal end positions can today only be estimated by calculating the muscle mass. Interior computing will be very difficult, and almost impossible as the EMG is just

a qualitative method (Knutsson, 1976). External methods should be more easy, but still complicated enough – and probably extremely exacting.

Skeletal measuring

The method for skeletal measurements was without any support, except the examiner's hand and arm; left arm-hand for left humeroscapular joint etc. A transparent angular caliper of a type used by geologists, sufficiently long as to the arms (rulers) was used. It was consequently possible to aim at the planes through the ruler, and to read the values also. The longitudinal axis of the humerus was defined to be from the bicipital groove to between the trochlea and the capitulum humeri, an externally visible line, marked with a rubber band (see Fig. 31). This axis has also been used for other angular measurements and proved useful. Difficulties were encountered in manipulating the preparation into position – and to keep the position during measurement. The measuring was performed six times through the material, not six measurements on each occasion, which gave an even distribution of the examiner's capacity and an adequate number of measurements, and also an opportunity of comparing the different individual joints.

Fig. 31 The rubber band from the centre of the bicipital grooves centre to between the trochlea and the capitulum humeri, indicating the long shaft axis of the humerus.

Naturally it was felt necessary to make systematic observations of living subjects before starting to measure the skeletal material, consisting of 92 joints, i.e. 4 968 angular measurements. The post mortem investigation had already confirmed the possibility of the facets to working as pawls; they were free, intra-articularly located to meet the edge of the cavity. The check-up on living subjects fitted with the skeletal theories, and what was very important, there seemed to be appliances in sport and daily life of the new skeletal end positions. To watch a game of tennis was to get the ideas and principles of the importance of the skeletal shape confirmed. Eventually it seemed astonishing that nobody had found it out already, at least I was told so many times, after having explained the whole thing. This must have been found out, was the usual comment, not any comments implying incorrect ideas; they seemed somehow self-evident to most people. This self-evidence was a confirmation, so the comprehensive measurings were initiated.

During the measuring, however, it became clear that, regarding spear throwing, too much liberty of abduction level was permitted by the

skeletal shape to correspond to just spear throwing. The first two positions: abduction 90° , and spear throwing are effectuated by the meeting between the ridge between supraspinatus and infraspinatus parts of the facet area, and the top or dorsal edge of the spear's stalk of the cavity; this will give a free choice from 70° to over 90° as to abduction regarding spear throwing. Spear or javelin throwing is most certainly performed at a high degree of abduction, say $80-90^{\circ}$. Other casting may be performed at a lower degree of abduction. So the abduction levels were selected to be $80-90$ degrees for spear throwing. This is to be remembered, as it appears again in the statistical results.

The third end position of skeletal origin, the forehand drive position, is created by a broader contact, namely between the larger infraspinatus facet and the dorsal, circular part of the edge of the glenoid cavity. This gives the most stable end position as to the skeletal contact, which will show in the clinical measurements for reasons to be discussed. The three skeletal end positions covered by this study, and of which the measurements have been made, are located from the top of the cavity and downwards to the forehand drive position's contact more caudally at the edge of the cavity. There are end positions of skeletal origin at backwards conducted position for functioning forward, and also at forward conducted position for functioning forward and backwards. The sword draught functions back-wards, but the punch in boxing certainly works forward. Details of these things are considered beyond the scope of this study.

Clinical measuring

The clinical material for the measuring of skeletal end positions consisted of 30 subjects, 20-70 years of age. That is 60 joints, as many as the skeletal. The number of measurements per joint and position, however, is just two because of the time consumed per measurement. Initially four measurements were planned, but this proved impossible to carry out owing to the time it really took to perform the measurements, fifteen minutes or more per side. With a short break four measurements would have meant 1 hour per individual. For all practical reasons, half an hour per patient was almost too long. It is to be noted that two measurements per position actually means 36 measurements per subject, three positions with three angular measurements each are nine, multiplied by two are 36 measurements per subject. The limited number of measurements makes it more necessary - and more likely - that they will be as correct as possible. As experience, incidentally, was lacking on this kind of measurements, it has to be commented here that too many measurements could possibly spoil the whole investigation. The clinical measuring was perhaps even more complicated than the skeletal. In the clinical measuring one was more or less blind-folded, i.e. had to "guess" the tangential plane. The length of humeri length axis was easier, as it was defined on the surface (definition with the skeletal measurements, and photo). There are, however, landmarks, palpable and capable of giving information for these measurements. Professor Harald Brodin kindly not only allowed me to perform the measurements at the Red Cross Hospital in Stockholm, furnished the patients and provided the working space, he also advised me and discussed the possible methods of succeeding in the rather complicated undertaking of measuring the angles. The first principle was that the central part of the spina scapulae was perpendicular to the tangential plane of the glenoid cavity. The second principle that in the vertical plane it is possible to check up the cavity's plane by palpating the margo medialis (vertebralis) scapulae, which with its tangential line is approaching the tangential plane of the cavity cranially with an angle less than 20° . Furthermore the acromion, the coracoid, and even the cavity are palpable. With all these aids it was possible to decide the position of the tangential plane and the

Fig. 32 The scapula from behind. Note the spina scapulae, margo medialis, and the subarticular tuberosity.

shaft axis of the humerus in relation to it. The procedure, however, was somewhat time-consuming, and did not allow more than two measurements for each position. There are a few more principles available to decide the planes, any inquiry will be answered hereon, but it seems meaningless to try to relate them here. The anatomical sketches from Benninghoff (1949) - Fig 32 i.a. - of the skeletal anatomy will elucidate the above mentioned anatomical aspects.

The measurements were taken 2 x 3 x 3 for each side without changing the position more than necessary. The patient was seated beside an adjustable bench with hard pillows to support the arm examined. The successive routine in clinical measuring might have had some improving influence on the results, but what is more certain is that the comprehensive skeletal measuring rendered qualifications for the clinical measuring. The skeletal measuring was performed first, and the clinical a few months later. The longitudinal shaft axis of the humerus was indicated with a rubber band on skeletal preparations. The same line was used in clinical measuring: from the bicipital groove to between the capitulum humeri and the trochlea, a palpable longitudinal axis, visible on the skeletal preparations and easy definable. An angular caliper of the type used by geologists was used, with the long arm fully covering the distances concerned. The distance, then, being from the imagined contact point to the distal humerus, the angular values were measured for forward-backwards conduction and abduction. The rotation was measured with the aid of the position of a line through the epicondyles, in relation to the "zero" position. This is a very good method for determining the rotational position. It is to be remembered, however, that the humeral torsion requires the lower arm to be 10° outwards rotated at "zero" position (indicating 10° of supination of the humerus).

This means that at the abduction plane there is always, in the neutral rotational position, a stop at 90° for abduction. This is defined 90-10-0° where 90° is the abduction level, 10° is the forward conduction,

and 0° is rotation outwards (supination), or neutral rotational position.

Spear throwing is defined $85 - 10 - 90^\circ$, where 85° is the abduction level, 10° is the backwards conduction, and 90° is the outwards rotation (supination). The forehand position is defined $50 - 45 - 80^\circ$; 50° is the abduction level, 45° backwards conduction, and 80° is the outwards rotation. It is to be noted that the skeletal end positions at backwards conduction imply maximal outwards rotation, which certainly tightens the capsula.

Statistical methods

The null hypothesis was that the observed figures in each group were in fact equal. Testing was carried out utilizing the 95% level, corresponding to a probability of 5% (or $p = 0.05$) that the observed difference should occur by chance, given that the null hypothesis is correct. If p is found to be less than 0.05, the hypothesis is rejected and the values are considered different. The significance level is chosen according to usual practice.

The figures were tested according to the F-test, with numbers of degrees of freedom depending on the number of groups involved as well as the number of measurements and individuals.

The formulas for the statistical calculation are:

$$\text{Total variation ST} = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij}^2 - M$$

$$M = mn \left(\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} \right)^2$$

$$\text{Sum of } i\text{-th group} = S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij}$$

$$\text{Variation in } i\text{-th group SP} = \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{S_i^2}{n_i} - M$$

The F-distribution is calculated according to the formula:

$$p = Q(x) = \int_x^\infty \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{v_1 + v_2}{2}\right) y^{\frac{v_1}{2} - 1} \left(\frac{v_1}{v_2}\right)^{\frac{v_1}{2}}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{v_1}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{v_2}{2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{v_2}{2} y\right)^{\frac{v_1 + v_2}{2}}} dy$$

p or $Q(x)$ is the test value, deciding the significance in per cent.

Degrees of freedom are: 1. clinical material $v_1 = 1 (2-1)$, $v_2 = 60$ (number of n:s) or observed, individual joints. $D_f = 1 \times 60 = 60$ clinically. Skeletal material, columns = 6, $v_1 = 6-1 = 5$, and $v_2 = 60$ (number of joints). Skeletal $D_f = 5 \times 60 = 300$. That makes a very much higher degree of freedom for the skeletal material, which will have its consequences.

Results

Skeletal material

The means for each group of six angular values of the skeletal measuring, including the means and standard deviations, are listed separately. Analysis of variance for abduction 90° , spear throwing, and forehand drive abduction degrees, are listed below. The angular values are 360 for each position, making a total of 1 080.

The total angular measurements, including forward-backwards conduction and rotation of 92 skeletal joints, are listed at the end of the entire study, as they occupy more than ten pages, and not all values are used for the calculations as some individuals were too young. The angular values in the complete tables, anyhow, are $3 \times 3 \times 6 \times 92 = 4\ 968$. Three angular positions, measured six times for three different angular values at each position give this total.

Statistical analysis of the angular values of the skeletal material listed after text concerning abduction levels for 60 joints gives:

Abduction 90°	Mean 93.97 $\pm$ 3.4	Mean values for abduction in each position at skeletal locking
Spear throwing	Mean 85.61 $\pm$ 3.5	
Forehand drive	Mean 54.66 $\pm$ 2.2	

These values are similar to the corresponding means in the clinical material.

The means and the statistical analysis concern just the abduction levels, no forward-backwards or rotational position. The one-way analysis of variance, then, of the 1 080 angular values concerns the respective three groups of abduction 90° , spear throwing, and forehand drive. The analysis of variance resulted in the following values for the respective positions:

Abduction 90° according to Henke:	F = 1.89	p $\cong$ 0.1
Spear throwing:	F = 1.06	p $\cong$ 0.4
Forehand drive:	F = 1.53	p $\cong$ 0.2

It will be seen immediately that the value for spear throwing is rather high, and the value for abduction 90° is rather low. Both, however, are far above 0.05, where the limit for likeness is. Below 0.05 the values are unlike, the null hypothesis is not valid. Above 0.05, on the other hand, the similarity of the angular values is mathematically clear, according to the criteria set before the calculation.

Skeletally, the values do not need any further comment except that spear throwing has the highest p value, the reason for which has been given. Abduction is prone to be most inexact, as the skeletal contact is rather small.

The material consists of three age groups, 21-35, 36-50, and 51-70 years, 5 males and 5 females in each group = 30 subjects. This is valid for the skeletal material, the clinical has got 5 age groups, each decade from 20 to 70.

Abduction levels for the three movements to be defined as to their end positions, namely abduction 90° , spear throwing, and forehand drive, are listed below as means of six measurements, which have been used for the statistical calculation. The total skeletal material consists of 92 joints. To match the clinical material and furnish the right ages 60 joints have been picked out to get just 5 males and 5 females in each of the age groups 21-35, 36-50, and 51-70 years, which makes 60 joints.

Presented in the below tables are the means and the standard deviations of each group of six measurements for each joint. After text the

measurements are tabulated, as well as complete skeletal material, including measurements of abduction degree, forward-backwards conduction, and rotational position. The clinical material comprising a much less number of measurements will be presented in extenso later in the text of this part.

It could be of some interest to see the means and the standard deviations in the individual groups (for each joint) of six measurements, and to compare between different joints, individuals, and different movements, which is what actually is done by the analysis of variance to be calculated for each of abduction, spear throwing, and forehand drive.

So the means and the standard deviations are listed below for the 60 skeletally measured joints from the Westerhus material used for the statistical analysis. 100 is the male-female separation line. Below 100 is a female individual, and above 100 is a male (as a general rule). The pattern will consequently be five numbers below and five numbers above 100, as females comes before males in the lists. The complete lists of measurements will be found separately after text.

TABLE 5. Skeletal abduction levels

Westerhus No.		Abduction 90 ⁰	Spear throwing	Forehand drive
32	dx	92.50 $\pm$ 2.07	84.83 $\pm$ 1.69	53.92 $\pm$ 1.80
	sin	93.00 $\pm$ 4.41	84.50 $\pm$ 1.38	54.25 $\pm$ 1.21
62	dx	93.50 $\pm$ 1.87	83.00 $\pm$ 2.45	54.00 $\pm$ 1.67
	sin	93.58 $\pm$ 1.63	87.25 $\pm$ 3.40	55.17 $\pm$ 2.46
44	dx	92.30 $\pm$ 3.67	82.67 $\pm$ 2.66	54.83 $\pm$ 3.43
	sin	95.67 $\pm$ 3.01	84.17 $\pm$ 2.86	54.83 $\pm$ 3.53
71	dx	97.00 $\pm$ 5.25	83.83 $\pm$ 3.19	54.67 $\pm$ 1.50
	sin	95.25 $\pm$ 2.82	84.67 $\pm$ 2.94	53.83 $\pm$ 1.47
52	dx	94.90 $\pm$ 0.92	85.08 $\pm$ 2.42	53.83 $\pm$ 3.54
	sin	96.08 $\pm$ 2.54	86.58 $\pm$ 3.47	55.83 $\pm$ 1.60
109a	dx	92.60 $\pm$ 4.22	84.67 $\pm$ 3.14	53.17 $\pm$ 1.33
	sin	93.40 $\pm$ 2.73	86.42 $\pm$ 4.80	53.5 $\pm$ 1.84
111	dx	93.33 $\pm$ 3.61	86.08 $\pm$ 3.00	54.50 $\pm$ 2.07
	sin	91.30 $\pm$ 2.07	84.67 $\pm$ 2.25	53.75 $\pm$ 1.89
213	dx	94.30 $\pm$ 2.42	86.67 $\pm$ 2.66	54.67 $\pm$ 2.80
	sin	94.30 $\pm$ 2.42	86.33 $\pm$ 5.24	54.67 $\pm$ 2.50

Westerhus No.		Abduction 90 ⁰	Spear throwing	Forehand drive
156	dx	93.83 $\pm$ 2.64	84.83 $\pm$ 2.40	55.75 $\pm$ 2.04
	sin	96.50 $\pm$ 1.87	86.17 $\pm$ 1.83	56.50 $\pm$ 1.05
201	dx	94.50 $\pm$ 2.17	87.67 $\pm$ 3.44	55.00 $\pm$ 2.28
	sin	92.50 $\pm$ 3.66	85.08 $\pm$ 2.97	51.91 $\pm$ 1.43
15	dx	93.16 $\pm$ 2.32	87.33 $\pm$ 5.15	55.08 $\pm$ 2.62
	sin	97.00 $\pm$ 2.61	88.92 $\pm$.56	57.58 $\pm$ 0.80
21	dx	92.50 $\pm$ 4.15	83.92 $\pm$ 3.04	53.50 $\pm$ 1.76
	sin	93.50 $\pm$ 3.45	84.58 $\pm$ 4.74	54.83 $\pm$ 3.83
63	dx	95.67 $\pm$ 2.09	87.30 $\pm$ 5.81	55.00 $\pm$ 1.26
	sin	97.20 $\pm$ 2.64	86.83 $\pm$ 3.66	55.50 $\pm$ 1.64
84	dx	90.58 $\pm$ 2.65	86.25 $\pm$ 3.82	54.17 $\pm$ 1.83
	sin	93.67 $\pm$ 2.64	86.83 $\pm$ 6.11	53.83 $\pm$ 1.94
72a	dx	95.83 $\pm$ 6.21	85.58 $\pm$ 3.35	53.92 $\pm$ 2.42
	sin	95.00 $\pm$ 3.29	88.67 $\pm$ 4.84	53.67 $\pm$ 0.52
181	dx	90.83 $\pm$ 4.03	83.42 $\pm$ 2.20	55.50 $\pm$ 3.33
	sin	95.00 $\pm$ 1.41	84.42 $\pm$ 3.11	54.67 $\pm$ 2.16
158	dx	95.83 $\pm$ 4.12	87.17 $\pm$ 3.25	53.33 $\pm$.82
	sin	96.08 $\pm$ 3.26	87.00 $\pm$ 3.46	55.17 $\pm$ 2.11
133a	dx	95.67 $\pm$ 3.27	88.25 $\pm$ 5.31	55.08 $\pm$ 3.85
	sin	91.58 $\pm$ 3.64	86.42 $\pm$ 4.82	55.83 $\pm$ 4.62
159	dx	91.92 $\pm$ 3.93	84.00 $\pm$ 2.53	53.00 $\pm$ 1.26
	sin	93.00 $\pm$ 4.98	85.67 $\pm$ 3.20	54.83 $\pm$ 0.93
131	dx	91.33 $\pm$ 2.58	86.75 $\pm$ 6.63	55.08 $\pm$ 1.91
	sin	90.90 $\pm$ 4.57	88.17 $\pm$ 5.22	56.83 $\pm$ 1.03
55a	dx	92.50 $\pm$ 4.23	83.92 $\pm$ 2.01	55.00 $\pm$ 2.37
	sin	94.17 $\pm$ 1.47	85.83 $\pm$ 1.17	54.67 $\pm$ 2.25

Westerhus No.		Abduction 90 ⁰	Spear throwing	Forehand drive
97b	dx	95.91 $\pm$ 4.15	84.17 $\pm$ 3.97	54.75 $\pm$ 1.94
	sin	97.33 $\pm$ 4.59	86.58 $\pm$ 4.39	53.42 $\pm$ 2.58
1	dx	95.17 $\pm$ 1.72	84.50 $\pm$ 1.76	54.50 $\pm$ 2.51
	sin	96.00 $\pm$ 3.55	87.00 $\pm$ 3.63	55.58 $\pm$ 2.54
60	dx	93.00 $\pm$ 1.41	85.25 $\pm$ 4.64	53.58 $\pm$ 1.96
	sin	92.25 $\pm$ 2.52	86.17 $\pm$ 4.07	54.25 $\pm$ 1.84
94a	dx	94.00 $\pm$ 1.55	83.33 $\pm$ 2.42	53.08 $\pm$ 1.74
	sin	92.30 $\pm$ 3.09	86.67 $\pm$ 1.83	54.17 $\pm$ 2.71
116a	dx	93.16 $\pm$ 2.04	84.08 $\pm$ 2.29	54.00 $\pm$ 1.79
	sin	93.67 $\pm$ 2.50	85.00 $\pm$ 3.85	55.17 $\pm$ 1.94
155	dx	96.17 $\pm$ 2.14	85.50 $\pm$ 1.52	55.67 $\pm$ 1.50
	sin	96.33 $\pm$ 3.20	86.92 $\pm$ 1.56	55.83 $\pm$ 2.32
3	dx	92.67 $\pm$ 2.42	82.33 $\pm$ 3.83	56.50 $\pm$ 0.84
	sin	91.17 $\pm$ 3.19	84.67 $\pm$ 1.37	56.83 $\pm$ 1.60
138	dx	94.75 $\pm$ 2.72	84.50 $\pm$ 1.05	55.25 $\pm$ 1.94
	sin	93.25 $\pm$ 2.75	86.17 $\pm$ 5.04	53.92 $\pm$ 1.63
190	dx	92.92 $\pm$ 3.41	86.25 $\pm$ 4.56	55.50 $\pm$ 1.64
	sin	94.67 $\pm$ 1.86	84.83 $\pm$ 2.11	54.50 $\pm$ 2.07

Clinical material

The result of measuring is that there seems to be a constancy of the abduction levels for the three positions, both between different joints, and consequently between different subjects, as well as between clinical and skeletal measurements. The forward-backwards conduction, respectively, are also fairly similar, almost constant.

The reason why spear throwing is high has been mentioned; these values have been somewhat selected to be 80-90°. The p value for the forehand drive is twice as high as the p value for abduction 90°.

Clinically the corresponding values are much higher, due to the much lower number of degrees of freedom because of the lower number of measurements (1 x 60 compared to 5 x 300).

Clinically, the p value is highest for the forehand drive, which is probably due to this position being a very common end position in daily life (end of circumduction). The clinical values are, respectively, abduction 90°: $p \approx 0.4$, spear throwing: $p \approx 0.5$, and forehand drive: $p \approx 0.5$, a very small difference, but still a difference in the following decimals. The selection regarding spear throwing was carried on in the clinical material from the skeletal. It is to be noted that forehand drive has the highest p-value, still.

The reason for this larger similarity within clinical forehand drive values, then, should be the soft tissues, such as capsula (tight at 80° of rotation), and the proprioceptive innervation not least, feeling the right position for this very common skeletal end position.

This means that at the abduction plane there is always, in the neutral rotational position, a stop at 90° for abduction. This is defined 90-10-0° where 90° is the abduction level, 10° is the forward conduction, and 0° is rotation outwards (supination), or neutral rotational position. Spear throwing is defined 85-10-90° where 85° is the abduction level, 10° is the backwards conduction, and 90° is the outwards rotation (supination). The forehand position is defined 50-45-80°; 50° is the abduction level, 45° backwards conduction, and 80° is the outwards rotation. It is to be noted that the skeletal end positions at backwards conduction imply maximal outwards rotation, which certainly tightens the capsula.

TABLE 6. Clinical abduction levels

	90° abduction	Spear throwing	Forehand drive
21-30 yrs.	97 - 13 - 0	87 - 15 - 90	54 - 43 - 80
females	98 - 10 - 0	85 - 15 - 90	57 - 47 - 80
	97 - 11 - 0	87 - 11 - 90	54 - 43 - 80
	98 - 09 - 0	83 - 10 - 90	53 - 45 - 80
	96 - 08 - 0	85 - 11 - 90	53 - 47 - 80
	93 - 09 - 0	83 - 09 - 90	57 - 47 - 80
21-30 yrs.	97 - 10 - 0	85 - 10 - 90	53 - 47 - 80
males	95 - 09 - 0	82 - 08 - 90	54 - 49 - 80
	97 - 12 - 0	83 - 08 - 90	54 - 47 - 80
	98 - 13 - 0	82 - 13 - 90	53 - 45 - 80
	97 - 10 - 0	87 - 12 - 90	54 - 47 - 80
	95 - 11 - 0	83 - 08 - 90	53 - 44 - 80

	90° abduction	Spear throwing	Forehand drive
31-40 yrs. females	93 - 12 - 0	87 - 15 - 90	50 - 47 - 80
	95 - 10 - 0	80 - 10 - 90	52 - 44 - 80
	96 - 09 - 0	85 - 10 - 90	54 - 46 - 80
	97 - 11 - 0	83 - 11 - 90	53 - 43 - 80
	98 - 12 - 0	83 - 11 - 90	53 - 42 - 80
	97 - 10 - 0	85 - 09 - 90	54 - 45 - 80
31-40 yrs. males	97 - 11 - 0	83 - 11 - 90	57 - 43 - 80
	95 - 10 - 0	85 - 10 - 90	53 - 47 - 80
	98 - 12 - 0	85 - 11 - 90	53 - 47 - 80
	97 - 10 - 0	85 - 12 - 90	53 - 47 - 80
	95 - 11 - 0	83 - 11 - 90	56 - 43 - 80
	96 - 12 - 0	87 - 09 - 90	56 - 45 - 80
41-50 yrs. females	95 - 10 - 0	87 - 09 - 90	57 - 47 - 80
	96 - 11 - 0	85 - 08 - 90	58 - 43 - 80
	95 - 11 - 0	86 - 12 - 90	57 - 42 - 80
	96 - 12 - 0	87 - 11 - 90	56 - 43 - 80
	95 - 10 - 0	83 - 12 - 90	57 - 47 - 80
	93 - 11 - 0	84 - 10 - 90	53 - 47 - 80
41-50 yrs. males	87 - 10 - 0	81 - 09 - 90	57 - 47 - 80
	93 - 12 - 0	87 - 10 - 90	55 - 45 - 80
	94 - 06 - 0	83 - 09 - 90	54 - 43 - 80
	97 - 10 - 0	87 - 09 - 90	57 - 47 - 80
	95 - 10 - 0	83 - 07 - 90	58 - 48 - 80
	93 - 09 - 0	85 - 09 - 90	57 - 45 - 80
51-60 yrs. females	95 - 10 - 0	83 - 09 - 90	57 - 46 - 80
	93 - 09 - 0	85 - 07 - 90	53 - 47 - 80
	97 - 11 - 0	85 - 10 - 90	56 - 47 - 80
	95 - 09 - 0	87 - 09 - 90	57 - 43 - 80
	95 - 10 - 0	83 - 09 - 90	56 - 45 - 80
	94 - 11 - 0	84 - 08 - 90	57 - 43 - 80
51-60 yrs males	93 - 09 - 0	82 - 11 - 90	53 - 47 - 80
	95 - 10 - 0	85 - 09 - 90	56 - 42 - 80
	99 - 13 - 0	87 - 11 - 90	57 - 46 - 80
	97 - 11 - 0	85 - 09 - 90	53 - 45 - 80
	95 - 11 - 0	85 - 10 - 90	57 - 45 - 80
	94 - 09 - 0	86 - 08 - 90	58 - 45 - 80
61-70 yrs. females	95 - 10 - 0	85 - 10 - 90	57 - 47 - 80
	95 - 15 - 0	87 - 13 - 90	58 - 41 - 80
	94 - 12 - 0	78 - 10 - 90	52 - 43 - 80
	96 - 13 - 0	81 - 12 - 90	57 - 46 - 80
	95 - 11 - 0	87 - 09 - 90	53 - 47 - 80
	93 - 09 - 0	86 - 08 - 90	52 - 46 - 80
61-70 yrs. males	95 - 10 - 0	85 - 10 - 90	53 - 47 - 80
	93 - 11 - 0	83 - 08 - 90	52 - 45 - 80
	95 - 09 - 0	86 - 12 - 90	56 - 43 - 80
	94 - 08 - 0	84 - 08 - 90	57 - 46 - 80
	97 - 10 - 0	85 - 09 - 90	53 - 42 - 80
	95 - 10 - 0	83 - 11 - 90	54 - 43 - 80

These, then, are the clinical values for each individual, given as means of two measurements at each position, for each joint. The means of the means are as follows:

Abduction 90° (Henke, 1863): 95.333 ± 1.919
 Spear throwing: 84.467 ± 1.995
 Forehand drive: 54.883 ± 2.051

The clinical mean values are abduction 95°, spear 84°, and tennis 55°, for abduction levels. The analyses of variances will follow after the complete list of measurements.

The complete list of clinical measurements will appear in the appendix. The one-way analysis of variance for the clinical values will be given.

First comes the abduction level for abduction 90°, and its analysis, hereafter the spear throwing, and the forehand drive with their values and analyses.

It is to be observed that the variation for spear throwing is much less than for abduction, and forehand. The reason for this is a selection of values to correspond to spear throwing, and not just to any throwing. The locking per se is possible from 70-90°, but corresponds to spear throwing only between 80-90°. This was observed from the start of skeletal measuring and was also adjusted in the clinical.

The forehand drive has a broader skeletal contact, but that does not influence much without support; the influence is more detectable in clinical measuring. The influence of the soft tissues should be noticeable in these common positions. The abduction stop should be the less exact end position, both clinically and skeletally. For one thing the capsula is not torquated at the abduction stop, the skeletal contact is "thin".

Table 7 and 8 give the measurements in each single joint, right and left side respectively. The first four numbers, then, are representing one individual with two joints: 95 - 99, 97 - 99 etc.

TABLE 7. Measurements of abduction level for abduction to 90° clinical measurements, angular values

<u>21-30 yrs.</u>	<u>31-40 yrs.</u>	<u>41-50 yrs.</u>	<u>51-60 yrs.</u>	<u>61-70 yrs.</u>
95 - 99	95 - 91	92 - 98	91 - 95	92 - 98
97 - 99	93 - 97	99 - 93	91 - 95	97 - 93
96 - 98	98 - 94	93 - 97	99 - 95	97 - 91
96 - 100	95 - 99	94 - 98	94 - 96	98 - 94
98 - 94	96 - 100	91 - 99	91 - 99	92 - 98
97 - 89	95 - 99	95 - 91	97 - 91	95 - 91
99 - 95	94 - 100	85 - 89	91 - 95	94 - 96
97 - 93	93 - 97	91 - 95	93 - 97	96 - 90
94 - 100	97 - 99	92 - 96	97 - 101	93 - 97
97 - 99	97 - 97	94 - 100	98 - 96	91 - 97
95 - 99	93 - 97	92 - 98	91 - 99	95 - 99
95 - 92	97 - 95	97 - 89	97 - 91	97 - 93

Mean of measurements = 95.275 ± 3.07

Measurements of abduction levels, forward, backwards, and rotation have been listed previously.

The one-way analysis is computed according to the formulae given in Statistical methods, resulting in a p value = 0.409, indicating a clear similarity between the angular values. The F value = 0.685. The degrees of freedom are rather low, 2 - 1 x 60, which coincides with higher p-values than for skeletal measurements.

TABLE 8. Measurements of abduction level for spear throwing clinical measurements

<u>21-30 yrs.</u>	<u>31-40 yrs.</u>	<u>41-50 yrs.</u>	<u>51-60 yrs.</u>	<u>61-70 yrs.</u>
85 - 89	91 - 83	80 - 82	84 - 80	83 - 87
87 - 83	75 - 85	89 - 85	88 - 82	88 - 86
90 - 84	87 - 83	80 - 86	85 - 89	75 - 81
81 - 85	79 - 87	84 - 90	81 - 89	79 - 83
83 - 87	80 - 86	86 - 80	81 - 89	85 - 89
79 - 87	80 - 90	87 - 83	89 - 83	83 - 89
87 - 83	85 - 81	89 - 85	81 - 85	81 - 89
85 - 79	87 - 83	88 - 82	87 - 83	81 - 85
86 - 80	81 - 89	82 - 88	88 - 82	82 - 90
83 - 81	83 - 87	84 - 90	91 - 83	86 - 82
89 - 85	80 - 86	81 - 85	82 - 84	86 - 84
87 - 79	83 - 91	81 - 87	87 - 84	81 - 85

Mean of measurements = 84.475 ± 3.47

The one-way analysis is computed according to the formulae given in Methods. The p value = 0.489, is indicating a clear similarity between angular values. The F value = 0.482. The degree of freedom is 2 - 1 x 60.

TABLE 9. Measurements of abduction level for forehand drive position clinical measurements

<u>21-30 yrs.</u>	<u>31-40 yrs.</u>	<u>41-50 yrs.</u>	<u>51-60 yrs.</u>	<u>61-70 yrs.</u>
56 - 52	49 - 51	55 - 59	60 - 54	55 - 59
58 - 56	48 - 56	55 - 61	55 - 51	63 - 53
49 - 59	56 - 52	60 - 54	51 - 61	49 - 55
57 - 49	51 - 55	61 - 51	60 - 54	55 - 59
51 - 55	55 - 51	54 - 60	61 - 51	50 - 56
59 - 55	57 - 51	51 - 55	54 - 60	54 - 50
55 - 51	55 - 59	59 - 55	55 - 51	50 - 56
50 - 58	55 - 51	52 - 58	52 - 60	54 - 50
52 - 56	50 - 56	57 - 51	60 - 54	53 - 59
57 - 49	55 - 51	54 - 60	50 - 56	55 - 59
49 - 59	58 - 52	55 - 61	55 - 59	56 - 50
50 - 56	53 - 59	60 - 54	63 - 53	55 - 49

Mean of the measurements = 54.833 ± 3.70

The one-way analysis, computed according the same formulae, gives p = 0.500 and F = 0.461. Same degree of freedom, 2 - 1 x 60 = 60. The result indicates a similarity of values.

Obviously, a large number of angular values have been calculated statistically. Primarily one is entitled to ask: Are they numerical sufficient? How could one compare two clinical measurements with the six skeletal? First question: The number is enough, skeletally and clinically. The p values would have been more similar with more clinical measurements which was planned, but impossible to accomplish for practical reasons (because of time consumption). The highest p value in skeletal and clinical, respectively, will be easy to find, as well as the lowest, despite the difference in magnitude caused by a considerable difference of the degree of freedom skeletally - clinically.

The fact that forward-backwards conduction has not been computed does not matter much; firstly it was actually in skeletal spear throwing

and showed a high degree of similarity between the values, and secondly I do not think a small difference in these values would have influenced the evaluation of the angular, abductional degrees. The rotational degrees were so difficult to measure, and so very much alike when measured, that they were put at 0-90-80°.

The interesting thing in the statistical calculation, then, is that the selection of 80-90 values for spear throwing shows so clearly in the tables of p-values p. 62. Some other selection, aim of this part of the study, must also occur. The forehand drive position is the clinical position with the highest p value. This seems very reasonable as it is a common position, rotated 80° (capsula is tight), and certainly facilitated by the proprioceptive nervous system. It is even somewhat higher than the spear throwing, where the same selection has been made as in the skeletal material. No such restriction was made for the forehand drive, still the p value clinically was as high as the spear throwing.

The reason for such a high p value for the clinical forehand drive has been mentioned, and will be again. Firstly the anatomy favours a good and stable contact at the end of circumduction, where the broad infraspinatus facet and the circular, dorsal part of the edge of the glenoid cavity meet; secondly, with the soft tissues, there will be a tightening of the capsula at rotation, and not less important – the proprioceptive nervous mechanism will facilitate entrance into this very common position the joint.

Thus the values obtained seem to tell us that there exists a mechanism in the glenohumeral joint for creating end positions, a mechanism involving the greater tubercle and the edge of the glenoid cavity. The greater tubercle, in the mechanism, functions as a pawl – it meets the edge, braces, and locks the motion in the joint. The consequences are joint mechanical, and ergonomical, as related previously in this study.

It is obvious that Nature already made a selection, which I exaggerated by selecting the spear throwing values 80-90 in the measurements. If no natural selection (biological) had been present, there would not have been such similarity, statistically, between the angular values. The important and significant thing is that the forehand drive (end of circumduction) has such a high p value clinically, illustrating the function of the soft tissues in this very common, skeletal end position.

The presence of the mechanism is proved by the abductional values. The lowest significance occurring at abduction 90° still proves this.

Discussion

There seems to exist a mechanism of the glenohumeral joint implying a firm, skeletal locking of the joint at specific posture positions. This locking derives its importance, not from stopping the movement backwards of the extremity, but from locking the humerus with the scapula in forward conduction. The force of the movement is considerably increased, for example at spear throwing, and the well-known forehand drive in tennis.

These locking positions have not been defined earlier, and consequently their ergonomic importance has not been recognised. This study covers three skeletal end positions of the glenohumeral joint, or four including the sword draught position, which has not been measured and calculated as have the abductional stop (Henke, 1863), spear throwing, and the forehand drive position (end of circumduction).

Henke defined the abductional stop in 1863 as caused by the meeting between the greater tubercle and the edge of the glenoid cavity, MacConaill described the close packed position of the glenohumeral joint as caused by a congruence of the joint surfaces, but exactly the same

position as spear throwing. Hjortsjö described the circumduction movement in 1964, and the rotation of the arm, including the stop at the end of the movement. Nowhere have I found any attempt to combine the findings of Henke with end positions of the glenohumeral joint. On the contrary, Henke was ignored in the 1930s, when the abduction stop and rotational position were discussed. The stop was considered to be caused by the meeting between the greater tubercle and the acromion. Saha (1958), however, pointed out that the abduction stop was also present after acromiectomy. This statement really speaks for Henke's theory, and supports the idea that a skeletal locking could also occur at other positions, involving the greater tubercle and the edge of the glenoid cavity.

During the systematical work studying the greater tubercle, the function of the glenohumeral joint regarding its skeletal components, the end positions were found to exist (with all reasonable probability). The skeletal findings were practically-theoretically more or less confirmed by clinical examinations, watching tennis games, etc. The comprehensive skeletal measuring was started and followed by the clinical investigation (living subjects). These findings, and results of the statistical calculations have been related in Results.

There are a few points of special interest, regarding measuring, and regarding anatomy (spatial relations). For the measuring a humeri length axis is needed, which can be defined and marked on the surface by applying a rubber band from the bicipital groove (middle) to between the capitulum and the trochlea distally on the humerus. This gives a reasonable and visible length axis of the bone which is very useful when making the measurements I did. Note well, the ruler of the caliper can be applied according to the definition. One does not necessarily need the rubber band in every situation. The definition is also applicable to clinical measurements. The anatomical clue is the position of the tangential plane of the cavitas glenoidalis. The scapula is considered to make an angle of 30° with the body's frontal plane, but the collum scapulae makes an angle of 20° backwards with the tangential plane of the shoulder blade. This leaves 10° of anteversion, or forward in relation to the frontal plane.

These facts have been considered in the present study, and denoted length axis, and anteversion of the tangential plane of the glenoid fossa. A further anatomical fact of interest for investigations of this kind (clinically) is, in addition to the well-known fact that the spina scapulae (middle part) is perpendicular to the tangential plane of the glenoid fossa, that margo vertebralis (medialis) scapulae has an inclination of 20° versus the same tangential plane. By using these and other anatomic facts it was possible to accomplish the clinical part of the measurements. The skeletal part was easier as it was possible to see the morphology of the skeleton directly when making the skeletal measurements.

Otherwise, the measurements were rather easy, the difficulties being to really keep the skeletal preparations steady, and to figure the position of the skeleton out in the soft tissues when making the clinical measurements. The standard deviations are moderate, and the difference mostly seems to be below 10° . This speaks in favour of a reasonably small error of the method, and also in favour of the reliability of the results obtained. From this discussion, then, should follow that the investigation of skeletal preparations, and clinical subjects, given similar results, speaks for the presence of a mechanism of the glenohumeral joint of man, implying skeletal locking positions which are of very great ergonomic importance because they create a unit of the scapula and the humerus, thereby adding considerable force to defined movements.

These ergonomic considerations could not be attended to previously, because we did not realize the mechanism (except the abduction stop). In this study there has been no time or room for any measurements,

especially as they would certainly turn out to be extremely exacting, requiring, moreover, some equipment that I did not have access to. To perform this study as it was, proved to be just enough, considering its three parts – the degenerative changes having been added and found to be a comprehensive subject in themselves. However, the three seemed to belong together, and having started, what was more natural than to try to bring it to an end?

A few more anatomical considerations might be called for, and given some space here. The supraspinatus facet is the smaller of the two, extending 1.5 cm longitudinally on the top of the greater tubercle with a width of 1 cm, whereas the larger infraspinatus facet extends 2.5 - 3 cm, and is 1.5 cm wide. There is, consequently, a distinct difference in size between the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus facet. Between these two there exists an angular relation implying a decline of 30° of the infraspinatus from the supraspinatus, which is oriented perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of the humerus. These relations of course do have a bearing on the function of the skeletal end position.

Thus, the supraspinatus facet, for example, or the ridge between the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus facets, is the skeletal part engaged in the locking at the abduction stop, and spear throwing. The forearm drive position has a much greater surface of skeletal contact in the infraspinatus meeting the circular part of the glenoid cavity. This circular part of the edge is from the base of the coracoid and downwards much broader than the anterior part. This is also valid for the stalk part, which is much thicker dorsally – even if the ventral aspect conflues with the base of the coracoid. This intrinsically speaks for a load occurring, teleologically, that load, then, should be the contact of different parts of the greater tubercle when arriving at the skeletal end positions. This seems to be very strong evidence in favour of the mechanism described in this part. There are, however, other exhibits, related in this part, which also corroborate the theory of an inbuilt mechanism of the glenohumeral joint.

As to the rotational position, it must be considered totally clear that the rotation is prerequisite for the locking, the first prerequisite and the most important; without rotation, no locking. The greater tubercle must rotate right to be able to hit the edge. The soft tissue anatomy has been studied at the section table, pictures from one such occasion are to be found on p. 56, Fig. 29-30. The anatomy allows the contact between the mentioned anatomical structures, for the facets are clearly intra-articularly situated, as is the edge of the cavity. The tendon insertion mechanism is to be described elsewhere, and has already been briefly described in this part (p. 57). The important thing is that the anatomy allows the supposed mechanical function, also with the soft tissues in situ.

As we now are approaching the point where a conclusion should be possible, I think it is in order to recapitulate the situation, the measures taken, the considerations made. Firstly there are no previous reports found in the literature on exactly this subject, its ergonomic effects, etc. Secondly, and to allow for the virginity of the subject, extensive measurements have been performed, first on skeletal preparations, and then on clinical subjects to explore the skeletal end positions, statistically computing their significance. The soft tissue anatomy was carefully examined at autopsy, to make clear if a function like that supposed was possible, considering just the soft tissues. The construction was found to permit this type of function. The statistical calculations gave the answer that there was a similarity between abduction levels for the three different positions in the groups, regarding the mechanical function of the skeleton. In this way, both the possibility and the likelihood of the supposed built-in mechanism were confirmed.

Practically, examinations, testing of volunteer subjects, watching

tennis and spear throwing, and also metallic shotput throwing, gave their votes for the existence of the mechanism. Knowing something about the short abductors and their conditions for the work they had to perform, I found two things: 1. They need a support for heavy work. 2. They are definitely overloaded at high elevation, high speed – and a possible high load. Evidence for the theory that heavy work was supported was clearly found in the skeletal end positions, and it remained to prove the effects of overloading according to 2., which will be done in the last part. The overload manifests itself as glenohumeral pitting. Thus, the existence of skeletal lockings might be deduced teleologically, as they are needed in daily life (and sports), just as the overloading will be obvious if lifts of some weight are carried out in certain posture positions.

The prime goal of this study was to find out the loading curves at the abduction arc. Exploring the tendon insertion made it necessary to find out the aims of the intra-articularly located facets, covered with thick, meniscuslike connective tissue. Then the skeletal end positions came to be involved, the degenerative changes initially almost alien proved to be real; therefore the end positions and the degenerative changes were included in the study. There were suspicions at an early stage of degenerative changes, as the loads were rather high. Glenohumeral pitting, however, was a far too advanced change to have been created by any normal load in the glenohumeral joint – it was approaching the changes of the hip joint and the knee joint, where loads are higher than in the glenohumeral joint. The very specific conditions for the pitting and the distribution of degenerative signs will be related in Part III.

The skeletal end positions, consequently, were just coincidentally found, when searching for the tendon insertion to make mechanical calculations of the load. This led to a few years more studying, computing, and writing. The importance, however, of these end positions could hardly be overestimated, or not properly estimated at all before they had been measured. The basis for the idea, I would like to repeat, is the report by Henke in 1863 of the existence of a skeletal stop for abduction. I found that book on the mechanics of joints when searching for the classical Germans, which I also found.

Next to the report of Henke the most important announcement in literature was MacConaill's description of the close packed position of the glenohumeral joint, defining exactly the same position I found in spear throwing, and defining it, if not exactly from the same skeletal parts, so still skeletal. Hjortsjö's almost German, exact description of the circumduction movement gave me many thoughtful hours with skeletal preparations, and when examining living subjects. It seemed as if there had been several close hits in literature, Mac Conaill and Hjortsjö being the closest. Henke definitely hit the skeletal end positions in 1863, but only one position, and probably the least important too. It has been my pleasure to be able to collect these data, adapt them to my own theories and try the synthetic solution in the way described in this part.

It is hard to foresee what use the knowledge of end positions will have in future. I hope it will be useful in studying sports, working, and everyday undertakings. Knowledge is easy to carry, a Swedish proverb tells us. Something good ought to come out of this new knowledge, but very much remains to be solved in details, including the explanation and the training of presumed adepts to be taught new methods. It is to be observed that there is extensive learning involved in the appropriate use of one's own skeletal end positions – as in the training of a spear thrower (javelin contest), metallic shotput thrower, or tennis player, in contrast to all heavy pushers and towing people, who probably will mostly find the right positions by themselves, not knowing exactly how or why.

The skeletal end positions seem to have been proved to exist by systematical observations and statistical calculations of the angular values

for the abduction levels where the skeletal lockings occur. Abduction was the first movement being observed to imply a skeletal locking by Henke in 1863. Their purpose, and even their necessity for the function of the glenohumeral joint are obvious. It is not peculiar that the skeletal end positions exist, but it is peculiar that they have not been observed and described earlier. The reasons for this are hard to point out, but could be connected with the conception of joint mechanics according to the classical picture: no contact in the joint, but an imaginary pin determining the application of the principles of mechanics.

The new approach, not only to the mechanics, but also to the function of joints offered in this study is (as pointed out by Fischer 1907) to consider the form of the joint surfaces – and to be aware of the fact that the real axis of motion has to be located in the joint space – at the contact point. Additively to Fischer it should be pointed out that juxta-articular structures such as the tubercles and the edge of the glenoid cavity are of paramount importance to the mechanism of the glenohumeral joint. The greater tubercle and the edge of the glenoid cavity are both intra- and extra-articularly situated; the functioning parts, however, intra-articularly. It is by their extension intra-articularly they function, though rooted and existing as extra-articular structures. The double function of the greater tubercle as a pawl to hinder motion in the joint at specific posture positions, and as a tendon insertion have been analysed. It was obvious that both functions were possible simultaneously (details in Part II, p. 55-56, Figs. 29-30).

The skeletal end positions have obviously come to stay. They have been found during a systematical search, proved by extensive measurements of skeletal and clinical materials, calculated statistically and found to be significantly similar between different individual joints for the same position of three described skeletal end positions. During observation they have manifested their existence in examinations and while watching different sports, such as spear throwing and tennis. One could say for certain that spear throwing would be impossible without this locking, just as tennis should have to be performed otherwise, the forehand more similar to the backhand, needing an extra support now and then – even if the backhand may well be supported by a skeletal mechanism at least initially, depending on body rotational position.

The shape of the edge of the glenoid cavity might be added as evidence of its function to meet the greater tubercle, as the posterior part (acting in skeletal end positions in backwards conduction) is much broader than the anterior part. This is functional or teleological evidence, skeletal reaction by hypertrophy as an answer to load is not unusual. The ergonomic part of the reason why the skeletal end positions were created is the most important, the use of the abduction stop in Roman rings is only a rare example. The two positions in backwards conducted position, however, are more useful. The forehand drive position, and the use of this position in daily life is a good reason for its existence. The skeletal end positions are doubtless very useful; as already pointed out, spear throwing would be impossible without skeletal support. Spear throwing has probably influenced the history of mankind from its earliest days. It is to be recalled that the Cro-Magnons used the spear, which they certainly could do the correct way as they were *Homo sapiens*, possessing the same skeleton as the inhabitants of Westerhus 1100-1330 A.D. and as we do in 1980.

Skeletal end positions also occur in animal joints, and are obviously aimed to function with the lines and limits of the movements of the animal concerned – to support and give extra force at specific postures, such as that of an Impala antelope at the touch down from a long jump, considering the glenohumeral joint. A few more animal joints will be briefly mentioned in Comments. Otherwise I think by now I have exhausted my

examples and points on the skeletal mechanism, denoted the skeletal end positions, implying a skeletal stop for the motion in a joint at specific, well defined posture positions.

A summary of the skeletal end positions of this study should contain the reasons why they were found, how they were found, how they have been proved to exist, and how they function - if they are useful, have a purpose, etc.

The reason, then, why they were revealed was the search for the tendon insertion. There were a lot of things seemingly not fitting reality within the classical description, and then again, fitting. The surfaces of the facets, for example, were smooth but not in all cases. A smooth surface is not the usual picture of a tendon insertion, but sometimes the surface was marked by an unmistakable degenerative sign. So how could it possibly be an insertion, and at the same time not be? According to literature the insertion was located on the top of the tubercle (Gray 1973), and at the same time there should exist a mechanism of the function to stop movement of the arm in abduction at 90° . Suppose this was a general mechanism, working in other positions as well as that described by Henke (1863). The thing to do, then, would be to undertake a careful, systematic search for possible locking conditions in the glenohumeral joint. There were a lot of them, and the problem was to give priority to the most common, find out their exact ergonomics, and apply the theory. To explain the double function of the facets was first to be done.

The soft tissue anatomy was studied on the autopsy table, with the result that as far as the soft tissues are concerned, both functions, i.e. tendon insertion and pawl in a locking mechanism, were possible for the top of the greater tubercle. It was comforting to recognize the conjuncture or positions between MacConaill's close packed position and my own spear throwing position; on the other hand, there was also a perfect similarity between the forehand drive position in tennis of this study and the classical circumduction movement in the glenohumeral joint as described by Hjortsjö. These literary data really steadied my hand in the work to come. Saha's statement that the abduction arc's stop at 90° is also present after acromionectomy (1961) naturally did a great deal to confirm my belief.

There was also a tendency to find confirmation of the theory of the skeletal end positions. Some animals such as the Impala antelope exhibited beautiful locking mechanisms in their glenohumeral joints, as it eventually grew more clear to me, by clinical investigations, watching tennis, javelin, and other sports that the mechanism of the skeletal end positions simply had to be there, to facilitate the heavy movements in sports and other hard work. The short abductors, even the tendineous cuff, including the subscapularis and the teres minor, could be considered too weak for such heavy work as spear throwing, for example. A prerequisite, then, is that the scapula moves, and the humerus is a functional unit with the scapula, making it possible to influence the ergonomics of the shoulder joint for the skeletal end positions by locking the glenohumeral joint.

The methods of proving the existence of the skeletal end positions mathematically by computing a great number of measurements of clinical and skeletal joints, have just been related in Methods - results, and will only be briefly recapitulated here. Measurements were possible by gaining access to skeletal preparations at the Osteological Research Laboratory, University of Stockholm, and patients at the Red Cross Hospital, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm. The techniques for the measurements were as uncomplicated as possible, using a plastic, transparent angular caliper with long rulers, and utilizing a new definition for the long axis of the humerus (there was no definition previously). The difficulties were to keep the skeletal preparations steady enough, and to find the respective

plane in clinical examination. These difficulties have been mentioned in Methods. The statistical calculation was uncomplicated, and resulted in p values indicating a similarity of the angular values in the respective groups (abduction, spear, forehand).

The applications and usefulness of the skeletal end positions have been mentioned. Most important are the ergonomic consequences for the function of the shoulder, whereby a locking in the small shoulder gives much additional force to the shoulder girdle as a whole.

Conclusions

1. There is a mechanism in the glenohumeral joint of skeletal origin, related to the skeletal shape, stopping motion in the joint at specific posture positions.
2. The most important function of this mechanism is not merely to stop motion in the joint, and movement of the extremity, but to lock the humerus with the scapula in, for example, forward conduction in spear throwing.
3. There are historical notes on spear throwing, or the use of the javelin as a missile weapon in hunting etc., which make it plausible for the related mechanism to have been of importance to the history of mankind; in addition modern javelin throwing can be studied at athletic contests today. Thus, the intimate relation between Homo sapiens and spear throwing is established. The conclusion is that the skeletal end position for spear throwing is created by the skeletal shape of this species.
4. The forehand drive is to be seen on TV, and is easy to watch and judge. The rotation of the body is most evident when females play; maybe the male sex is capable of mobilizing more muscular power, using the thoraco-scapular joint instead. The locking, however, is the same whether the body rotates or the scapula moves on the chest. The conclusion is that the skeletal end position at the end of the circumduction movement at 50° of abduction increases the stability and strength in forward conduction in that posture.
5. The skeletal end positions are palpable and recognized by the distinct feeling of skeletal resistance to movement in specific posture positions. Conclusions: the skeletal end positions can be palpated and felt as resistance to motion in the joint (or movement of the extremity).
6. The accumulated facts, including the statistical calculations, are massive evidence of the existence of skeletal end positions.
7. The measurements and the statistical calculations are the scientific proof that the angular values are measurable and that the skeletal end positions do exist. The measurements are sufficiently constant to be considered as representing a biological mechanism.
8. The skeletal end positions are hereby introduced, and offered for the judgment of many competent colleagues. They were found in a systematic search and derive their importance from ergonomic function, giving extra force to specific movements in specific postures, because of skeletal locking in the glenohumeral joint of man and beasts.
9. The skeletal end positions have not been known previously. It is obvious that they open up new ways to increased knowledge, a more

accurate knowledge of the ergonomics of the glenohumeral joint of man, all glenohumeral, and all skeletal joints.

10. By this locking mechanism, due to skeletal shape, the function of the shoulder girdle complex is directly or indirectly influenced, as no joint could be stronger than its weakest link. The glenohumeral joint of man is weak where the short abductors alone have to supply the force – and vulnerable. The skeletal end positions support the short abductors at specific posture positions.

PART THREE

DEGENERATIVE CHANGES FROM TRACTIONAL LOAD

The surroundings of joints carrying sexing marks have to be differentiated from juxta-articular marks caused by load. In some cases the sexing marks and marks of load coincide, for example in the female pelvis in the form of signs from childbirth. Possibly there are more examples like this.

Tendon insertions have long been a non measurable determinant of sex in human osteology (Martin 1928 and Acsadi-Nemeskéri 1970 inter alia). As a sex determinant it is mostly the size and the more robust configuration in the male sex that are determinative – a more or less subjective evaluation in other words. This sex difference is valid for all insertions of muscle tendons – whether loaded or not – even of the mimic musculature, still more obvious in the neck, and on the processus mastoideus where more mechanical load is being distributed. Some insertions, however, are more heavily loaded than others, and under certain circumstances and conditions, such as sex, age, time (epoch), special occupations, etc. To be heavily loaded a tendon insertion has to participate in some mechanical work which implies loading the insertion. The insertions round big joints may fulfil these requirements, as do attachments of capsulae and ligaments, and also origins of muscles, as we shall see.

The joints carrying the heaviest loads according to these theories are, from the top downwards: the shoulder, lower back, pelvic girdle, hip joint, knee joint, and ankle joint. The elbow and the wrist could possibly also fulfil the requirements for being heavily loaded, but it is obvious that the hip joint, involving a long outer lever and short inner lever, and in addition a high load (the body weight), is so much heavier loaded than the wrist, and even the ankle. The static load (dead weight) is certainly greater at the ankle than on the hip joint. The important thing, however, is the inner lever and the performance of movements. The foot is certainly longer than the collum femoris, regarding walking, jumping, etc., which makes the load lower at the ankle. The loads on the spinal column are muscular as well as being transmitted by the ligamental apparatus to the vertebrae, directly from another skeletal part. This is also valid for the pelvic ligaments, and for every joint, considering the capsular mechanism.

It is all a matter of force, weight, velocity, and the length of levers. For the spine there are calculations of load according to mechanical laws, as well as intradiscal measurements of pressure, Nachemsson (1970). The levers are very long in these cases, for example at forward bending. The loads on the pelvic girdle have not been calculated to my knowledge, but are certainly very high, not least during pregnancy and childbirth. The child's weight influences the load on the pelvic bones, and the loosening of the ligamental structures (in the sacroiliac joint e.g.), due to hormonal influences, will facilitate the erosions.

As far as the big joints (the hip, the knee, the shoulder) are concerned, there are always some degenerative changes from tractional load, i.e. small pits or cysts juxta-articularly. These changes have to be

described separately, not in this study together with the degenerative changes in the glenohumeral joint. They correspond to attachments of capsula and ligaments, and are most probably caused by tractional load, transmitted by the fibrous capsula, hereby creating a permanent sign of wear and tear. The small cysts are also found at ligamental insertions, e.g. the cruciate ligaments in the knee joint, especially the anterior ligament's proximal attachment.

In the hip joint there are constantly found some changes in the intertrochanteric fossa, which looks like a cystical change from tractional load, only unusually large and with an anatomical name of its own. It is self-evident that the forces at the hip could be rather high in extension, flexion, and rotation, considering the long outer lever, and the much shorter inner lever. The muscles inserting in the intertrochanteric fossa are the obturati, which are rotators and flexors. Herein they are similar to the rotator cuff of the glenohumeral joint (inter alia the short abductors). The abduction at the hip joint is propelled by the glutei medius and minimus. The changes in the fossa are proliferative or cystical, or both.

The knee joint has no longer levers than the hip joint has, if one looks downwards (leg, foot), but if the length of the trunk and the femur, from the shoulder to the knee joint, is considered, then the length from the shoulder to the knee joint is longer than the leg is. The inner lever is shorter than the collum femoris, provided a person stands on one knee, and leans backwards, for example when pulling. The lower leg has to be fixed somehow – under a thwart, for example. In that case the quadriceps surae, especially the medial head of the gastrocnemius, will function as a flexor in the knee joint. The outer lever, then, is from shoulder to knee, and the inner only a few centimetres. The material fact is actually not the length of one lever, but the relative length of two levers – their relation, or quotient. For the hip joint this quotient can be estimated to 1:10 as for the obturati, inserting in the fossa intertrochanterica and having their origins round the foramen obturatum on the pelvis (pubic region). The quotient is the relation between the length of the collum femoris and the length of the leg. The corresponding value for the glenohumeral joint is about 1:20. The calculated ratio of transmission is also about 1:20, so the method of dividing levers can be used as an estimation of the transmission ratio for a joint. The relation intended for the knee joint is 1:15, according to this reasoning: 7.5 cm to 120 cm (= 0.0625), provided the subject is standing on the knee, the lower leg is fixed, and the movement is flexion of the knee. For the hip joint external weight is close to body weight, or 50-100 kg. This, most certainly, is more than the shoulders will ever have to carry. The transmission ratio of the hip is 1:10, and that of the shoulder 1:20, however, 10 kg will be 100 kgf in the hip, but 200 kgf in the shoulder (glenohumeral joint) for the insertion of the short abductors. So, external load and the transmission ratio decide the load on a defined insertion in a specific joint. Loads in the shoulder seldom exceed 5 kg ($\times 20 = 100$ kg), but in the hip joint the loads are seldom lower than 50 kg ($\times 10 = 500$ kg). Flexion of the knee joint comes in between these two with the transmission ratio of 1:15, for example pulling 30-50 kgf standing on knee in a boat, leaning backwards. The values in such a case will be $30-50 \times 15 = 300-450$ kgf.

There is always the weight of the arm to be considered, as far as the loads in the glenohumeral joint are concerned. The arm's weight of 2-3 kg will give a load of 40-60 kgf on the tendon insertion of the short abductors, for example in abduction movement. The arm is lifted more often than the leg is, seldom loaded with the body weight, and even if it is, the latissimus dorsi carries the load, not the short abductors when hanging by the arms, e.g. The external load in the glenohumeral joint, including the weight of the arm, can never approach the loads in the hip

joint. At the parry movement pertaining to sword fighting, however, the load is very high: $2 + 2 + 3 = 7$ kg (two swords, and one arm) $\times 20 = 140$, or – as the transmission ratio is higher than 20 outside the abduction arc, perhaps $30 \times 7 = 210$ kgf on a specific part of the insertion. The external load for the arm will not exceed this, i.e. not be as high as 10 kg. Kinetic energy, however, may be released, but it has not been possible to measure these forces. A higher load than 10 kg occurs when hanging by the arms, but will (as already pointed out) not affect the insertion of the short abductors. The same is valid for other gravitationally directed forces, sometimes the skeletal end positions are used – only the anti-gravitational movements and their forces affect the short abductors, and primarily the high speed lifts in supinated or pronated position of the arm. It is to be noted that there is definitely a high speed character of the parry movement; it is a high lift, and the load is one of the highest possible in the glenohumeral joint. The movement in timber cutting is definitely also of high velocity and load, also anti-gravitational in the cutting out.

The parry movement is definitely an anti-gravitational movement, carried out in a constantly pronated position. As the hip joint, it is definitely more heavily loaded both with external load – and internally, on the insertions of the obturati in the trochanteric fossa. The magnitude of the loads in the hip joints are 300-600 on the insertion, whereas the loads in the glenohumeral joint are lower, or 200-300 (values in kgf). There is a greater variety of changes in the hip joint, e.g. proliferative changes, larger cysts, etc. The knee joint takes a position in between the hip and the shoulder, regarding the loads, and regarding the changes. Transmission ratio hip 1:10, knee 1:15, and shoulder 1:20. Additively to these ratios, then, the outer load is deciding the load on the insertion.

Previous observations of degenerative changes of the cystic type concern the spine – Ingelmark (1956), Swedborg (1974) – the female pelvis – Angel (1969), Gejvall (1970), Nemeskéri (1972), Ullrich (1975) – and the knee joint – Gejvall (1974). Here we can easily recognize the loci just described for the maximal load, except the shoulder. The respective studies have been referred to in the Introduction (p. 9), and will not be further related here, other than as regards specific details. The shoulder has not previously been studied with regard to the changes of the type to be described in this part. The changes in the knee joint are cystic, sometimes confluent, or proliferative, maybe a larger solitary cyst. These changes have been described (by Gejvall in G.O. Janzon 1974).

Changes of this type at the knee joint had not been previously described. The findings were cystical, and proliferative, located on the medial planum popliteum, just at the origin for the medial head of the gastrocnemius muscle. The changes on the planum are comparable to those in the trochanteric fossa of the hip joint. The degenerative changes on the vertebrae are cystical, caused by tractional load most probably via capsular and ligamental attachments, as well as muscle origin and muscle-tendon insertion. This region, however, will not be further discussed as the changes here have been said to be the result of inflammation (Ingelmark 1956). The changes in the pelvic girdle, on the other hand, have proved to exist in females, usually after several childbirths, and they are most probably the result of load during pregnancy and childbirth.

Some pros and contras for these cysts being a result of tractional load will be given in the discussion, later on.

Anatomy

The anatomical regions of interest for the degenerative changes are: the bicipital groove, the facets, their margin to the articular cartilage, and the lateral aspect of the greater tubercle; in other words, the entire greater tubercle, except the region for the insertion of the teres minor. The short abductors, namely the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus, insert over the whole mentioned area, according to the findings to be accounted for in Results. The degenerative changes have been utilized to indicate the insertion area, which will be shown in the tables, their shape and appearance will be shown by means of photographs.

The greater tubercle is 1-2 x 3-4 x 1-2 cm long, high, and deep. It is a protuberance laterally on the proximal humerus, consequently located on the lateral aspect of the bone, opposite to the collum chirurgicum humeri. It is extended dorsolaterally rather than ventromedially, where the bicipital groove and the lesser tubercle are located. Once again: medially is the collum chirurgicum, and no protuberances exist here – of importance to the mechanics and for the mechanism, for the degenerations only inasmuch that no insertion other than capsular attachments will be located there.

The surface of the greater tubercle is 8-12 cm², totally utilized for insertion by the short abductors (except the part of teres minor, in addition a part of the bicipital groove is used). This location of the insertion in the groove was previously not known, but the supraspinatus tendinitis was known to be located there by the clinical investigation in this study (Clinical Epilogue, p. 109). The gross anatomy is most probably known to the reader (otherwise it is to be seen in any textbook of anatomy, e.g. Gray 1973). The specific degenerative changes and some special locations, as well as the glenohumeral pitting, are illustrated below, and on the next page, and also in the following, as most pictures reflect this region.

Fig. 33 Westerhus No. 183 (age 50-60), male. Died in battle, killed by sword, judging by cranial lesions, and several cuts from an edged weapon. Photo by Lars Wiklund. Right SWA-region, pos.-pitting (225 comparative figure).

Fig. 34 Same individual, right elbow with a cut mark on the radial side of the distal humerus, which could have been caused by a blow from a sword, the arm of 183 held, then, in an extremely pronated position. If the arm of the wounded man had not been held in a pronated position, the blow would not be located radially-dorsally (provided the man was upright, arm lifted). If 183 died with a sword in his hand, receiving among other wounds the blow dorsally on the distal humerus of his right arm, then the location of the blow verifies sword fighting, and the maximally pronated position the arm is held at in the parry movement of sword fighting. The cut is clearly too fine to have been caused by an axe.

Material and methods

91 pairs of humeri from the Westerhus population have been examined, 41 female, and 50 male. The proximal humeri were carefully explored, especially the greater tubercle where the insertion for the short abductors was expected to be located – also the region of the facets' surface was carefully examined. The exploration was made with the naked eye, and with the aid of calipers where there were any findings. Some related findings have been accounted for in Material, p. 26. These findings, however, correspond to other muscles than the short abductors (see p. 26). The aim of the investigation from the start was to find the tendon insertion and to find out if there was any difference according to age or sex obviously depending on load or specific movements; in other words, whenever possible the changes were related to specific movements, or occupations – regarding the insertion of the short abductors.

As to the grading and sizing, the following references and reasoning are relevant. The dorsal areas of the pubic bones in females who have borne children are regularly the location for changes (at the symphysis ossis pubis), graded by Nemeskéri (1972). This graduation seems to have been used later by Ullrich (1975). The whole phenomenon is more or less denied by Herrmann & Bergenfelder (1978), still summarizing: "The existence of outspoken changes is more usual in multiparae, no changes at all is more usual in nulliparae." This conclusion is based upon less than 50 cases, more exactly 49 pairs of pubic bones, from 29 to 89 years of age. Nemeskéri's grading is obviously a synthesis of Putschar (1931), and Stewart (1957), who presented their own materials, as did Ullrich (1975),

Fig. 35 Glenohumeral pitting dorsolaterally. Note the depressed area and the smaller cysts laterally.

consisting of 22 pairs of pubic bones, stages 0-2; and 16 pairs stages 2-4, concluding that the more births, the more severe changes on the pubic bones. This material, then, consisted of 38 pairs of pubic bones. The degeneration on the pubic bones were in general much larger than the same types of changes to be described on the greater tubercle. In stages 2-4 they are coalescent and most like pittings. The conclusion was that the more births, the more advanced the degenerations occurring. In stage 4 the whole area of degenerative changes was confluent, including depressed areas and pittings, but hard to distinguish from each other. This makes the comparison with the more discrete changes in the glenohumeral joint more or less impossible, as these changes are easier to define and distinguish, not being so outspoken.

The degenerative cystic changes are graded and sized (figures are given below): pit, cyst, coalesced pits or cysts - depressed areas, pitting. There will follow a synthesis of the available data in literature, further developed by giving approximate numerical values in cm for the size of the different types of degeneration. Above the depressed area comes the pitting, which is said to exist when the depressed area is between 5 mm up to 2-3 cm, containing several cysts. Pitting is, when measured as a surface, 5 x 5 mm, and 5 x 5 x 5 mm for a single cyst, as the minimum values. The numerical values are 25 for the surface and approximately 150 for the volume. These values are not exact figures for surface or volume, but comparative.

Previous studies all refer to each other, and there is no measurement, except in Gejvall's material, where the size of the largest cyst is given (1974). The method of calculating the comparative figures seems to be very useful, when it comes to comparison. The degenerative changes dorsally on the pubic bones are confluent, and very large, which makes measuring very difficult. As to the glenohumeral degenerative signs, they are more discrete than those introductorily mentioned, and certainly the easiest to measure and to count, and they therefore constitute suitable material for studies of grading and sizing. Previous grading, then, consists of description according to the terms mentioned: pit, cyst, depressed area, pitting. Coalesced area seems to be somewhere between depressed area and pitting - it could mean just three, or maybe only two

cysts. I have not used the term, just the above mentioned; coalesced is insufficiently descriptive to be used at all, at least in the glenohumeral joint, where the depressed areas are so distinct, containing cysts or coalesced cysts which are really difficult to separate. The measurements and calculation of comparative figures are more relevant and useful. No measurements have been made previously in the literature, except by Gejvall (1974), but there are large tabulations of the results in the previous studies. The tables are rather long. They are not relevant directly to the sizing and grading based on counting and measuring presented above, and to follow in a tabulation below. The previous connotations have been adopted in this study (except coalesced). Pitting of the glenohumeral joint, which is definitely the most outspoken degenerative sign, has been evaluated and compared between individuals according to the method of measurement, just described.

All grading and sizing is built upon previous works, adding, however, the measurements, and the counting of individual cysts, this idea and method being facilitated by the fact that the degenerative signs are not so outspoken in the glenohumeral joint, as they are, for example, in the pelvis, hip joint, and in the knee joint, where the load is higher. The term pitting was introduced by Gejvall (1974), and related in three metrical values, defining the size. What I have added, then, is the multiplication to get comparative figures, defining the size of an area in two dimensions, or a volume in three dimensions. As we shall see, this method facilitates the comparison.

By introducing popliteal pitting, Gejvall took the step out of the central regions, such as the spine and the pelvic girdle, leaving the way open to the shoulder, for example. The details regarding this pioneer work, a further possibility to explain popliteal pitting ergonomically, and the significance of findings like this, will be discussed later on.

The respective changes, their denotions and sizes are:

- Pit = 1-2 mm
- Cyst = 2.1-5 mm
- Depressed area = 5 mm to 2-3 cm x less than 5 mm, containing cysts
- Pitting = 5 mm x 5 mm and more as a surface with cysts on it or
5 mm x 5 mm x 5 mm as a solitary cyst ("volume")

Coalesced cysts are omitted and substituted by pitting, or depressed area, as coalesced cysts could mean both types of pitting.

In words, then, pitting is either a solitary cyst of a certain size, or a depressed area of a certain size, containing several cysts (that might be coalesced). The solitary cyst might as well be a coalescence of smaller cysts. Fig. 36 shows the bicipital groove and degenerative changes.

So the degeneration of the cystic type was measured, counted as to the total number of small cysts for a region, or in a depressed area. The total depressed area was measured as to the comparative figure for surface area or volume which were calculated. The largest pitting was measured in three dimensions, presenting a comparative figure about 300 units, comparable to the largest in Gejvall's material, also 300 units. This large one alone was twice the mean value for males in the material as regards pitting. The arms were otherwise evaluated together to avoid effects of left-handedness (dx and sin). Judged by the predominance of right-handed pitting in this material, the frequency of left-handed persons should be about 10% or less. As the degenerative changes were spread over the whole surface with age, it was necessary to compare not only males and females, but also individuals below and over 35 years of age, and to arrange the different regions defined totally, and in different ages. The sexual difference was statistically calculated regarding glenohumeral pitting. The distributions of frequencies were calculated just as frequencies, or proportions of the whole age group.

Fig. 36 Rather large cysts medially on the tubercles and laterally in the bicipital groove. Note the depressed area in the groove. (Same subject as Fig. 35.)

The degenerations were distributed over the facets, the lateral aspect of the greater tubercle, and in the groove towards the articular cartilage zone. Furthermore, the very noticeable location in the bicipital groove should deservedly be mentioned separately. Degenerations occurred most regularly in the bicipital groove, on the lateral aspect, and as glenohumeral pitting, of which the medial and the pitting were the definitely most outspoken.

The insertion area was divided in 14 regions: bicipital groove, supraspinatus, intermediate zone supra- to infraspinatus, infraspinatus anterior, infraspinatus posterior. The supraspinatus, the intermediate zone, the infraspinatus anterior and posterior were each divided in three parts: 1. facet to articular zone, 2. facet's surface, 3. the lateral aspect of the greater tubercle. They were defined where changes were found. Every individual, regardless of age and sex, had the medial changes. Almost every male subject demonstrated glenohumeral pitting dorsocaudally, behind the infraspinatus area. The degenerative signs, their location, and the ergonomic interpretation shall be related in Results.

Glenohumeral pitting occurred in almost all males, but also in some females. The chi-square method was chosen for statistical calculation.

Statistical methods

The problem was to compare the frequencies of glenohumeral pitting in males and females. There are different methods of comparing two percentages in two samples. Chi-square is one such method which gives reliable results, provided that no figure in the 2 x 2 contingency table is below 6 and the groups are not too small. The size of the groups and the size of the material can be evaluated by dividing products of the cells with total sum in a specific pattern, where the result shall fulfil certain qualifications to make the samples suitable for the method. These samples did so, and so the chi-square method was chosen for the calculation. According to the rules, the chi-square should not be used if any cell has a

numerical value below 6, or if the quotients

$$\frac{g \cdot e}{n}; \frac{g \cdot f}{n}; \frac{h \cdot e}{n} \text{ or } \frac{h \cdot f}{n}$$

are less than 1, or two of them are less than 5.

If the females had shown no glenohumeral pitting at all, the calculation would not have been necessary or possible. As it was now several of the females did, more or less. Therefore the possibility of this distribution, compared to the majority of the males displaying pitting, occurring by chance has to be calculated.

The comparative figures were calculated for the surfaces of the pittings. The mean for males was 150 and the mean for females presenting the phenomenon was 50.

The values above mean were considered positive findings as to occurrence. The sometimes more discrete signs in some females will be discussed later. The very distinct sign in most men is interpreted as the mark of a periodical, very hard load in the glenohumeral joint in a pronated position of the arm, load being as high as it possibly could be in this joint.

The 2 x 2 contingency table looks as follows:

	B ₁	B ₂	Total
A ₁	a	b	a + b = g
A ₂	c	d	c + d = h
Total	a + c = e	b + d = f	a + b + c + d = n

where A₁ is male, A₂ female; B₁ possessing, B₂ not possessing the special quality (glenohumeral pitting² in this case).

$$x^2_0 = \frac{(ad - bc)^2}{efgh} n \quad \text{without correction - and}$$

$$x^2_s = \frac{n \left((ad - bc)^2 - \frac{1}{2} n \right)^2}{efgh} \quad \text{with Yates' correction.}$$

The actual figures will be put in at the end of Results.

The x² value gives the procentual probability in tables of the x² distribution with one degree of freedom for the probability for the difference to occur by chance in per cent. The limit for significance has been set 0.01 in this case, i.e. the highest possible according to conventional manners in statistics.

Results

The tables comprise 91 x 14 evaluations of degenerative changes according to the principles accounted for introductory and in Methods. The humeri have been evaluated and registered as pairs avoiding influence of left-handedness, which makes 91 lines and 14 columns. The regions are divided, and subdivided from the medial to the lateral part of the insertion, also accounted for, from the bicipital groove to the SWA ("sword fighting attachment") - or glenohumeral pitting. They are classified in points according to size and number of cysts in the region. Size of glenohumeral pitting has been calculated and is represented by comparative figures. The points for the changes other than the pitting were 0.3 to 6 points, maximally 3 for one locus at one arm, two arms making 6 as a maximal

score for a locus. Measuring the size and counting the numbers made the score for a locus fairly easy to calculate. The comparative figures for the SWA facilitated comparison of the pittings, calculation of the means, etc. The mean for males was 150 units, and for females 50 units, as regards the pitting. Above the means (principally) the changes were accepted to be glenohumeral pittings – whether as a sign of sword fighting or timber cutting or anything else – above 50-75 for a female, and above 100-150 for a male is probably a skeletal sign that the individual performed the fighting with a one-handed sword during his or her lifetime, alternatively cut timber. The female pitting of a lower degree (below 50 units) might have another genesis, to be discussed, or more correctly, insinuated in the discussion. It could as well be caused by moderate timber cutting.

Because of its compactness the table will appear separately on the following pages. Females come first, younger individuals before older. Old males consequently come last. Note the high values for the SWA (pitting) in most males, some values above 300, and several above 200. Only a few females have acquired round 100 units – but it is possible, still, that some females really have cut timber or used the sword during their lifetime. Some females do not present any pitting at all, some have a discrete pitting (below 50) and about 50 units; they are doubtful as to the interpretation. Females with around 100 units, tall, and buried near the church could possibly have used the sword or been cutting timber; the changes are similar to male glenohumeral pitting. They might even have performed some other male occupation or duties. It is not certain that all the females around 50 units really did either. As it is impossible to prove whether they did or not, I have referred them to the first group, timber cutting, hereby at least not favouring the predominance of male sword fighting statistically. Female sword fighting might occur as might female timber cutting or other typical male work in some females' life. The more discrete glenohumeral pitting could be caused by unarmed defence, which some females possibly could have used from time to time. If the changes were caused by household activities, agriculture, or childbearing, certainly more than 40-50% of the female population would carry them. Maybe the noble art of defending oneself – say from offensive thrusts – was necessary for just about 10-15 of 41. The aggressiveness of the male population seems beyond any doubt, considering their skeletal traumatology. This theory on unarmed defence is not unlikely against this background.

The SWA as a sign of sword fighting or timber cutting will be further discussed. It could be appropriate, however, to indicate here what has already been said: the load in the parry movement of sword fighting is the highest possible in the glenohumeral joint, on the insertion of the short abductors (in man); it was occurring in Westerhus at the time these people lived as proved by the skeletal traumatology. Sword cuts were frequent among males but did not occur among females. Timber cutting certainly occurred. Glenohumeral pitting is the most distinct degenerative sign occurring in the glenohumeral joint in this material.

The last table shows the population divided in two groups, below and above 35 years of age, the sums and the means for each locus being given. The quotient above/below is then calculated, indicating the relative frequency of changes in that part, comparing old/young. The most common loci have quotients of about 1.0, indicating that they are as common in young as in old people. Quotients approaching 5, and above 10 indicate that the changes are more common after the age of 35 years. That is valid for loci 1. and 2., i.e. on the facets, especially towards the articular cartilage region. Maybe the loads will affect these regions in the long run, at specific conditions.

Results of the statistical calculations

The material consisted of 91 individuals, 50 males and 41 females, and the occurrence of glenohumeral pitting was 41:50 males, and 19:41 females.

As the requirements mentioned in Methods were fulfilled by the figures, the calculation was performed according to the below schedule:

	B ₁	B ₂	Total
A ₁	9	41	50
A ₂	22	19	41
Total	31	60	91 = n

$$x^2_s = \frac{91((9 \cdot 19 - 41 \cdot 22) - \frac{1}{2} \cdot 91)}{31 \cdot 60 \cdot 50 \cdot 41} = 11.214747$$

$x^2 = 11.215$ - with one degree of freedom. The result is out of ordinary tables for p values, and far below $p = 0.01$, which means a definitely significant difference between male and female as to the occurrence of glenohumeral pitting in this material.

Results of studying the frequencies of changes below - above 35 years

These comparisons were made by calculating the mean frequency of the changes for each of the 13 loci on the facets, glenohumeral pitting excluded, as it was studied with regard to sexual distribution, and was not supposed to show a different occurrence until below 20 years of age.

So, the relative frequencies were divided above - below 35 years of age. A similar distribution in the groups should be represented by a figure about 1.0. Such figures occurred for the medial degeneration, some lateral degenerations such as lateral supraspinatus (medially), laterally the posterior infraspinatus. The more special locations, however, were clearly more usual above 35 than below. For the location close to the articular cartilage zone the figure was as high as 14, signifying that this location was more common above 35 years. This might tell us that a longer use, and perhaps more specific movements (undertakings), should give a more unusual location of the degenerative changes. The location of the glenohumeral pitting is a specific location, appearing somewhat later in life, and almost only in males; it is located dorsally, laterally, and often extends just to the articular surface.

The location of the insertion both laterally and on the facets means that the resultant point of attack under normal conditions will most probably be located in between the branches of the Y, part III, over the edge between the facets and the lateral aspect of the greater tubercle.

Summarizing: What we know is that the pitting occurs significantly almost exclusively in males, and might be an indication that the individual cut timber or used a sword during his lifetime. The more discrete pitting observed in some females is harder to interpret. Some females are in between, and some have very discrete pittings. Many females (50%) have no pitting at all. No females have any skeletal marks (wound) from sword fighting, but more than 15% of the males have. It is obvious, from an ergonomic point of view, that the pitting is caused by a load in pronated position of the arm. Parrying is possible unarmed, with the naked arm. Parrying is always performed in pronated position. In two-handed timber cutting the arm is pronated, too, the load directed to the posterocaudal part of the insertion which makes it possible to create a similar degenerative sign. So the moderate pitting in some females could be due to restricted timber cutting.

Fig. 37 A typical pitting and damage post mortem (artefact).

Fig. 38 The largest pitting: subject 211, comparative figure about 300. This skeleton was buried close to the church and had a depressed area on the right temporal region of the skull, not necessarily caused by sword but probably inflicted in battle.

TABLE 10. Distribution of degenerative changes, greater tubercle, supra-spinatus and infraspinatus area, bicipital groove and sword fighting attachment (SWA), 91 pairs of humeri, 41 female and 50 male, the tendon insertion area divided into 14 defined regions, see Fig. 37. 1 = close to the articular cartilage, 2 = on the facet, and 3 = laterally down to the epiphyseal line. The highest point for one locus is 6, as the highest is 3 for one arm, considering number of pits, cysts, and possibly surface comparative number for the depressed areas. Glenohumeral pitting, or SWA, is calculated according to the comparative figure for surface, as the SWA always is a depressed area, or at least has an area.

Right and left are evaluated together, to avoid effects of left-handedness, also regarding the SWA. In one case a right-sided solitary cyst alone represents the pitting (211), the comparative number refers to a volume in this case.

1. 41 females 20-60 years old, sum of points for right and left arm; 6 is maximum for each locus
 - square comparative figures for the SWA

No.	Bi-cipital groove	Supra-spinatus			Supra- to infra-spinatus			Anterior infraspinatus			Posterior infraspinatus			Glenohumeral pitting (SWA)	
		1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.		
56	3.5	1	0	1.5	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	3.5	0	0	4.5	60 +
73	5	0	0	4.5	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	4.5	damaged -
30	5	0	2	4	0	0	1.5	0	0	0	3	0	0	4.5	44 -
8	3.5	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0.3	0	4.5	36 -
101	5.5	0	1	5	1	0	damaged	0	0	0	4.5	0	0.5	2	48 (damaged) -
224	4	0	0	2.5	0	0	2	2	0	0	3	5	0	6	66 +
69	6	1	0	5.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	5	0	5	30 -
1	4.5	0	0	4	0	0	1.5	0	0	0	2	0	0	5	0 -
225	6	0	0	4.5	0	0	3	0.5	0	0	3	3.5	0	5	57 +
38	5.5	0	0	4.5	0	0	1.5	0	0	0	4	0	0	1	damaged -
60	4	0	0	5	0	0	1	0	0	0	4	0	0	5	damaged -
97 b	4.5	0	0	4	0	0	damaged	0.8	0	0	4	1.5	0	5	195 ! +

No.	Bi-capital groove	Supra- to infra-spinatus						Anterior infrapinatus						Posterior infrapinatus						Glenohumeral pitting (SWA)
		Supra-spinatus		Supra- to infra-spinatus		Anterior infrapinatus		Posterior infrapinatus		Anterior infrapinatus		Posterior infrapinatus		Anterior infrapinatus		Posterior infrapinatus				
		1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	
55 a	6	0	0	5	0	0	3	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	6	0	-			
97 a	6	0	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	damaged	0.5	2	0	damaged	-				
63	6	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0	0	3.5	0	0	0	4.5	36	-			
84	6	0	0	4.5	0	0	2	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	4	0	-	= 4	SWA	
fem																				
40	5.5	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.5	2	0	4	0	84	+			
24	5.5	0	0	4	0	0	3	0	0	0	3	0	0	3.5	0	0	-			
54	5.5	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0	0	4.5	0	0	5	0	74	+			
94 a	6	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0	0	3.5	0	0	4.5	0	36	-			
11	3	0	0	5.5	0.3	2.5	3.5	0	0	0	4	4	0	4.5	0	77	+			
96	4.5	0	0	5.5	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	3.5	1.5	0	4.5	0	0	-			
42	4.5	0	2.5	6	1	0	3	0	0	0	3.5	1.5	2	4	0	0	-	(damaged)		
72 a	3.5	0	0	5.5	0	0	4	0	0	0	5	0	0	5	0	0	-	(damaged)		
21	3	0	2	6	0	0	2	0	0	0	2.5	0	2	6	0	0	-			
106	4	0	3	5.5	2	0	2	2.5	2.5	0	5	4	0	4	0	98	+			
68	4.5	0	0	6	0	0	5.5	0	0	0	6	0	2	6	0	104	+			
89 b	4.5	0	2.5	4.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	2.5	2	3	0	52	+			
44	5.5	3	3	3	0	0	0	4.5	2.5	4	4	0	0	3	0	24	-			
98 a	5.5	0	0	5.5	2.5	2.5	1.5	3	1	1.5	5.5	4.5	4.5	5	0	68	+			
15	3.5	0	1	4.5	4.5	5.5	1.5	2	5	4	2	2	3	4.5	0	50	+			
32	4.5	3	6	6	6	5	3	6	6	5	2	2	0	2	0	99	+			
34	3.5	0	0	5	3	3	4	2	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	0	4	0	damaged	-			
71	5.5	4	4	0	2	2	3	2	2	4	5.5	3	2	2	0	0	-			
226	5.5	0	0	6	0	0	3	0	0	4	3.5	0	5	0	84	+				
52	4	0	0	5	0	0	2.5	0	0	4.5	1.5	0	4.5	0	76	+				
92	5	1	5	4.5	0	0	2	0.5	2	5.5	3	3	6	165	!	+				
23	4	0	2.5	4	0	1	2.5	3	5	4	2.5	5.5	5.5	189	!	+				
57	4	0	2.5	4	0	2.5	2	0.3	2	2.5	0	4.5	63	+						
62	3.5	0	0	4.5	0	0	3	2	1	5	2	0	76	+						
Total	108	7	15	114.5	16.3	13	55.5	30.8	29.5	92.5	45.5	24	96.5	15	SWA	female				

(over 50)

2. 50 males 18-60 years old, sum of points for right and left arm; 6 is maximum for each locus
 - square comparative figures for the SWA

No.	Bi-cipital groove	Supra-spinatus			Supra- to infra-spinatus			Anterior infraspinatus			Posterior infraspinatus			Glenohumeral pitting (SWA)	
		1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.		
172	5.5	0	0	5	0	0	1	0	0	0	4.5	2	4	6	267 +
175	5	0	0	5	0	0	4	0	0	0	4.5	0	0	4.5	277 +
200 a	5.5	3	4	4.5	0	3	3	0	0	0	4.5	0	0	4.5	167 +
189	4.5	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0	0	3.5	2	5	4.5	84 + (depr.) +
122	4.5	0.5	0	5	0	0	3	0	0	0	1.5	0	0	5	161 (depr.) +
208	4.5	0	0	damaged	0	0	4	0	0	0	2	0	0	4.5	damaged - 0 -
137	4	0	0	damaged	0	0	4	0	0	0	3	0	0	4.5	154 (depr.) +
190	4.5	0	0	5	0	0	damaged	2	2	2	3	0	0	4.5	151 (depr.) +
194	5.5	0	5	5	0	0	2	0	0	0	4.5	0	0	4.5	160 (sin) +
53	4.5	0	0	4	0	0	2	0	0	0	3.5	0	0	4.5	120 (+) +
171	5	0	0	4	0	0	2	0	0	0	3.5	2	0	4.5	77 (+) - dam. ! +
3	5.5	0	0	5	0	0	damaged	2	2	2	3	0	0	4	160 (+) sin ! +
191	5	0	0	4.5	0	0	1.5	2	2	2	6	2	0	4.5	169 (+) sin ! +
155	5	0	0	6	0	0	3	0	0	0	4	1.5	0	3.5	damaged - -
166 b	5	0	0	6	0	0	3	0	0	0	4	1.5	0	3.5	damaged - -
133 a	5	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0	0	4	5	0	5	201 +
120	5	0	0	5	0	0	3	0	0	0	5	3	2	4.5	141 (sin) +
131	4.5	0	0	4.5	0	0	2	0	0	0	3	0	0	4.5	160 +
156	6	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0	0	4	0	0	5.5	91 (+) - dam. ! +
153	5	0	0	4.5	0	0	3	0	0	0	3.5	0	0	5	141 - depr. area ! +
183	4	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	0	2.5	0.5	0	4	225 + depr. area ! +
135	3.5	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	0	2.5	0	0	3	57 + damaged -
166 a	4	0	0	4.5	0	0	3	0	0	0	3.5	1	0	5	183 +
116 a	5	0	0	3.5	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	4.5	235 (sin) +
201	4	5	3	5.5	0	0	4	0	2	2	2	1	2	4.5	192 - +
202	5.5	0	2.5	5	0	0	3.5	0	0	0	4.5	2	0	4.5	96 doubtful? +

No.	Bi-cipital groove	Supra-spinatus			Supra- to infra-spinatus			Anterior infraspinatus			Posterior infraspinatus			Glenohumeral pitting (SWA)
		1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	
138	4	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	4	0	0	3	259 +
139	5.5	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	4	2	0	5	141 - +
98 b	5	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0	4	0	0	3	241 + +
104	4.5	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0	3.5	2	3	4.5	126 +
111	6	0	0	4.5	0	0	3	2	4.5	2	2	5	2	246 +
211	3.5	0	0	4.5	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0	3	366 ! +
195 a	4.5	0	0	4	0	0	3	0	0	4	0	0	5	134 +
115 a	3.5	5.5	0	4	4	0	3	3	0	3	4	0	5	168 +
160	5	0	0	5	0	0	4	0	0	5	4.5	2	4	202 +
146	5	1.5	0.5	4.5	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0	4.5	372 ! +
136	4.5	0	0	3.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	4	2	4.5	2.5	4	damaged -
182	3	0	0	damaged	0	0	0	0	2	damaged	1.5	0	damaged	91 + (depr.)
178	5	0	0	5.5	0	0	3	1.5	1.5	3.5	2	1.5	4	171 (depr.) +
223	5	0	0	4.5	0	1	0	0	0	3	0.5	2	4	152 + (depr.) +
140	4.5	0	0	4.5	0	2.5	3.5	0	0	4	2	0	4	84 + (damaged) +
109 a	4.5	2	2	4.5	0	0	4	0	0	4	0	0	4.5	114 +
213	6	0	0	4.5	0	0	0.3	1.5	6	2	2	0	4.5	228 +
134	5	4	5	3	4.5	4.5	0	3	5	4	1.5	0	4	50 - damaged
4	6	0	4	4.5	0	0	3.5	0	0	6	0	0	5	173 +
162	5	5	3	4	2.5	0	0.5	1.5	4	4	3	3	5	174 +
157	5.5	1	2	5	1.5	1.5	3.5	1.5	0	4.5	0	0	4	damaged -
121	4	2	3	6	2	1	1	3	3	3.5	3	0	4	66 - sin ! -
147	5	1	2	5.5	2.5	3	0.5	-	damaged	-	0	0	4.5	361 ! +
159	5	0	0	4	5	5	5	2	2	4	0	0	4.5	- arthritis -

The numerical values for degenerative changes in each locus comprise a point scale, with 3 points a maximum possible for each arm and each locus and 6 the highest point for two arms and one locus (i.e. one individual). Note the high points for bicipital groove, supraspinatus 3. and also for infraspinatus 3. - corresponding to the lateral aspect of the respective regions.

The sword fighting attachment (glenohumeral pitting) is calculated by length times width, which gives a comparative figure. Note, however, not a square surface in mm^2 , but a square comparative figure. Only the partly or totally damaged regions have a comparative figure below 100-150 in these adult males.

There seems to be no need of calculating a mean value for the loci, as the mentioned apparently have means close to 5.0 and are outstanding. The values will be calculated for above and below 35 years of age in the last table.

TABLE 11. Distribution of degenerative changes

The same tendencies are at hand for men as for women, the concentration of the degenerative changes to the bicipital groove, the supraspinatus 3., infraspinatus anterior and posterior 3., and the SWA. The SWA is definitely more pronounced in men, which is one fact speaking in favour of the theory that it is the result of a male performance or occupation, necessarily carried out in a position loading this part of the tendon insertion. See text for more complete discussion.

The beneath figures calculated from the table over the distribution shows the spread with age. The groups are chosen below and above 35 years of age, respectively. There is no sex difference other than regarding the SWA.

The spread is calculated by dividing two mean values, namely for each locus, regarding the young and the old group.

	Bi-cipital groove			Supra- to infra-spinatus			Anterior infraspinatus			Posterior infraspinatus		
	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.	1.	2.	3.
I. Under 35 yrs. 37 subjects	180.50 4.88	23.00 0.62	152.50 4.12	2.00 0.05	3.00 0.08	61.50 1.66	7.00 0.19	4.00 0.11	126.00 3.40	29.80 0.80	9.00 0.24	159.50 4.31
II. Over 35 yrs. 54 subjects	253.00 4.69	61.50 1.14	201.00 3.72	41.30 0.76	40.00 0.74	146.80 2.72	62.30 1.15	66.5 1.23	194.00 3.59	84.00 1.60	46.00 0.85	220.00 4.07
Quotient II/I	0.96	4.04	0.90	14.07	9.14	1.64	6.05	11.39	1.06	2.00	3.54	0.94

Discussion

The degenerative changes, which have been discussed since 1912, when they were first mentioned by Loescke, have come to stay. The first locus at which they were found and discussed was the pelvis, where the child bearing and the childbirths cause cystical changes in female individuals. They have to be regarded as established, even if a somewhat more detailed investigation of the pelvis of nulliparae could be desirable. These recurrent periods of extremely high loads on the pelvic bones have left marks, also investigated by Putschar (1931), Stewart (1957), Angel (1969), Gejvall (1970), Nemeskéri (1972), Ullrich (1975), and Herrmann & Bergenfelder (1978) – and Gejvall (1982). Grading and sizing are complicated by the confluence (coalescence) of the signs, the described method (in this study) is composed of statements from these authors, with addition of the calculation of comparative figures for the surface of the depressed areas.

Popliteal pitting was the first degenerative sign outside the pelvic girdle to be described, Gejvall (1974). His material is middle-neolithic fishermen from the island of Gotland, Sweden. The material consists of nine subjects, all males, and presenting a specific degenerative sign. This sign consists of large cysts and/or other degenerative signs such as proliferative excrescences on the medial part of the planum popliteum, where the medial head of the gastrocnemius muscle has its origin. The changes are cystic – pittings as well as proliferations, just like the changes in the intertrochanteric fossa. The changes were mostly left-sided and/or bilateral. The largest cyst had a comparative figure of 300, which speaks in favour of a considerable load – periodically, maybe at long intervals. The load, however, has to be heavy to produce these changes (cf. to the hip joint, the obturati – up to 500 kgf). The outer lever has to be long, and the inner short; that will give the heaviest loads, just as in the hip joint.

The fishermen being middle-neolithic, it is almost impossible to define what type of boat they were using – maybe just a hollow tree. The barrel, or exactly what kind of boat they were using is not important, however. The essential point is that they used a small boat containing 2-3 people, somehow like a canoe to be paddled standing on one or two knees. What if the stem man harpoons a seal? The beast will try to escape – and the small boat with its men will be towed along. Here the interesting action will take place: the man in the stem will certainly lean backwards, to counteract the traction of the beast, hereby flexing one or both knees. This flexion of the knee will load the origin and the insertion of the gastrocnemius muscle, especially the medial head. The insertion is the achilles tendon, and the origin is the planum popliteum. The force is most probably over 300-400 kgf in this moment, considering the weight of the beast, weight of the barrel, and the force of the sea, depending on the weather. Most important, however, is the transmission ratio for the joint-linkage used, which is about 1:15 (7.5:120), inner lever to outer lever, knee to shoulder. An outer force of 30-50 kgf is capable of producing an inner load of 300-500 kgf. Most probably the tension in the towing line will reach that value, depending on friction, velocity, direction, etc. The forces cannot be calculated without an experiment, but evaluated; the transmission ratio can be calculated.

A propos of direction of force: if the man in the bow is right-handed, the harpoon will be thrown to the left of the boat. The towing will consequently be directed left of the boat. Say that the man stands on his left knee, then the left gastrocnemius will be loaded. Left-sided popliteal pitting is most common. Naturally there are other possibilities; the man might stand on two knees, be left-handed, etc. The weight of the beast in water is probably very low, but it is the living force that counts. Most

probably the boat was towed, with its 2-3 men, and it would take a certain force to do the towing.

In this discussion we are now approaching the subject of the study: the insertion area for the short abductors in the glenohumeral joint. There are at least two items to be explained: 1. location of the tendon insertion and 2. distribution of the degenerative changes according to age and sex. First one should discuss if the changes are degenerative – and draw a preliminary conclusion on that point.

There are degenerative changes to be found on the greater tubercle, corresponding to the insertion of the short abductors anatomically, degenerative changes of the same type as, and almost identical with, the previously described by Putschar (1931), Stewart (1957), Nemeskéri (1972), and Ullrich (1975). Popliteal pitting revealed by Gejvall in 1974 was the first sign of tractional load outside the pelvic girdle and the spinal column.

If these changes, here described and referred to as mechanical load, according to previous findings, were not signs of mechanical load, what would they be? Inflammatory? Some *lusus naturae*? I think one can get rid of both these objections by the same reasoning. As they are explainable just as degenerative changes from tractional load of some magnitude, and have been found at such loci where the loads are high, why should they be inflammatory? Maybe they are hormonal in the pelvis, or inflammatory – or both – in addition to load. Why should they be a *lusus naturae*? A *lusus naturae* is defined as a teratism by Dorland (1949), not explainable by any functional, only by embryologic factors (ontogenetic). Foramina nutritia do not have "floors", are not multilocular, and are not at all cystical. Post mortem damage to the bone can be easily recognized by anyone, especially by a well-trained osteologist. It is very hard to find any explanation for the small cysts, other than the mechanical theory. As we have seen and shall see, the degenerations are located according to mechanical principles, and not like any *lusus naturae*. That is valid for the changes on the pelvic bones, and on the planum popliteum, as well as in the hip joint (described earlier in this part), and like the changes on the greater tubercle.

The tendon insertion has been assumed to be located on the top of the tubercle in the previous literature, cf. to Introduction (p. 18). It has been said to have this location in all available literature, monographs as well as textbooks, from Poirier & Charpy (1911) to Gray (1973). There has been no mention of the lateral aspect of the tubercle, or the alternative of both facets and the lateral aspect, which is found to be the material fact in this study (giving a Y-shaped attack), as related in Results, part III. This means that the functional point of attack mechanically is located at the edge or the ridge between the facet surfaces and the lateral aspect of the greater tubercle. This Y-shaped traction is very likely to function normally. In very special positions, and maybe very high loads, another distribution might work. This, however, is a question considered beyond the scope of this study. The degenerations are most frequent laterally, but they do occur on the facets as well, and more frequently after the age of 35 (according to the tables). Glenohumeral pitting is located on the facet surface and behind the infraspinatus region. It is the most commonly occurring degenerative sign on the facet surface as to size and occurrence. This pitting is, in magnitude (comparative figure), the most distinct degenerative sign of all, mostly occurring in males.

The degenerative changes denoted glenohumeral pitting, analogously to popliteal pitting (Gejvall 1974), are really interesting and intriguing as theoretically very valuable in explaining the importance of the rotational position, hereby constituting a criterion for the mechanical genesis not only to the pitting itself, but of all degenerative changes in the gleno-

humeral joint. This is valid for the different loci of degeneration regarding the combination with some specific movements according to the rotational position of the arm, which in turn are to be combined with specific occupations or type of movement. The loci to be compared should be located as far apart as possible, and corresponding movements should be as exactly defineable as possible.

The distribution of load goes back to clinical testing, where the rotational position is found to be decisive by MacLauglin (1947). Inward rotated positions (pronation) will load the infraspinatus, and outward rotation (supinated position) will load the supraspinatus, or: supinated position loads the supraspinatus, and pronated position loads the infraspinatus. The position the arm is held in during abduction, and at which the movement is performed, decides the load; that is, the medial, supraspinatus part will be loaded in flexion, and the postero-caudal part will be loaded at maximal pronation, which occurs in the parry movement and the arm towards the tree in timber cutting.

As it is, then, the infraspinatus will be loaded in the pronated position, the region behind the infraspinatus will be loaded only in extreme pronated position, as for example in the parry movement, with or without a sword, to ward off an offensive thrust or timber cutting. This is the region for glenohumeral pitting, the largest degenerative sign, very distinct and clear, occurring almost exclusively among males, not at all in the same frequency or to the same extent in females. A clearly significant difference is shown in the occurrence, and above all there is a difference in the magnitude of the pitting between the sexes. Considering movements and postures, there are few undertakings comparable to the parrying in sword fighting, or just parrying to ward off an offensive thrust (with the naked arm, unarmed). The heaviest load will be at the moment two swords meet in the air, and the region loaded at that moment happens to correspond exactly to the precise part of the insertion area where glenohumeral pitting is located. Timber cutting is a quite different type of movement, anti-gravitational, however, in the cutting out, of high velocity, suddenly stopping and repetitive. The load on the insertion of the arm nearest the tree is located dorsocaudally exactly as the load in sword fighting. The less pronounced changes in some females, then, could equally well correspond to a parry movement with the naked arm. Certainly it would be possible to argue for a few pages on this subject, but I do not think a non-believer would be more convinced by this. A short recapitulation: the load is highest at high lifts, high velocity, and high external load. All these circumstances exist in the parry position in sword fighting, which is the highest possible load for the insertion of the short abductors. The pronated position, in which the parry movement is performed, directs the load precisely to the location for glenohumeral pitting. These events could not possibly be a coincidence. As to the frequency of the performance: 1-5 times per year, or once each other year does not matter much for the creation of the degenerative changes – the most important thing is the load. The joint ergonomics are also of importance. Repetition is needed – and will certainly occur on a day when sword fighting is performed. The important thing for causing the changes is not everyday repetition, but the magnitude of the load, and exactly the same part being loaded several times.

The medial degeneration is caused by a daily load, sometimes larger and caused by lifting heavy objects, giving higher loads, comparable to degenerations in the hip. The medial degenerations are located from the bicipital groove, laterally towards the supraspinatus part of the greater tubercle. The same type and frequency of degenerations also occur on the medial part of the greater tubercle's supraspinatus part meeting the degenerations within the bicipital groove. These degenerations are the most common, occurring in every individual, young and old, male and

female. This medial location, especially the location in the bicipital groove, was previously not known. The location has a special clinical importance, related in Clinical Epilogue (p. 109). The medial parts of the insertion will be loaded in flexion and supinated position of the arm. This movement is very common, but the loads are not as high as on the posterolateral part, where glenohumeral pitting is located. The forward lifting on the one hand, and the parry movement and timber cutting on the other, are opposites in every respect: occurrence, load, and location (opposite in the insertion area). The forward lifting (flexion) occurs very frequently, and the parry movement rather infrequently, timber cutting probably more frequently in most men. Nevertheless they are the most commonly occurring degenerative changes in the insertion of the short abductors. Glenohumeral pitting, when it occurs, is the most distinct degenerative sign.

It is to be pointed out once more that the medial degenerations, though not so large and distinct as glenohumeral pitting, still occur in every glenohumeral joint, old and young, male and female. The changes are very distinct still (see points in the table), and located in the bicipital groove and on the lateral aspect of the greater tubercle's supraspinatus part. The degenerative changes correspond to flexion at outward rotated position (supination), i.e. elevation forward-pronation (movement, not position). These movements are perpetual, occurring in every individual's daily life. Sometimes it is more heavily loaded. Glenohumeral pitting, on the other hand, is a degeneration related to selected movements, maybe seldom occurring, but when they occur heavily loaded.

It is interesting to consider and to compare these two characteristic types of movement, and to correlate them to their respective locations in the insertion area. They are the two most distinct, definitely as far apart as possible in the insertion area, representing different rotational positions. The occurrence of the flexion at supination in every individual means a correlation to a common occupation or daily life. The linkage between glenohumeral pitting and males, and its being much larger than any degenerative sign, speak in favour of some specific male occupation, implying a heavy load. For the creation of degenerative changes caused by small ruptures, the heavy load is very important. Repetition of movement seems to be necessary, but daily repetition is certainly not essential. To create the degenerative changes, the load must return to exactly

Fig. 39 A close up of Fig. 37. There is a distinct difference between the artefact (bottom) and the pitting in the upper part. Though there might be a depression on the artefact (towards the pitting), the depression in the pitting is doubtless.

the same part of a region of insertion area, in other words the position of the arm and the posture must be repeated as exactly as possible. I am convinced that spear throwing and sword fighting were such occupations with an individually well-established pattern of movements. Spear throwing means protection for the insertion of the short abductors, or at least an efficacious aid from the skeletal end positions. Sword fighting is carried out outside the zone of action of the skeletal end positions, and has to be performed unaided by this mechanism, as has the motion in the joint in timber cutting, a very high load being distributed to the insertion of the short abductors, and to a restricted area because of the specific posture position.

The two types of movement just described, the flexion at supinated position, or pronation, and the high elevation in pronated position, are represented in the insertion area by changes located 3-4 cm apart, which makes them anatomically distinguishable for certain. The functions are also very different, and represented by distinctly different movements as to frequency of the performance, load, velocity, and height. The movements, or the degenerative changes, have a different occurrence in the two sexes, with a predominance of the movement interpreted as sword fighting or timber cutting among males. It is impossible to separate any other movements out of the many possible, usual movements, as none seems to occur as commonly, or be so heavily loaded as either of the two mentioned, represented by the most distinct degenerative changes. Furthermore, the sexual distribution is interesting, and is also statistically calculated (see Results p. 89) according to the chi-square, 2 x 2 contingency table with one degree of freedom. The result of this calculation was $\chi^2 = 11.215$, which means a very high significance for the sex difference not being that large by coincidence. Some biological selection must be involved, such as the sword and the axe being used almost exclusively by males. It is to be noted that glenohumeral pitting was considered at the mean for females = 50 units, and for males at their mean, or 150 units as a basic principle. Using exactly the same criteria in numerical values would have meant practically no female sword fighting or timber cutting. However, sword fighting or timber cutting among females might have occurred, but not to the same extent as among males. This theory is supported by the skeletal traumatology as a whole in the Westerhus material. The more discrete glenohumeral pitting also occurring in some females is impossible to interpret; it might represent a very restricted use of the sword or a restricted timber cutting, and again it might also represent the parry movement with the naked arm from time to time. Some females present a pitting of just below 200 units, and all above 50 and to 100 are not quite certain, but are registered, as having used the sword or having been cutting timber in their lifetime. Below 50 fall in the most uncertain group. 22 females had no such changes as glenohumeral pitting, 9 males did not have any. Some preparations, both male and female, were damaged in the actual region and impossible to read, most negative males are so from this reason. The tables show which specific bones were damaged, and where.

Summing up, tendon insertions have long been used as a sex determinant in osteology. Their configuration and general appearance are more robust in the male sex, Acsadi-Nemeskéri (1957) *inter alia*. Heavy loads on tendon insertion are known to give rise to a specific, small-cystic degeneration, also used for sexing, Gejvall (1970), as they are confined to the female pelvis after repeated childbirth. Cystical changes in the spine were already described by Ingelmark in 1957, and more recently by Swedborg (1974).

Gejvall revealed some rather large cysts in middle-neolithic fishermen from the isle of Gotland (in G.O. Janzon, 1974). The interesting thing about these cysts was the location, primarily out of the central skeleton,

and secondarily on the planum popliteum, where the medial head of the gastrocnemius muscle has its origin. This muscle works when the lower leg is fixed, and the knee flexed against a resistance as when standing on one knee in a small boat being towed by a harpooned seal or other beast. The changes of degenerative character are obviously from tractional load, similar to changes found in the hip joint, on the insertions of the obturati in the intertrochanteric fossa. The loads are of similar magnitude (see p. 80-81).

The important thing about these findings is that they indicate a path to other, similar phenomena, in the hip joint, and in the shoulder joint where the forces have been calculated to be in the vicinity of forces in the knee and in the hip. This is why the present study was initiated, especially this part of it, in which the degenerative changes are studied.

Previously described methods of recognizing changes and connotations used in this connection have been used, except the term coalesced cysts. The depressed areas have been recognized, and the pitting. The term popliteal pitting which was coined by Gejvall for the large changes in the knee joint of middle-neolithic fishermen has been used as a model, cognizing glenohumeral pitting to denote a specific degenerative sign found almost exclusively in the male shoulder.

All degenerations in the glenohumeral joint, on the greater tubercle, have been measured, counted, and in the case of depressed areas, large cyst, or recognized as pittings, also calculated for a comparative figure, defining the size of the degeneration (corresponding to surface or volume, by multiplying metrical values). Hereby a direct numerical comparison is possible.

By this routine all glenohumeral pittings were sized, male above 150, female above 50 (mean for male-female) considered to be real pittings, and a probable sign that the subject had either used a sword during his or her lifetime, cut timber or defenced themselves without weapons. The explanation of this conclusion is to be found in each of the parts, as the entire theory of load, rotational position, distribution of load, etc. is involved. Suffice it to state here, that extremely few movements are performed at maximally pronated position. Parrying is, as well as timber cutting and the parry movement pertaining to sword fighting is. The pitting in itself is the most distinct, and largest degenerative sign of the glenohumeral joint, which is in line with the load in warding off an enemy sword, being the heaviest load possible in the glenohumeral joint, considering the velocity and the fact of two swords meeting in the air. Timber cutting is more difficult to evaluate but still considered to be of significance for the glenohumeral pitting.

The medial degeneration, corresponding to flexion in supination or pronation movement, is to be found in every single individual's bicipital groove and lateral supraspinatus aspect medially (towards the groove). There is no difference between various ages, and no sex difference whatsoever in this region. The corresponding movement is necessarily some daily routine, the same in both sexes, young and old. Lifting forward, or flexion in the glenohumeral joint, is certainly such a movement, sometimes extra loaded, but occurring several times each day. The difference between medial and lateral degeneration is clear. No further subdivision is possible today, or with this skeletal material.

Conclusions

1. Tractional loads create degenerative changes exerting their effects on insertions, attachments, and origins of muscles. These degenerative changes are recognizable, predictable, and measurable. Mechanical laws direct their location, the levers in use being of the utmost importance, deciding the load and which part of the insertion is to be loaded.
2. The glenohumeral joint is a very instructive joint regarding the influence of the rotational position, deciding as it does the exact location of the insertion area, and thus locating the degenerative changes.
3. Glenohumeral pitting is the most specific and largest degenerative sign of the glenohumeral joint. The occurrence of sword fighting in the present material is confirmed by previous findings, Gejvall (1960), and may be related to this as well as timber cutting could be.
4. The highest load in the glenohumeral joint that ever existed is the parry movement in sword fighting. Therefore it seems highly probable that the sword fighting is the causative factor in glenohumeral pitting. It is also possible that the load in timber cutting could be equally high, however.
5. All ergonomic facts point in favour of a link between glenohumeral pitting and sword fighting, and the influence on the distribution of load is also confirmed by this thesis. Alternatively the pitting could be created by a specific, heavily loaded performance like timber cutting.
6. All loads in clinical tests, as well as in daily life, are distributed by the effects of the rotational position. The most common movement in the glenohumeral joint is the flexion-supination, which corresponds to a locus where every individual, regardless of age and sex, presents pronounced degenerations, namely the most medial part of the insertion including the lateral part of the bicipital groove.
7. The more discrete changes in the glenohumeral joint, compared to the hip, the knee joint, and the pelvis, make a specific grading and sizing possible. Even the calculation of comparative figures regarding surface or volume is possible, which facilitates comparison between individuals.
8. The degenerative changes described in this part are certainly no *lusus naturae* or artificial products. They are brought on by tractional load according to mechanical laws.
9. The same is valid for the previously described degenerations in the pelvis, knee joint, etc. Their existence is predictable, according to the lever's length and mechanical principles.
10. Thanks to the special construction of the glenohumeral joint, its function, and the use man found for it, the conclusions could be drawn and the connections postulated.
11. The possible conclusions as to connection movement-degenerative change(s) have been drawn, limited to the common flexion in supination, medially, and the more uncommon, but certainly occurring movement elevation in pronation distributing the load dorsolaterally in the insertion.

12. No further conclusions can be drawn today, as other movements are less common and/or not so heavily loaded – besides being located too close to each other to permit the certainty possible for the two locations mentioned.

13. Future possibilities exist for utilizing these methods of recognizing the distribution of load in a joint, even if the conditions in the glenohumeral joint of man are extremely favourable, by the existence of the rotational distribution of load in the insertion area. It should also be possible, utilizing larger material and more known ergonomic details as to possible occupations of the population, to find out more about the glenohumeral joint of man. Specific occupations and movements are prerequisite for doing so, in this study exemplified by flexion-supination (daily lifting), and, on the other hand, timber cutting or sword fighting.

COMMENTS (VOCABULARY)

These comments are actually a substitute for a word list or vocabulary; they will be principally semantic on the meaning and the use of words, some special words used in this study with a special meaning and reference. I would not like to do as Humpty Dumpty did in Wonderland. He said: "When I use a word it means just what I choose it to mean – neither more nor less." And Alice said: "The question is whether you can make words mean so many different things." – "The question is", Humpty Dumpty said, "which is to be the master – that's all." I would like to add to this discussion that it is necessary to define exactly the meaning of words used in a specific context or on a limited subject as in this study. Therefore I am writing this vocabulary, where I cannot refrain from commenting on the classical German theory on the axis of motion, and its dominance – related to another classical fairy tale.

The imaginary axis and its dominance and prevalence in the minds for almost a century is really noteworthy. Maybe it is explainable the way I suggest by quoting H.C. Andersen. The concept and the corresponding words axis and axle will be explained and their use in this study accounted for. The etymology of the word pawl, as well as the reason for using this word to denote the part locking at the skeletal end position will be related and explained, respectively. Motion and movement have been used with special reference and connotation in this work; this is explained and a suggestion made concerning the future use of these words with this specific meaning. The denotation skeletal end position is somewhat explained, as is the term tractional load, both used very often in this study. They should be understandable from the context, but they have not been defined or explained properly in the text.

The fact that the old German theory involving the central, imaginary axis was not checked or even criticised for 100 years must be due to a massive, imposing layout in the textbooks of anatomy, and probably the author's personalities and their authority when it was introduced and propagated. The mechanism described by H.C. Andersen in "The Emperor's New Clothes" might have been working in the minds, nobody daring to say: "I do not understand". The theories consequently were accepted, quoted, and appeared in one more textbook, monograph, or paper. It is to be recalled and noted that this theory was included in a course for orthopedic surgeons as late as 1979 (Y. Chao). So nobody ever questioned the central axis theory for more than a century!

The word axis denotes a theoretical, imaginary thing: the axis of motion, the axis of momenta. The axis is mostly a point on paper, round which the movement occurs, or is thought to occur. Usually the axis exists in some kind of imaginary, two-dimensional world; of course it might be three-dimensional too, but the axis is always unreal. It could, however, correspond to something real as well – in a two- or three-dimensional reality. An axle is always real, a pin or the central axle of a wagon wheel. The plural of axis is axes, and the plural of axle is axles.

According to most dictionaries the word pawl denotes a hinged or pivoted part of a mechanism to fit the teeth of a ratchet-wheel to stop the wheel. As a sea term, pawl denotes something to put under the barrels to prevent them from rolling on the ship's deck. This term seemed adequate for the function of the greater tubercle bracing and locking – corresponding to the Swedish word "bromsklack". Pawl is referred to by the dictionaries to Welsh pole, Latin palus (stake), and French épaule (shoulder), probably because of the pivoting function, which is shared by the greater tubercle, pivoting as it is round the joint's axis of motion (contact point). Therefore it is interesting, intriguing, and irresistible to use this word, meaning just shoulder.

Of the two words motion and movement, motion is the most abstract,

but the words are almost synonymous according to the dictionaries. We might speak of motion of the celestial bodies, but usually we say movement of an arm, or a leg. Again, motion could be a gesture, or something that expresses emotion. One finds long lists of different meanings and situations in which to use motion or movement, respectively. My standard dictionaries have been: Random House, college edition (1968) and Funk & Wagnall, international edition (1973). In addition I have used the Swedish PRISMA dictionaries English to Swedish, and the reverse (1975 Swedish-English; 1982 English-Swedish). They do not mention the distinction I am about to make here; these meanings are used in the text of the study.

Motion in the joint, between the joint surfaces, invisible.

Movement of the extremity, from motion in a specific joint, visible.

This distinction is very useful, as spatial changes in the joint, of its surfaces in relation to each other, are not the same as the spatial changes in position of the extremity (caused by motion in a defined joint). Rotation in the glenohumeral joint (motion), corresponds to flexion or extension (elevation forwards-backwards), but at 90° of abduction rotation of the caput and the humeral shaft coincide. Sliding down in the cavity (gliding, grinding) – motion – is matched by abduction of the extremity – movement.

The denotation skeletal end position definitely connotes a stop caused by the skeleton or the skeletal shape, which is intended. The stop aimed at, then, is located at the end of the range of free motion in a joint. These skeletal end positions are physiological, within the normal function of the joint. As they have hitherto not been recognized, there is nothing written about their enormous ergonomic importance in the glenohumeral, and most certainly many other joints.

The term tractional load has been coined as there really is a use for it in this study. It may seem strange, and perhaps even inconsequent, as load is something laid upon something or someone, a burden, accelerated only by the weight of the burden and the force of gravity. As to the glenohumeral joint, however, gravity gives a continuous load on the insertion in question at upright position. Furthermore, there is a definition of load in the Random House Dictionary – Engineering: any of the forces that a structure is calculated to oppose. A distinction is being made between the load that is changing (live load) and the constant load (dead load). Gravity's load (arm's weight) is dead load, then. But any change in the load by working etc. should be live load in any direction, not only vertical to the tendon insertion.

As to glenohumeral pitting, it is the most hard-featured theory of this study, seemingly – so it has been given some space of its own in this chapter both considering the term itself, as for its existence – and not least its creation in this early medieval material. A discussion of forces and loads capable to create the pitting will follow, closing the comments.

Comparative osteology, of course, has been the object of discussions at the laboratory during the work. There has not been much time for more than discussions, comparisons, singular observations on different species concerning mostly the glenohumeral joint. It will be stated, nevertheless, despite the lack of even larger systematical observations, that there exists a clear and obvious locking mechanism of the glenohumeral joint in animals. The anthropoids have four facets instead of the human two, but they are smaller, less distinct. The bear has a very special glenohumeral joint, including more torsion of the humerus and otherwise more manlikeness than other beasts. The Impala antelope has a beautiful humerus-scapula locking mechanism, and certainly needs it when coming down to the ground from its long jumps. A sophisticated locking mechanism has also been observed in the flying dog. As to degenerative changes, no observations were made on animal bones; the human pittings from hunting seal, timber cutting and sword fighting, as far as I know, are not

equalled in the animal kingdom.

This last chapter has been devoted to the explanation of words, and how they were used in this study. It was necessary to do the explaining somewhere; the words were not so many as to call for a glossary, and the explanations were rather long, so it seemed suitable to do the explaining this way, by means of comments.

The term glenohumeral pitting is coined in this study analogously with popliteal pitting in the knee joint. Popliteal pitting is to be considered created by extraordinarily high loads on the planum popliteum, where the origin of the medial gastrocnemius is situated, and which is extremely loaded by bending the knee – the long lever knee-shoulder working; by fishing at sea, standing on one or both knees.

The lever in the glenohumeral joint could not be as long as from knee to shoulder, and the load not that high as on the knee by fishing on the sea. Therefore it really takes a very specific movement or performance to explain the creating of a degenerative change in the glenohumeral joint, almost equalling popliteal pitting though the transmission ratio is higher in the glenohumeral joint, 1:20 to 1:15 in the knee. The specific movement or performance has to be of high velocity, hereby adding the kinetic energy to the static load. It is not possible to calculate the kinetic energy. The static load, however, can be calculated or at least estimated. The static load considering the transmission ratio of the glenohumeral joint should, for the movement in question, approach 200-300 kgf.

There is another requirement of position to make the load influence exactly the posterocaudal part of the facet region. Elevation and pronation are prerequisite to bring the load to this region. The pronation has to be near the maximal, elevation should be over the head, and the load has to be directed gravitationally, i.e. the force anti-gravitationally. No movements directed towards the ground could be considered as causative for the specific degenerative sign glenohumeral pitting. The static load has to be as large as possible to give the required 200-300 kgf of static force.

Seemingly there are many movements that fulfil the requirements of creating the largest medieval pitting, occurring almost exclusively in males. Some examples could be timber cutting, house building – no movements where the force is directed towards the ground are possible, agriculture consequently is no good alternative to explain the pitting. Glenohumeral pitting is also right-handed, i.e. the occurrence is below 10% on the left side (or predominating on the right side).

As to timber cutting is it fully possible to get a load on the dorso-caudal part of the facet area when cutting with a large axe using two hands.

Some unrealistic suggestions might be mentioned: painting roofs, cleaning windows, and pouring water into a high located vessel to fill it. The general principle here is that movements mentioned comprise one or both arms over the head. The inwards rotated position is an absolute requirement; the extremely high lift is not that necessary, if only the direction of movement is anti-gravitational – and there is a load, static and/or kinetic.

A good and possible example would be the sword fighting with one hand sword, rather heavy (about 2 kg), and locking the hand between the hjalts of the grip. Sword fighting is performed at inwards rotated (pronated) position, is loaded, anti-gravitationally directed and performed with speed. Parrying would mean the double weight and some velocity. The weight can be calculated-estimated to be 200-300 kgf on the specific part of the tendon insertion where glenohumeral pitting is located. It is hard to judge from an archaeological point of view what tools and weapons were really used in a small medieval parish like Westerhus, even if they used axes or swords to fight. Their enemies, however, seem to have used

swords, at least to some extent. Maybe one is entitled to make a presumption that the sword was the weapon of the highest classes, but of interest to males of all classes, and that most men during their life-span used both axe and sword – if ever joining a battle. It seems possible as well that a male of low social status could be able to shift from axe to sword in the same battle. It is not unlikely that most males tested the sword, its function etc., and maybe prepared themselves before going out in battle.

It is fairly easy from an ergonomical point of view, however, to state on the base of this study that the sword could cause the pitting – or its use did, and if not – something that is ergonomically equal for the glenohumeral joint, some movement or performance. Timber cutting seems to be almost equal to sword fighting, provided the axe is held with two hands, and the tree is approached with the cutter's right side, which is reasonable if he is right-handed. The short abductors will in this position accelerate the function and give force to it. It is, however, difficult or impossible to tell how much force, as it is an oblique movement, weight of axe and cutting force are not known. It is, however, reasonable to consider timber cutting as another possible cause of glenohumeral pitting, occurring with certainty among males mostly. To explain the position needed for the creation of the pitting I have found sword fighting more understandable, especially the parry movement, where the direction is in the vertical plane, the loads are known, etc. Velocity, by the way, could be about the same in sword fighting and timber cutting, kinetic energy not being possible to measure in either. Pronation of the arm turned towards the tree in cutting timber, then, is postulated to have occurred in medieval times as it does today. Pronation is absolutely prerequisite to direct the load to the posterocaudal part of the facet area.

There are differences, of course, between one-handed vertical sword fighting and two-handed oblique timber cutting. The same part of the insertion is loaded, however, but there are no skeletal end positions to relieve the load in either. It does not matter much if the degenerative sign should be caused by sword fighting, timber cutting, or even another performance, provided it is an occupation that occurred on the relevant place in the relevant time. It is also to be noted that the most important glenohumeral pittings were found in males, buried near the church. Whether these hōlder-men were cutting more timber – or fighting more with the sword – is not possible to decide. It must be accepted that we have at least two performances as possible causative factors of glenohumeral pitting. Compared to the causes of medial degeneration these lateral certainly are to be considered few – even if they were three.

As to the occurrence of sword fighting and timber cutting, the last mentioned must have been the more common. The occurrence of sword fighting, however, has to be considered as highly probable – to which extent and the percentage of the population who carried it out is harder to decide. Timber cutting, considering the hard climate and the need for houses and firewood, certainly was of a general occurrence. Owing to the straighter ergonomic conditions as to direction of movement, load, and the pronated position in which the arm was held during the performance, sword fighting was chosen as the performance to illustrate the position for loading the posterocaudal region of the insertion. Glenohumeral pitting might as well be caused by timber cutting as by sword fighting as by possibly some other movement or performance fulfilling the requirements fulfilled by sword fighting and timber cutting.

CLINICAL EPILOGUE

Clinical practice prompted the original questions, and the theoretical answers either confirmed clinical, manual experiences or were easily applied back and confirmed in the clinical, manual praxis and routines. The rotational position's importance for the distribution of load is a good example; the location of the glenohumeral pitting indicates where the load is distributed, resulting from a special posture position, as in sword fighting. The location of the tendon insertion in the bicipital groove is another good example and of great value for the therapies such as friction, injection, and the ultrasonic treatment which must be given to the diseased part of the tendon insertion. The tendon insertion was previously not known to be located in the bicipital groove, but clinical experience confirms the osteological findings of this study, which in turn confirm the clinical diagnosis of tendinitis at this location earlier.

Periarthritis humeroscapularis (Duplay 1872) actually means pain and stiffness of the shoulder for an unknown reason ("inflammation" of the joint's surroundings). The precise location of the disease certainly is in the insertion of the tendineous rotator cuff on the greater tubercle. That is, in the insertion of the short abductors, as they are the one inserting on the greater tubercle, according to the designation used in this work. The functions of the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus are doubtless abduction and rotation respectively (Duchenne 1959 and others).

Paasila (1965) found more than 50% of 624 cases of periarthritis humeroscapularis to be supraspinatus tendinitis. Glatthaar (1936) found in 70 autopsies that degenerative changes affected the bone in 100% of the cases at 50-60 years of age. The predilect location for the tendinitis process was the right supraspinatus region. There have also been theories in the literature on arthrosis of the sulcus intertubercularis (bicipital groove), which are referred to by Glatthaar.

According to my findings in the osteological part on the degenerative changes, they are located in the bicipital groove, and the supraspinatus region laterally (see Part III). These are the most frequent locations (see Table 10, p. 91) and it is from a clinical point of view worthwhile to note the location in the groove, as the tendinitis here seems to be curable by ultrasonic treatment, which is not the case with all tendinitis.

In addition the glenohumeral pitting (in the medieval material) occurs dorsocaudally on the infraspinatus facet, laterally in almost every individual. In other words: degenerative changes are present in the bicipital groove, on the supraspinatus, and on the infraspinatus laterally in every individual, irrespectively of age and sex. Furthermore, most individuals have a SWA or glenohumeral pitting - a few females very distinctly and most males very clearly and much larger changes than most females; the mean for male SWA is 150 units, and for female SWA it is 50 square points (units).

The interpretation is that forward elevation (flexion) and some kind of lateral elevation (abduction) are the most common and most loaded movements - together with the very special elevation and rotation that occurs for example at parrying in sword fighting. Furthermore, these movements certainly are of high velocity. The forward elevation (or flexion) at the glenohumeral joint is a most common movement; it is noteworthy, then, that not only the supraspinatus part of the tendon insertion, but the bicipital groove as well is loaded by this movement. This is judged by clinical experience and the osteological findings (see tables pp. 91-94).

The next most usual movement seems to be the type movement which, pertaining to sword fighting, is always of high elevation, high velocity, and highly loaded. Timber cutting will certainly load the same part of the insertion.

According to clinical findings, and statistical calculation concerning

modern man, a supraspinatus tendinitis is most likely to occur during the first six weeks of tendinitis of the shoulder (continuous more or less agonizing pain in the shoulder, and stiffness). This suggests that the supraspinatus affection is the first to come in the disease, and that the infraspinatus tendinitis is more likely after six weeks – it comes later, perhaps as a result of overload (overuse) because of the diseased supraspinatus. Tendinitis localized in the bicipital groove seems to occur mostly in elderly people, often later than six weeks in the disease as well, but there is no statistical calculation of this impression.

Most pain and stiffness of the shoulder emanates from the insertion of the short abductors of the glenohumeral joint. These insertions are definitely the most loaded (by tractional load) part of the glenohumeral joint because of gravity and the very short inner lever, compared to the much longer outer lever. The process of tendinitis is dependent on load and unload, occurring in the transitional zone: tendon – cartilage – bone. To judge from the osteological material in this study, changes affecting the skeleton regularly occur before the age of twenty years (in the regions mentioned), whether causing pain or not. It has been proved that skeletal degeneration occurs in 100% at defined locations and ages in autopsy material from 1936 (Glatthaar).

The therapy in this very common disease should be load relief, and if necessary injections or friction, and possibly ultrasonic treatment. Treatments are here mentioned on a declining scale of effectiveness according to my clinical experience – in the order I think that treatment should be tried, which means that load relief is to be regarded the most effective treatment – and the most difficult to accomplish. Only load relief is not enough in severe cases, but facilitates the diagnosis.

All kinds of gymnastics and mobilisation (passive or active) are contraindicated, especially in the frozen shoulder syndrome, where the only thing one could do by using such methods is to cause harm. The glenohumeral joint is really frozen (or should be to correspond to the diagnosis, which is otherwise wrong), and no motion should occur. The stiffness in the cases is caused by a reversible shrinkage of the fibrous capsula, according to Melvin Glimsher in Boston (1960). Pain usually disappears when stiffness comes (if you do not treat) – it is like Nature's own immobilisation of the shoulder joint (the glenohumeral joint, actually) to relieve pain. The load in all kind of exercises seems to do more harm than good to the tendinitis. It will be recalled that the EMG investigation had to be halted because of the deteriorations.

It is impossible to stabilize or totally fixate the arm relative to the trunk, to absolutely hinder any motion in the glenohumeral joint, or to unload the insertion of the short abductors completely. My own experiences from treating fractures with plaster of Paris bandages prove that. Perhaps an adequate bandage, as it was used in the clinical study 1974-77 at Karolinska sjukhuset, did not totally hinder motion in the joint, nor unload the muscles completely, but definitely hindered the extreme movements. And the subject was made to keep the bandage on over night.

The beneficial effect of tape bandages was not measurable. But in small series (groups) there was a tendency for tape bandage only to be better therapy than the bandage and ultrasonic treatment. The interpretation is that without the ultrasonic treatment the arm was kept more at rest. The fact that the patients asked for a new tape bandage though they had cutaneous lesions from earlier tape bandages, speaks in favour of the beneficial effect of the tape bandages. The tape could not possibly do any other harm than to the skin anyhow. There is no risk of stiffness because of the bandage; the frequency of frozen shoulder is even lower than expected (than it would be without the tape) among patients having the tape from 3 to 6 weeks. The expected frequency would be 5-7%, and the observed frequency was $5:300 = 0.0167$, or less than 2%!

The sector which a fixation should be arranged at in a case of tendinitis, is indicated by the loading curve for the contact point method of calculating the loads at the abduction arc (Part I). The sector 30-60° of abduction is easy to reach with a pillow of suitable size; the arm should be 10-20° anteverted to the body's frontal plane, and slightly inwards rotated.

There is no risk whatsoever that stiffness could be caused by such fixation as tape (or by any other fixation, provided it does not load the insertion), whether tendinitis or not. In tendinitis, as soon as the pain disappears the mobility of the arm returns (if it is not a frozen shoulder). Surprisingly this seems to be the case even after a fixation lasting more than one year. In tendinitis it is the pain that is the problem, not the stiffness. In the frozen shoulder it is the stiffness that is the problem, not the pain. There is, however, an evident risk of somatic and psychic damage when a person with a stiff and painful shoulder is badgered with orders to move the arm, even if all movements provoke pain, as they usually do in tendinitis. Many such patients told me they had disobeyed the orders and found that the disobedience was beneficial to their shoulder disease.

Thus the precise location of the tendon insertion has come out of the osteological study and is confirmed in the clinical investigation. Most important is that the high loads have become possible to calculate, and the adequate unloading position for the short abductors is physically, mathematically explored. Moreover, the fact that this insertion is the one with the highest loads in the glenohumeral joint (and the shoulder joint) makes it plausible that it should be the predilect location for the tendinitis of the shoulder – just as all clinical experience suggests.

The load on the short abductors is high because the inner lever is short, the muscles work mostly anti-gravitationally, and the outer lever (the arm) is comparatively long. Inner lever 3-5 cm to outer lever 35-70 cm. That is, 1-2 kg could give a load of 200-300 kgf at a specific posture. The short abductors really need an extra support, which they are given at defined postures by the mechanism of the skeletal end positions, where the greater tubercle functions as a pawl, brought to the meeting with the edge of the glenoid cavity by adequate rotational position and direction of movement. This mechanism will, however, not give any support at high elevational levels. The rotational position, though, is of fundamental importance to the abduction test in diagnosis, where the load is being distributed by the humeral rotation.

It so happens that the medieval habit of sword fighting really confirms the theoretical basis for a useful clinical testing procedure in tendinitis, such as the MacLaughlin abduction test at a defined plane and different rotational positions. This test was described by Mac Laughlin (1965) based upon more than 500 cases of clinical examination and surgical exploration of the shoulder joint. Others have found it similarly useful and reliable in their clinical work (Fahlström – Brodin 1976).

The principle for distribution of load is actually self-explanatory. The art of the insertion facing upwards will be loaded at abduction in erect posture. The upright position, whether standing or sitting, with the movement occurring at a defined plane and rotational position are prerequisites for the testing, facilitating the standardization of the procedure. This can further be expressed (in more complicated terms): abduction with the thumb upwards will load the supraspinatus, and abduction with the little finger upwards will load the infraspinatus. The movement of the supraspinatus is inwards rotation, but the load will be distributed to its insertion at outwards rotated position of the humeral shaft. Likewise the function of the infraspinatus is outwards rotation, but the load will be at inwards rotated position.

Both muscles are abductors and rotators, and work as such, as ab-

ductors depending on the rotational position of the humerus, as rotators the supraspinatus in inwards, and the infraspinatus in outwards rotating. The rotational theory decides which muscle is abducting at a given posture position, and which part of the insertion is to be loaded. The rotational theory consequently influences the diagnostical test according to MacLaughlin, the location of the degenerative changes, and the spread of them during a life-span.

The glenohumeral pitting is the best proof of the dependence of the distribution of load on the rotational position. It could not exist if the load was not influenced by the rotation of the humeral shaft and caput, that is if the same part of the insertion was abducting, and the same part of the cuff, consequently, always received the load, regardless of rotational position. As proved in this study, the load is distributed to specific parts of the insertion, via the fibres of the muscle and tendon in function – and to different parts at different rotational positions. The distance between the medial part of the supraspinatus and the bicipital groove to the lateral part of the infraspinatus area (SWA or the glenohumeral pitting region) is 3-4 cm.

There are other findings which also confirm the importance of the rotational position for the distribution of load, for example the degenerations on the medial part of the greater tubercle and in the bicipital groove, where there is a constant high occurrence of degenerative changes (signs of wear and tear). This medial area is necessarily loaded by flexion and at outwards rotated position, as well as by inwards rotation at specific posture positions. Inwards rotation is propelled by the subscapularis muscle as well, another member of the already mentioned tendineous cuff inserting on the lesser tubercle. There is, however, clear evidence that the supraspinatus takes part in pronation in specific posture position (in clinical testing, for example). The forward elevational and inwards rotational movements seem to be very common, and may sometimes carry a load that is extra high and/or reach extreme elevational degrees; explaining the frequency of degenerative changes found in the mentioned region. These movements occur many, many times each day for each individual.

The abduction movement at inwards rotated position of the arm is not a common movement, regarding the posture position in which the arm is held. As far as I have been able to find out it occurs only in window cleaning, parrying, and timber cutting. To test and to find out the position of parrying, the reader is recommended to perform a simple test: pretend to ward off an offensive thrust with the arm and control the position of the little finger! In sword fighting it is certainly the parrying that gives the high loads. With the arm held at maximal inwards rotated position, the dorsocaudal part of the insertion will be loaded when parrying, attaining double the weight of one sword. Timber cutting is more difficult to calculate and even evaluate. It has to be rather high, anyhow. The advanced pitting in most males must have been caused by sword fighting or timber cutting – or both.

The clinical resumé, then, is the diagnostic test described by Mac Laughlin and confirmed as well as somewhat explained by the findings of this study. The location of degenerative changes in the bicipital groove are of importance, as clinical findings have indicated tendinitis to occur at this locus.

The necessity of somehow unloading the tendon insertion of the short abductors to heal tendinitis, and the possibility of pointing out where and how, are the most important findings of clinical relevance presented in this study, for practical purposes and for the patients.

GENERAL DISCUSSION

The old German theories on the application of mechanics to a joint – or application of the principles of mechanics to start with – have been above discussion almost for one hundred years. Now they seem to be beneath discussion, one could be tempted to say. It is not, however, that easy to reject them just because one or two things are obviously wrong. The idea seems to have been that the motion occurred round the central, imaginary axis, but the real joint surface decided the form of motion (Fischer 1907). Hence the *evoluta*, which is the motion of the central, imaginary axis because of the form of the joint surfaces. The *evoluta* of the knee joint is most distinct since the joint surfaces are very long in the knee, the joint is egg-shaped (ovoid), and a hinge joint, which is why there will be a great dislocation of the *evoluta*. Besides, because of the immense amount of thinking, some in certain aspects very interesting (the *evoluta*), it would be unwise to regard it as beneath discussion or definitely wrong. It is evident, however, that some difficulties have existed. One is the calculation of the inner force – no real correspondence to the axis of motion means no inner lever. A cut muscle surface is far too inexact to be used for computing forces; it was multiplied by a constant to get the value for the inner force.

It is obvious that the contact point theory supersedes the central, imaginary axis of motion theory, according to all experimental evidence, and for practical reasons as well as in the light of common sense. How can one know for sure that nothing will prove to be wrong with this new theory either? There are things known now by me to be incomplete and/or perhaps not fully satisfactory. There might equally well be something more which has been overlooked, or done the wrong way, that I am not aware of now, but that someone in the future will find as wrong as I have found the missing axis of motion (or its real correspondence), the inner lever etc., in the classical theory. So, lifting my hat to the German anatomists of the early 20th century, I will proceed to the literature on joint motion, joint surfaces, and the contact point.

Saha (1961) and Pieron (1973) discussed the contact point and the contact between joint surfaces. As Pieron is to be understood he points out the contact in all joints to be punctual, or confined to a very small surface, compared to the whole joint surface. "His joint", then, is the saddle joint proximally of the thumb. Saha's statement is essentially of the same content, but as to the glenohumeral joint he discusses a contact laterally (circular), or over the whole surface, in addition to the central contact point. The lateral, circular contact, or the total contact are not compatible with the contact point theory. With articular contacts apart from the central contact point the joint could not function according to the contact point theory; it would work in different conditions.

Naturally I am not in a position to say that Saha was wrong. However, I can state that I find his theories improbable, because I did not see any skeletal joints (in almost 100) with an abnormal contact, for example the lateral, circular type (as described by Saha 1958). On the contrary, they were all similar and moved freely with one contact point and almost the same skeletal end positions. Needless to say, I really had the opportunity to test and check the positions. Consequently I ought to have observed any abnormal contact, as I paid special attention to precisely this question.

Something that I was early made aware of was the muscular resultant, that is the direction in which the muscle force is directed and works. In the experimental model this direction has to be the same as occurs naturally. This is of importance for the relation inner load to outer load, the quotient, but not so important for the calculation, actually, as the force is decomposed. The model was rebuilt once to get the most natural direc-

tion possible. The outer load and the weight of the arm, however, are not natural. The weight of the arm is overlooked, and the direction of the outer force is normalised to a right angle. These facts cause the results to be not the exact loading curve for a human glenohumeral joint, with a weightless arm and a perpendicular to this directed force, representing gravity. It is possible to compute the values according to the direction of gravity by sine dividing, and it should somehow be possible to compensate for the weight of the upper arm by adding the computed force in the gravitational direction. Mostly practical difficulties made me refrain from putting these ideas into practice. The whole matter was, I have to admit, complicated enough as it already was.

The loading curves, then, do not exactly represent the loads present in the glenohumeral joint at erect posture as they should do, because of some really great practical difficulties in calculating them. The values do, however, give the values for forces working at equilibrium in the experimental conditions. These conditions are more like the circumstances in the human glenohumeral joint than in any previous experimental model known to us. The dissimilarity of the model to reality is that the weight of the arm is missing, and the gravity force is orthogonal to the outer lever. Tendencies of the curves are the same, only the highest motor effects at 45° (contact point), and 90° (central pin) should be somewhat higher. The differences at different levels of the abduction arc are more distinct according to the experimental model than in reality. The mentioned deviations (such as no arm's weight) affect just the loading curves and the quotients, as forces are decomposed at any rate.

The loading curves tell us where the load is high, and where it is low at the abduction arc. According to the contact point method there is a maximum of force at $30-60^{\circ}$, whereas this maximum is at $60-90^{\circ}$ if the central axis (pin) is utilized (reflecting the classical theory). All available information speaks in favour of the contact point. The fact of the contact point corresponding to something really existent, and the central axis of motion merely to something imaginary, is also definitely in favour of the contact point. A measuring device has to correspond to something real, which the imaginary axis does not.

The loads are rather high, specially at high abduction levels according to the contact point method of computing. The lowest load on the insertion is ten times the outer load; inner load $\times 0.1 =$ outer load. The highest loads on the insertion are 40-50% higher (0.5-0.6); the highest load was obtained for 0° and the central axis, hanging arm. Quotients were arrived at by dividing outer load by inner load. A high quotient consequently indicates a low load, high motor effect, and low velocity. The same load will give 165 units at 90° of abduction, or 100 units at 45° - just as 100 units at 90° are only 60 units at the sector $30-60^{\circ}$. This is valid for the contact point method, and means that speedy movements are more effectively performed at higher abduction level (or lower, for example initiating movement below 30°) and the movements at the sector $30-60^{\circ}$ are most advantageous for working.

As to the sword fighting type of movement, or any elevation, this means that the sword's weight at high elevation is twice the weight of one sword (whole arm's length), in addition pronated position making the load higher (lower quotient G:T); the weight of at least one arm and the offensive sword in parrying, all this makes the load extremely high - it is reasonable to assume 300-500 kgf but impossible to calculate exactly, as we are out of the abduction arc; also the rotational position is another than in the experimental model. As an estimate the weight of one sword could be 1-2 kg, meaning 200-300 kgf on the tendon insertion. In addition the kinetic energy, and the length of the "irregular" lever (out of the abduction plane). It is very likely that the load is more than 300 kgf on the specific area of the insertion in the parrying type of movement. We

are approaching the load on the planum popliteum and the origin for the medial gastrocnemius head (15 x 30 = 450). The loads in the hip joint are not far away either, even if they are probably higher (500 kgf and more). It seems reasonable that equal values should cause equivalent degenerative changes. In the calculations above, the weight of the sword is estimated at 1-2 kg, Petersen (1919). Double length of humerus, and the double weight of one sword at the parry movement have to be considered. This is why the load is extraordinarily high exactly at this specific movement.

To return for a short while to the imaginary axis in the humeral head's centre, it is to be noted that the general occurrence of central axes and axles, for example in wheels of all kind, might have influenced the human mind to expect a central axis in all mechanical devices. The eccentric axis of motion is intrinsically somewhat peculiar and revolutionary. The extracorporeal axis/axle at the spatial limit of the moving body is almost incomprehensible. There are, however, simple applications of this principle - for example, the seesaw. It should be stranger to a critical mind for a skeletal joint to bear any resemblance to a jumping jack, than for it to resemble, possibly, an ancient drawbridge. The only thing in favour for the jumping jack is a superficial resemblance. Mechanically the drawbridge is a much better model for the skeletal joints.

Summing up, the axis of motion is located in the joint, at the contact point. The loads are rather high on the insertion of the short abductors. The load is low at 30-60° and highest at 90°, extremely high in the parry movement pertaining to sword fighting, and timber cutting as well.

The skeletal end positions have not been previously described. One was defined by Henke in 1863, the two others in this study have been cursorily mentioned and partially described, but never defined. There are many skeletal end positions involving the greater tubercle and the edge of the *cavitas glenoidalis*, and even for the lesser tubercle there is one described in this study. The skeletal end positions of the glenohumeral joint all have this in common: They involve either the lesser tubercle or the greater tubercle and the edge of the *cavitas glenoidalis*. The acromion has been made responsible for the locking at 90° of abduction and again the locking has been proved to exist also after acromionectomy. The importance of the rotational position for the locking has been pointed out by those commenting the phenomenon.

In this study, the rotational position and the abduction degree have been regarded as the primary prerequisites. In addition the movement forward or backwards is of a very great importance as this movement redeems the locking. The backwards conduction causes the locking or the meeting of the skeletal elements both at spear throwing and forehand drive position, provided the adequate rotational and abduction positions exist.

No studies of forward conduction have been performed in this work, other than a small number of systematical observations (less than 15). There are, namely, skeletal end positions at forward conduction (forward conducted position), provided the adequate rotational and abduction positions exist. One such position involves the lesser tubercle.

The definition of a skeletal end position, then, according to this work is the same as Henke stated for his abduction stop in 1863, at 90°: meeting between the greater tubercle and the edge of the cavity, or according to the terminology also used in this study: pawl function of the greater tubercle, meeting the edge of the glenoid cavity, and bracing.

Equally important are:

1. The rotational position: 0°; 90°; 80°; at abduction, spear, tennis.
2. The abduction position: 90°; 85°; 54°; abduction, spear, and tennis.
3. Conduction forward or backwards: forward 10°; backwards 10°; backwards 45°.

To define these positions three angular values are required denoting the relation humeral shaft versus the tangential plane of the glenoid cavity at each position. There are three end positions defined in this work:

1. Henke's abduction stop at 90° , defined plane and rotational position.
2. The spear throwing positions (MacConaill's close packed position, 1960).
3. The forehand drive position (end of circumduction, Hjortsjö 1964).

In the literature one finds a discussion on the abduction stop in the 1930s in which Ohnsorge (1932), MacGregor (1932), and Martin (1936) contribute views on the rotational position, the acromion, the greater tubercle – but neither mentions the edge of the cavity. Saha 1958, on the other hand, points out that the abduction stop is present after acromionectomy, hereby giving a qualified reason against the acromion creating the abduction stop, and giving good support for the theories of Henke.

The end of circumduction is mentioned in various writings. Most clear, but as far as the rotation is concerned not completely correct, is the description in Hjortsjö's *Motions and Movements* (1964).

A cone with its apex in the joint, and circular movement at the distal end of the extremity are fully possible in a ball and socket joint, provided the joint is ideal – and provided nothing intrudes. For the glenohumeral joint of man the whole thing is dependent on the rotation of the humeral shaft taking place or not. It is perfectly possible to circle the arm and the hand from the glenohumeral joint, describing a complete cone in the air, from 90° of abduction, as well as from 45° , as in between. If, however, the arm is rotated simultaneously from a starting point with the palm of the hand dorsad (dorsum ventrad) to a final position with the dorsum of the hand dorsad (palm ventrad) – a clock-wise rotation – then the movement will stop at the end position of circumduction, which is equal to the forehand drive stroke and hit position in tennis, if the circumduction is performed at 45° of abduction. The rotation will take place (regarding the hand) at the elbow and the glenohumeral joint, about 90° each. And note well, the arm stops if we rotate the hand and the arm simultaneously with the circular movement (the palm rotates 180°), but not otherwise.

The explanation now is fairly plain and easy: we arrive at an end position, most clearly at 45° , corresponding to the forehand drive stroke. For some reason Hjortsjö describes the stop as occurring when the arm is not rotated. The rotation, however, is prerequisite for the locking, as it will bring the greater tubercle into position for its pawl function. The rotation can be palpated under the acromion; the greater tubercle is a prominent landmark.

There is not much more to be explained or discussed concerning the end of circumduction.

Considering the spear throwing, the position was found at a systematical search for skeletal lockings in the glenohumeral joint. A similar position is described by MacConaill in his close packed position of the glenohumeral joint, defined to be at 90° of abduction, outwards rotation, and backwards conduction – exactly like one in this study, namely the spear throwing. The definition is consequently very much similar to mine, which was important to me. The explanation differs somewhat, but the skeletal origin is not questioned. MacConaill (1960) considers the congruence of the joint surfaces, whereas this study emphasizes the meeting between the edge of the glenoid cavity and the greater tubercle, hereby offering a different explanation, valid also for the mechanism of the forehand drive (as related), and the abduction to 90° according to Henke (1863).

Regardless of what mechanism is thought to stop the motion in a joint,

these two are almost identical: the close packed position and the spear throwing position of the glenohumeral joint. The fact that the locking condition at this position had been recognized by two persons instead of only by one person was important - to me. I have been feeling very much in good company when reading the books by Professor M.A. MacConaill, as I did realizing the similarity of the two positions. I had a comparatively easy task to find the skeletal end positions, once the idea appeared - the idea was possible to read in a book of Henke from 1863. The problem was apparently to exclude the function of facets as insertion, and still keep it, or to combine the functions as a pawl and as insertion, which was made at the autopsy table. The facets were free to act as pawls, and at the same time fulfil a function as tendon insertion. Once the locking positions were found there were so many of them that I could not mention them all.

In the literature, then, we find notes not only on the abduction stop, which was completely related by Henke in 1863, but also on the forehand drive and the spear throwing, defined as probable skeletal lockings, but incompletely described or explained. In the hope that the description now given is correct and as complete as possible, I will leave them here and turn to the ergonomic functions of the skeletal end positions.

As the skeletal end positions are new and unknown, not much is known about the enormous ergonomic effects they imply. Just try to imagine a javelin contest, where the competitors not use their skeletal end positions, only the rotator cuff muscles, for the throwing - it should be impossible! Compared to the forces delivered by the pectorales, the serrati etc. thanks to the locking of the humerus with the scapula, the power of the intrinsic scapular muscles is very small. I would rather not discuss how they can be sufficient in sword fighting, but they are obviously not! Much more is not possible to say about the ergonomics implied by the skeletal end positions of the glenohumeral joint today. No measurements have been made, and they are certainly not easy to make either.

The methods could be discussed, and will be. The point is that measurements of the kind described in this study never have been carried out previously. As stated earlier it has been a qualified manual performance to make the measurements as well clinically as osteologically. The inexactness for both clinical and skeletal measuring was not more than 5-10°. In skeletal measuring it was more obvious that different possibilities could exist; this was evident especially for the abduction level of spear throwing, which could be chosen to be from 70° to 90°. The skeletal part, the pawl of this locking, is the ridge between the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus part of the insertion area, which makes the choice of level rather free - which is advantageous in the practice of throwing, even if precisely the javelin throwing was practised at a more precise level. Thanks to the great freedom for level at throwing I had to intentionally restrict the readings to correspond just to javelin throwing, i.e. between 80 and 90°, which shows up in the statistics as a systematical variation, indicating definitely highest values for p (most similarity) regarding the values for skeletal spear throwing.

It has been mentioned that the measuring of skeletal preparations was made without any support at one arm-hand - the other manoeuvring the angular caliper, which was transparent so it could be aimed at the plane required for the measuring. The clinical measuring was almost as difficult as the skeletal, though there was a natural cohesion, there was also a restricted view as for the aiming at the planes. The real difficulty at clinical measuring was to decide the planes by palpating landmarks. This difficult part was facilitated by Professor Harald Brodin, giving me advice and access to the 30 clinical subjects to perform the measurements on.

The whole investigation of angular values was specific, and qualified, as nobody had done anything like it; it really was terra nova to set foot on. This made it even more important to do it correctly and in a manner that could be described and repeated. The basic principle (in clinical measuring) is that the tangent to the spina scapula (middle part) is perpendicular to the tangential plane of the glenoid cavity, and the margo vertebralis (medialis) tangent only deviates 10-20° from this plane. There are more aids which cannot be mentioned here because of lack of space. Inquiries will be welcomed and answered. Anybody attempting these measurements is bound to run into difficulties. The investigation of the hip joint according to the principles laid down in this study, will necessarily cause still more difficulties, skeletal as well as clinical. The skeletal preparation will need some support, the end positions will not have the same mechanism. An experimental model would be enormous, and difficult to transport in an ordinary car.

As to other joints, they certainly have their skeletal end positions. I remember observing one at the wrist once, a locking in dorsal flexion, consisting of a precise adaptation of the small bones (naviculare, capitatum, lunatum in a triangle), getting close packed in against the distal radius and stopping the dorsal flexion. Nowhere do I think, however, the skeletal end positions are so bright and clear as in the glenohumeral joint both anatomically and functionally.

The thing now remaining to be discussed is the statistical method. The one-way analysis was chosen to elucidate the variance between individual joints, and consequently also between subjects. Truthfully the two-way analysis of variance also tested, indicated an unlikeness in some groups, regarding the measurements in the same individual, and regarding method, not between the different subjects. So the one-way analysis was used to test if the subjects (the individual joints) exhibited great differences or not as to the angular values for their abduction levels at the skeletal end positions. The same method was used for the skeletal and the clinical material, two values for each position clinically and six values for each position skeletally.

Regarding the sex difference in the occurrence of glenohumeral pitting, the four-fold contingency table according to chi-square with one degree of freedom was used.

The results for both clinical and skeletal measuring clearly speaks in favour of the values of angular measurement at each position being similar between different individuals, which implies that a systematical choice of values occurs somehow, most probably by the choice of Nature, indicating that the skeletal end positions are a built-in mechanism in the glenohumeral joint of man, specific to the species *Homo sapiens*.

There is one more thing to discuss: Are the abduction levels enough to define the mechanism of the skeletal end positions? Honestly, I do not actually think they are, but rotational positions are very hard to measure exactly, and perhaps would not vary much; backwards conduction should have been statistically computed for tennis and spear, as well as the forward conduction for abduction 90°. One could not expect them to vary so much, however, that it would influence the judgement of the abduction positions and the heavy statistics, including multiple measuring – and if they did deviate, not even that should influence the judgement for the above mentioned reasons. So, after all, I think the abduction values are enough. Eventually the values for backwards conduction in spear throwing were calculated (skeletal material), and were found to be within the limits, i.e. $F = 1.2$, $p = 0.3$.

A propos of terra nova, the cystical degenerations from tractional load at origins, insertions, and/or attachments are relatively new. Though they were referred to in 1931 by Putschar, and even earlier by Loeschke (1912), which has been referred to in the 1970s according to references

in Part III of this study (p. 79), mostly regarding the female pelvis and loads caused by pregnancy and childbirth. With Gejvall's revelation in 1974 of popliteal pitting, observations have been made out of the pelvic girdle; other locations than the spine and the pelvic girdle were open for the future research. Via the knee joint there were open lines to the hip and shoulder joints. The findings on the planum popliteum have been related in Part III of this study, including some mechanical aspects, as to the magnitude of the loads and the probable mechanism for their creation (p. 80 and p. 87).

The cysts are said to be aseptic necroses. The cause of necrosis is evidently dependent on the tractional load. The patho-genesis for the tendinitis has long been considered to be a partial rupture and small hemorrhages. Personally I have long believed in the same mechanism as in the subdural hematoma: osmotic swelling of an encapsulated tissue, rich in protein and salt (blood) deposited in a milieu interieure which is more watery (liquor and interstitial fluid, respectively). The swelling by osmotic pressure could explain some rather large cysts, the multilocularity, and the phenomenon that some cysts cause pain and some do not. This difference might depend on the time factor, how long time it will take to create the cyst, swelling and pressing. Variations in pain as to intensity, duration, etc. are easily explainable according to this theory. Whether the cyst impresses the bone or not depends on location and maybe duration. Most probably it will take many cysts to create a pitting, and many hemorrhages to make a pit or a cyst. Cysts are often multilocular and situated on a large, depressed area, where the level is lower than the surrounding cortical bone cortex. This arrangement also seems to fit well with the osmotic theory of these cysts. For the subdural hematoma, see Trotter's original work: *On the pachymeningitis hemorrhagica interna* (1914), London.

We know what tools we have, how they were found, how they were created, and why. We know what they look like, and where they are situated: where the load is. Consequently we are able to calculate where we can expect to find the degenerative cysts. It is now our task to work with them, to make them tell their stories, why they appear just where they are found etc. The primary conclusion is that where we find the cysts, there is an insertion, attachment, or origin situated. The next thing is to find out what anatomical structure corresponds to the location - capsula, insertion for a tendon, attachment of ligament, or origin of a muscle. The next and very important thing is to judge the load, the probable frequency of load, or the possibilities for extremely high load - by analysing the ergonomics of the joint in question, regarding both inner and outer lever.

Thus, the decision where the insertion of the short abductors are located was a relatively easy task. The next thing to decide - why the changes are located exactly where they are - was a bit more difficult. According to the clinical testing, however, the load is distributed by rotation of the humeral shaft. The same principle must be valid for the creation of degenerative changes. The most striking phenomenon is the glenohumeral pitting, but it took months of cogitation to begin to realize what it was - naturally, and what I now am convinced that it is. Everything points to the sword fighting (especially the parry movement) as the causative factor of glenohumeral pitting: a high frequency of skeletal wounds from edged weapons in the Westerhus material, the technique and the position of the arm at sword fighting, not at least the pronated (inwards rotated) position, verified by a cut at the elbow region (lower humerus) from the radial to the ulnar side, dorsally, shortly before death in subject No. 183 in Westerhus (right side). This subject carried a very large and typical glenohumeral pitting as well (used for illustrations in Part III, Fig. 35, p. 84).

All these facts are in favour of the theory that parrying in sword fighting could pertain to male glenohumeral pitting (or maybe better vice versa). No single performance could possibly have resulted in a higher load on the dorsocaudal part of the insertion of the short abductors, where the glenohumeral pitting is located. So, according to the calculations, the medieval and the Viking era's sword fighting subjected a small part of this specific insertion to extremely heavy loads. Such loads are unlikely to occur in the future, just as it is unlikely that they should have occurred earlier in history. No wooden clubs were lifted with the arm pronated (at inwards rotated position); the parry movement of sword fighting is unique. Possibly equalled by the load on the same region in timber cutting. A moderate pitting, then, could be caused by unarmed parrying (self defence), or timber cutting.

Pronated position, or inwards rotated, by the way is the usual position in parrying, but also in parrying with the unarmed arm, a movement that per se could give rise to degenerative changes, similar to the glenohumeral pitting, but not to the same extent or size.

Glenohumeral pitting occurs among males with few exceptions. The difference between the sexes is highly significant (chi-square = 11.215 with one degree of freedom). There is an occurrence of a less outspoken pitting in some women, the cause of which could be guessed, not confirmed. The traumatology should be confined to the soft tissues, the guess, then, being that the reduced pitting should be a result of some females regularly having defended themselves. We have to refrain from that guess, however, as it cannot be confirmed by skeletal remains. The occurrence of the specific, pronounced glenohumeral pitting almost exclusively among male subjects is supporting the theory of a linkage between glenohumeral pitting, timber cutting or sword fighting.

Other degenerations are not easy to interpret, excluding the most medial, in the bicipital groove and the lateral supraspinatus aspect. They have necessarily been caused by flexion-inwards rotation (pronation) which is a very common movement, since they occur in every individual from below the age of 18. The general occurrence of these degenerative changes leads to the conclusion that they represent a common movement. The ergonomics fit in well with this assumption. The most medial and the most lateral parts, then, can be analysed and their function identified – in between it is impossible to tell anything. These two, however, the most medial and the most lateral, are separable, distinguishable. There is a distance of 3-4 cm between the anatomical parts, and a clear difference as to what kind of movement that gives the load.

Most ruptures in the insertion of the short abductors, according to this discussion, are caused by flexion and pronation (medial corner), and the parry movement: high elevation in pronated position. That is to be understood in the following lines: flexion and pronation are extremely common movements, usually of a moderate load – occasionally, however, of higher load (velocity, weighty objects etc.). Parrying pertaining to sword fighting as a type of movement is to be looked upon as occasionally occurring, but when it occurs implying extremely high loads. Flexion-pronation is a daily routine including some extra heavy loads, once a day, once a week, for example. The load is deciding, more than frequency; it is the ruptures that count. Repetition certainly is needed too, as far as for example glenohumeral pitting is concerned. Whenever occurring, however, the extreme loads of parrying in sword fighting are repeated – that day. Just lifting the sword at one hand implies very high loads in the specific insertion. The overloading, the extra high or extremely high loads are prerequisite for the creation of degenerative changes. The occurrence of sword fighting, however, is somewhat obscure. The occurrence of timber cutting is clear enough.

All other degenerations pertain to some unknown movements, occurring

in daily life and sometimes with an extra high load, extra high velocity – or both. Maybe there could be some specific movements giving rise to specific degenerations as to size and location, but it is not possible to approach the two mentioned in clearness and exactness. This material of scarcely 100 pairs of humeri is at all events too small to permit the analysis of degenerative changes over a 2.5 to 3.5 cm long area, the changes approaching each other, not being separated as the two examples given above. They are separated 3-4 cm and are each 0.75 to 1.25 of the insertion area's length in centimetres. The degenerative cysts are not accessible clinically as they do not manifest on x-ray. At operation they are filled with blood or other soft tissues. They are palpable only by the tenderness which is their characteristic.

It might seem careless to state that there is nothing more to get out of the investigation of the insertion area ergonomically pertaining to the distribution of load and kind of movement. But why careless? Are not the results already achieved good enough? There is one clinically very useful piece of information on the location of the insertion medially, another historical item on the fighting habits, and, regarding to ergonomics of the glenohumeral joint, some really important information as to the distribution of load and its location due to the rotational position of the humeral shaft. More precisely, the above mentioned degeneration, pertaining to sword fighting and denoted glenohumeral pitting, is probably linked to the parry movement, where the load is necessarily at its height. This degenerative sign really proves the function and the influence of the rotational position. The occurrence of sword fighting is already manifested by the traumatological findings. It seems probable, then, that other medieval populations should present glenohumeral pitting as well as the Vikings should be prone to do so.

In addition we have obtained information that the degenerative changes spread during a life-span, together with a general idea of how they spread. The distribution and spread during lifetime also presents an indication of the location of the tendon insertion, manifested by the accumulated degenerative signs in a population.

It now seems unnecessary to discuss the central items of the study together to any further extent. Suffice it to state that the loads are high on the insertion of the short abductors in the glenohumeral joint, especially in high and rapid lifts such as must have occurred in sword fighting; that the importance of the skeletal end positions is paramount primarily to the ergonomics of the joint by the unloading of the very insertion of the short abductors, but in defined posture only; and lastly that the degenerative signs manifest the insertion on the greater tubercle, confirming the high loads as well as the importance of the rotational position for the distribution of load in the insertion.

GENERAL SUMMARY

The summary will contain the theoretical solution of the application of mechanics to joints, according to this study and compared to what existed previously. It will also include the revelation of the skeletal end positions, including their definition (or methods by which they have been defined). The end positions are new territory (almost), as there existed no concept of skeletal end positions previously. The degenerative changes, lastly, are quite new in clinical medicine, though well known in archaeological osteology and forensic medicine from studies by Angelo (1967), Nemeskéri (1972), and Herrman & Bergfelder (1978) *inter alia*.

The summary consequently comprises the osteological, central part of the study, including experimental mechanics, definition of mechanics and interpretation of its ergonomic consequences, the spread of degenerative changes and the interpretation of its locations.

As to the principles of mechanics and their application, the classical German theory did not actually give the impression of being totally correct. Above all, the axis of motion, in actual fact a measuring device, was imaginary. The method for the calculation of the inner force was therefore impossible to set up, and the method used did not really seem to be realistic: The cut muscle surface to be multiplied by a constant! How was that constant calculated - or was it chosen?

The outer force was calculated (and still is calculated) from the imaginary measuring device central in the convex part of the joint. This was taught on a course for orthopedic surgeons in 1979 by a specialist in joint mechanics for skeletal joints from the Mayo Clinic, Y. Chao.

I wanted the forces to comply with physical laws known to me, and not to depend on a cut muscle surface or anything else. Besides, I had long ceased to believe in the central axis of motion. So I had to figure it out, create some mechanical set up and perform experiments of some kind.

The problem was two-dimensional, the basic theory actually one-dimensional concerning the orthogonal vector quantity, but considering the parallelogram of forces still two-dimensional. I decided to perform the study experimentally in two dimensions, comprising two muscles with almost the same function, only depending on rotational position; to select a plane well defined also as to rotation of the humerus, where a part of these muscles created the muscle resultant for the abduction movement; and to study the load on the insertion for the short abductors where the supraspinatus and the infraspinatus meet at the highest top of the greater tubercle. The model was built of profiled steel and teflon to decrease friction. The important thing, then, was to copy the two-dimensional projection of a human humerus on the adequate plane. This was done with the aid of a craniophore and a diagraph. That much I had learned or got confirmed during the course of skeletal biomechanics: the mechanics of a skeletal joint has to be studied in one joint and two dimensions, and for one muscle (muscle resultant). The experiments were planned to comprise the classical theory with a central axis, and the intra-articular, "heretical", exploiting the contact point.

Having an extremely skilful and imaginative collaborator, a craftsman interested in my project as well, I had no special difficulties in getting the model realized. The length of outer lever had to be just that of humerus for practical reasons, the epicondylar plane was chosen to represent the end of humerus as it manifests the level of load (the joint surfaces). Many practical details were solved in a rather conventional manner, dynamometers constituted the forces and were fastened to hooks or a steel-line (see photo). The phenomenon aimed at and looked for was the equilibrium at each abduction level and different loads. The kinetic energy was therefore disregarded, as was the friction.

Furthermore, the exact direction of the gravity force was disregarded,

experiments being performed orthogonally (to save space in the construction of the model). It should be possible, however, to calculate the force in the direction of gravity by dividing with a corresponding sine value. The outer force in that case will be higher. The loading curve would look otherwise, as outer force to inner force quotient is higher. As $\sin 0^\circ = 0$, the impossible zero could appear and complicate the calculation.

So the measurements were all orthogonal, not only the forces and the levers were decomposed to right angles in the system, but also the outer force (normally at another angle, directed gravitationally). By this method a lot of calculation was unnecessary, the zero was avoided, measurements were at right angle between the outer force (load) and the outer lever, which is a small deviation from the natural functional position. By this method, however, the forces could be calculated at equilibrium; the difficulties lay in exactly defining the contact point in case it was used as the axis of motion. The difference between using the central axle (pin) as to manipulation of the model was not great, only the axle was otherwise defined, but regarding the values there was a real difference. Most measurement values were constant for the central axis, with only the alpha angle (for inner force) changing. The contact point, on the other hand, is constantly moving; as the humeral head glides down in the glenoid cavity, the contact point migrates upwards. As a consequence the inner lever will get shorter at a higher level of abduction, just as the outer will get longer, and these factors work in the same direction: to heighten the load of a given weight or force, but also to increase velocity – a higher gear! It is after all not customary to work in a position with the arm elevated more than 60° of abduction, specific sports and occupations excepted.

According to the contact point theory, the highest capacity of the human glenohumeral joint is at $30-60^\circ$ of abduction. In case of the fixed central axle (pin), the experimental values indicate the highest capacity above 60° of abduction – where we all know it is not. The central axis of motion is thought, however, to move according to the shape of the joint, considering the evoluta, but this could not change the result much, as the caput is almost spherical. A migration at the periphery of the caput of the contact point working as an axis of motion will influence the length of the levers, and consequently the results, more. The loading curves definitely point out the contact point to be the physiological axis of motion for the glenohumeral joint of man, according to experience and for mechanical and teleological reasons.

Skeletal end positions have been known to exist more than at the abduction stop at 90° . They were caused by a meeting between the greater tubercle and the acromion according to a theory emanating from Ohnsorge, MacGregor, and Martin in the 1930s. This theory was disproved (1961) by Saha, stating the stop to be present after acromionectomy. The truth about the abduction stop was already told by Henke in 1863. He stated that a meeting between the greater tubercle and the edge of the glenoid cavity caused the stop, and that the rotational position had to be neutral and the movement performed at a defined plane, 10° anteverted to the body's frontal. In the event of supinated position of the humerus, the meeting will not occur.

Other skeletal end positions have been only somewhat described, such as the end position of circumduction, and the close packed position of the glenohumeral joint as described by MacConaill and explained as depending on congruence of joint surfaces regarding the close packed position, no references being made to the structures mentioned by Henke.

According to the findings in this study, the end position of circumduction and the close packed position of the glenohumeral joint are both skeletal end positions, and dependent on the meeting between the greater tubercle with the edge of the glenoid cavity. This meeting in turn is

dependent on the rotational position of the humerus and its spatial position as to abduction degree, and forward or backwards conduction. The two new skeletal end positions investigated occur in backwards conducted position, and are: the initial position of spear throwing, and the forehand drive stroke in tennis, where the javelin is accelerated and the tennis ball hit, respectively. Spear throwing is to be understood as javelin throwing in a contest for athletes in our days, or in older days the spear used as a missile weapon, e.g. in hunting. The forehand drive in tennis should be self-explanatory and susceptible of only one interpretation – it is the moment when the racket hits the ball that is intended.

The point of interest in the skeletal end positions is the stability, and even more the extra muscular force available through the locking. The humerus is locked with the scapula and has to follow any forward movement, which recruits the pectorales, the serrati anteriores, and perhaps even more muscles such as the trapezius. The same is true of the forehand drive stroke in tennis. As we know, the opposite hand for support is only used in the backhand position; it seems as if the forehand drive is somehow firmer than backhand and more forceful by itself. And so it is – because of the skeletal locking, recruiting more muscles and more power in tennis, just as in javelin throwing. One has to see these skeletal lockings both live and in skeletal preparation to understand them. So given the opportunity, the reader is recommended to manipulate a skeletal preparation to check where the greater tubercle meets the edge of the glenoid cavity, and in what posture position of the extremity bones the locking will happen.

The forehand drive is the broadest and skeletally most stable locking (the broadest contact); the broader infraspinatus facet comes into contact with the edge of the cavity, and they fit like a joint. Both 90° of abduction and spear throwing occur at a higher degree of abduction. The smaller supraspinatus part of the facet's area meets the edge of the cavity at a somewhat higher level (the stalk of the pear). These contacts are not so broad, especially not the spear throwing, but still firm enough. Spear throwing or casting utilizes this skeletal mechanism at different levels, from 70° to 90° of abduction in the same subject, judged by the skeletal form. This level is probably more restricted in lifetime by habits and preferences. It is to be noted, however, that not only spears but all kinds of things may be thrown by the mechanism, as well as heavy towing etc. can be performed by the aid of the locking; for example pushing and carrying can be made more forceful by the use of the end position of circumduction (the same as the forehand drive position).

To manifest these new skeletal end positions, they were measured skeletally as well as clinically. The most qualified and reliable measuring is the skeletal. The possibility to see the referent planes, to aim through the transparent angular caliper felt more scientific than the clinical, still rather qualified as measuring. The skeletal measurements are six per position, three times as many as the clinical. Clinical measuring comprised 30 subjects, skeletal measuring originally 46. This means close to 5 000 angular values in tables. The one-way analysis of variance proved to be the adequate method. The significance was put to 0.05 as it was the null hypothesis, i.e. the angular values not being dissimilar, that was of interest. Therefore 0.05 was the highest level for this so to speak "inverted" significance. To chose say 0.025 should mean a lower demand for the values to be similar, statistically.

The measurements were technically-manually a very qualified undertaking. Skeletal preparations were held in one arm-hand without support, just as a child is held, and with the left preparation in the left arm-hand of the examiner and vice versa. The free hand manoeuvred the caliper of a type used by geologists with long arms. The clinical measurements were

no less troublesome, as one had to find the landmarks on the scapula and the humerus, and to make the right judgements to find the probable tangential plane. Advised by my former teacher, Professor Harald Brodin, and given access to the clinical material from him, it was possible to carry out the clinical investigation. Results from the clinical and the skeletal measurings are equal.

By examining a large number of subjects, both skeletal and clinical, and doing it several times – six in the skeletal and two in the clinical – a comparison was made between live and dead, ancient and modern, a statistically satisfactory number of observations were available. At the same time a possibility of learning the method was secured. The skeletal measurings absorbed more than three months, the clinical about the same, but not for the same reasons. Statistical calculation, then, included some training and also absorbed a few month's time. The conclusion is: there is a mechanism, built into the glenohumeral joint of man, for skeletal end positions, manifesting its function to everyone who cares to look for it, skeletally, clinically, in the performance of various sports, and not least when examining a joint properly. These skeletal end positions supply extra muscular force by a locking of the humerus with the scapula at defined posture positions.

It is somewhat surprising that these skeletal end positions could have been overlooked for more than one hundred years after the complete description of the abduction stop (Henke 1863). There are more skeletal end positions than the three-four mentioned in this study. Initially I was planning to describe at least a dozen, but that should have been too much – for me as well as for the reader. Suffice it to say that we have observed skeletal end positions at forward conduction as well, and that the present head of the Osteological Research Laboratory, Professor Torstein Sjøvold, has pointed out where the lesser tubercle is functioning as a pawl ("sword draught position").

As to the question why the skeletal end positions were overlooked, it could have something to do with the belief in authorities; they did not mention any skeletal locking, so nobody cared to look for it. It was the same as for the central axis; the direct contact in the joint seems to have been a secondary question. The skeletal anatomy has been overlooked concerning the axis of motion, as well as concerning the fact that "something" was intruding the ideal, spherical movement of the humeral shaft at the glenohumeral joint. The something was probably considered to be of soft tissue origin.

Measuring the surfaces of the facets in the belief that they were the tendon insertion, we had to pass three stages of comprehension: 1. tendon insertion, 2. pawls, 3. both. The intra-articular location of the facets was checked at autopsy. The fact of degenerative changes existing on the facet surface proved their function as insertion. Glenohumeral pitting is located more or less on the facet surface of the infraspinatus region dorsally. The facet surface is smooth when not degenerated, not a typical insertion at all. The construction is related in part III, and will be only briefly related here. The insertion is Y-shaped, the functional point of attack must be considered located where the branches of the Y meet. The area for attachment, then, is the lateral aspect of the greater tubercle and the facet surfaces – to the articular cartilage. The construction implies a firmly adherent tissue on the facets surface, permitting the pawl function of the facet, and its functioning as an insertion.

It might be difficult for a critical mind to accept these new theories about the end positions of skeletal origin (skeletal end positions). What I could recommend in such a case is to watch a tennis match or javelin contest, and to recognize the postures where lockings are said to occur – or not. Further, the sceptic should gain access to a skeletal preparation

and look carefully at the positions given in this study - the clinical measuring I would not recommend (more than as aiming, possibly).

It has been noted in the literature, however, that there is a stop at the end position of circumduction. The close packed position of the glenohumeral joint, corresponding to the spear throwing position, has been mentioned too, by MacConaill. These are the most typical and common skeletal end positions, and definitely easiest to describe and exemplify.

Doubtless it is because of man's anatomy that he uses the javelin as a missile weapon, nobody ever saw an ape do it the same way. It is also because of man's anatomy that tennis is played the way it is. One could here state that the reason for bearing the sword on the left side of the body is the same in case of right-handedness, to be able to take it out of the sheath.

As another possible reason for the skeletal end positions not being observed previously, one could speculate over the difficulties of spatial thinking, or the fact that the facets, according to the textbooks of anatomy, were occupied by the function of being tendon insertions - and nothing else (the function as insertion should exclude any other function).

The small and sometimes somewhat larger cysts at the insertion of tendon insertion, origin of muscle, and attachment of ligamental-capsular structures have been recognized since the 1930s, especially the last ten years. They were also described by Ingelmark in the 1950s, located to the vertebrae and interpreted as inflammatory or allergic and secondary to tooth infection. They have been related by Swedborg to be correlated to pressure load and tractional load. High loads are assumed to exist in the pelvis of a pregnant female in late term, and at childbirth. This load is not continuous, of course, but repeated usually 6-8 times during a life-span in medieval times, in the absence of contraceptives. The changes are to be found near the articulation of the pelvic girdle, the pubes and the sacroiliac regions, as well as the ligamental attachments elsewhere, and the insertion for abdominal muscles. Changes of this type have been used for sex-determination of a museal preparation in Stockholm: the Barumman, or rightly the Bäckaskogswoman, as she was the mother of several children, according to the pelvic signs of wear and tear. As a fisher-woman she had worked hard and aquired "male" tendon insertions elsewhere, which is possible. In addition she was tall in stature, having allophyseal measures. So the definite sexing had to be done according to the occurrence of the cystic degenerations in the pelvis, secondary to childbirth, which are not likely to occur in male subjects (Gejvall 1970).

The most specific degenerative sign hitherto has been described on the planum popliteum of middle-neolithic fishermen from the isle of Gotland, by Gejvall (in Janzon, 1974), where he performed the osteological investigation and wrote this part of the study as head of the Osteological Research Laboratory at the University of Stockholm. Gejvall described the popliteal pitting which, as a professor of osteology with an experience of some 30 years in the field, he found to be an unique phenomenon, interpreted as the result of heavy load during paddling, fishing, and hunting at the sea (the Baltic sea). The pitting usually occurred in the left knee, but might occur in the right - or in both sides. Sometimes there were also, or instead of a pitting, proliferate changes in the cavity. The number of subjects carrying such marks were 9, all males. Anyhow, these small cavities and the proliferative changes were large enough to arouse the interest of a well trained and competent osteologist, the circumstances being considered to warrant a very strong suggestion that they were caused by tractional load. The largest cyst had a comparative figure (see part III) for volume of approximately 300 - comparative as the cyst is no ideal sphere and the figure is obtained by multiplying its size $8.5 \times 5 \times 6.8$ mm.

As the present study started at the Osteological Laboratory when Professor Nils-Gustaf Gejvall was the acting head of it, it is to be understood that I was aware of these cysts - I had the preparation in front of me several times before measurement made it clear that the largest cyst in the Westerhus material, where glenohumeral pitting is concerned, was just a little bit larger than the largest in the middle-neolithic material. The size of the medieval pitting was 8.6 x 5.9 x 6 mm (medieval = 304.44, middle-neolithic = 289 in comparative units). On the other hand, all cysts were not that big, but they occurred in almost every male's shoulder. It was possible to define the posture positions, the motion of the joint, and the movement of the extremity, that is the exact posture at which the arm was held during this performance. These things have been explained in Part III, and it is not necessary to repeat them here. The performance referred is the parry movement pertaining to sword fighting. This is certainly a very high load, and the pitting is the most distinct degenerative sign of the glenohumeral joint, as the popliteal pitting certainly is so for the knee joint, the pitting equalizing the degenerative changes of the hip joint. The size of the largest cysts (pittings) of the knee and the shoulder are comparable, but signs on the greater tubercle are not equalling changes in the hip joint (proliferative changes in addition).

As to the glenohumeral joint the distribution of load and its dependence on the rotational position is of the greatest interest. By this influence it is easy to separate movements in supinated and pronated position. In the insertion area these loads will concentrate on medial and lateral structures, or parts of the insertion, respectively. That is why it is possible to state with all reasonable certainty and all probability (without having carried out any experiments) that in parrying - especially pertaining to sword fighting - the load is distributed to the lateral, caudal (posterior) part of the facet part (infraspinatus) of the insertion area. This location is where we find the glenohumeral pitting, the most distinct mark of degeneration of the glenohumeral joint, comparable to the popliteal pitting in size, but not so pronounced as this and the degenerative changes of the hip joint (fossa intertrochanterica, e.g.). So the highest load coincides with the most pronounced degenerative marks in the glenohumeral joint. Medieval sword fighting is to be apprehended as carried out with one arm, weight of sword 1-2 kg, Petersen (1919).

Another movement is two-armed timber cutting, also loading the dorsocaudal region or SWA. This has been discussed in Comments. Flexion at the glenohumeral joint (elevation forward) is certainly one of the most common movements, occurring in daily life, loaded more or less, never unloaded (arm's weight - gravity). The load of this common movement is located medially (opposite to the pitting at 3-4 cm distance), in the bicipital groove and laterally on the supraspinatus part of the insertion. This region is constantly the location of massive signs of degenerations in all individuals, which speaks for a correlation to the most common movements. Ergonomically the location and the movements described are corresponding. If one specific disease should be located in this area, it could be "pitcher's" disease, as the ball is thrown with a spin and very forcefully, and the training for a pitcher is almost life long. This is only an ergonomical, clinical guess, not a statement, and no prediction or conclusion.

The intermediate loci, such as ISSP (on the supraspinatus-infraspinatus borderline), at the top of the tubercle, on the facet, towards the cartilage, are not explainable on the basis of this material. They must represent some specific (or maybe non specific) movements; they appear later in life (40 years) and may indicate a transference of load from laterally to the facets. I will leave these intermediate changes, then, with this comment; they remain to be identified as well and precisely as sword

fighting and forwards lifting, which are opposite in the insertion, and therefore are easy to define and separate. The cystical changes are not possible to study clinically. They are not visible on x-ray. They are palpable only by pain provocation, but not visible even at operation as they are filled with soft tissue or blood. The only way to study these cysts is on dry macerated bone, or preparated bone – not living bone.

Regarding the existence of degenerative cysts caused by tractional load, they are far above question, they are here – and they have come to stay. They are a part of today's knowledge about Nature. In addition can be stated that they occur round every big joint such as the elbow, knee, hip, shoulder, wrist etc. At the hip joint the fossa intertrochanterica (intertrochanteric fossa) looks like a pitting that has been given an anatomical name. Anyhow, it takes only a systematic observation to find a variety of degenerative changes at this locus, proliferative as well as cystical. The load is most certainly high enough round the hip joint to create these changes. For details see part III. The obturati, which insert in the trochanteric fossa, correspond to the short abductors in the glenohumeral joint. Note well, most of the changes referred to are caused by capsular and ligamental attachments. It is obvious, even if prematurely stated here in the summary, that these signs – discrete perhaps, but still signs of degeneration – have come to stay and to give more information in the future on the function of skeletal joints in health and disease. They can give some information archaeo-osteologically as well, even if not all information is as clear as that concerning the parry position. Thus glenohumeral pitting could be used as a criterion of the occurrence of sword fighting in a material. This is thanks to the warriors of Westerhus – and thanks to the medieval habit of sword fighting and timber cutting, thanks to "Them, from whom we learned". Silent, without any aim of teaching, involuntary, but totally clear and unmistakable.

GENERAL CONCLUSIONS

Part I

1. The axis of motion is situated in the joint space at the contact point.
2. The load on the insertion of the short abductors in the glenohumeral joint is very high, at some posture positions extremely high, depending on elevation, rotation, and velocity.

Based upon two-dimensional experiments and a comparison between the central axis of motion in the humeral head (pin), and the intra-articular contact point as an axis of motion (corresponded in reality by the natural joint) the conclusion is drawn that the intra-articular contact point is the natural axis of motion for the joint. The imaginary, central axis is rejected. Loads are calculated to be lowest at a sector of $30-60^{\circ}$, and highest at 90° of the abduction arc, which is the free range of movement of the joint at the defined plane from 0° to 90° of abduction, and defined rotational position.

Loads are extremely high at the parry position, pertaining to sword fighting, which is out of the abduction arc's plane at inwards rotated position, and a very high elevational degree, highly loaded, and of high velocity. In the arc the load on the insertion of the short abductors is about twice the load at 90° , compared to the load (of the same weight) at 45° of abduction. In case of parrying the load is doubled once more (two swords meeting). We then arrive at the magnitude of several hundred kilograms (200-300). The load could as well be similarly high at timber cutting.

Part II

3. Skeletal end positions are a mechanism of the glenohumeral joint in man, giving extra force at defined posture positions.

Comprehensive studies on joints, skeletal as well as clinical, give the same results: there are locking conditions in the glenohumeral joint of man, occurring at nearby the same position in every individual. The ergonomic importance of these skeletal end positions or locking conditions, is paramount by enabling man to throw the spear (javelin) and to play tennis. The locking positions are being used in daily life, and many types of activity. They are useful by unloading the short abductors and giving stability and extra force at defined posture positions.

Part III

4. Degenerative changes from tractional load indicate the location of the tendon insertion. Glenohumeral pitting verifies the importance of the rotational position.

By measuring and evaluating the cystical changes located on the top of the greater tubercle, where the insertion area for the short abductors is located, it has been proved that the insertion is located on the facets and laterally, down to the epiphyseal line. Some specific distributions of degenerative changes have been described in this work, and interpreted as caused by defined activities. One such activity is flexion in supination of the arm, causing the location of degenerative signs medially in the insertion. Another type of movement is the high elevation at maximally pronated position (inwards rotated), pertaining to the parry movement and timber cutting. So the flexion and the supination - both occurring

very frequently but not always so highly loaded – cause the changes medially and in the bicipital groove; whereas the high elevations at pronated position always are extremely high loaded (the weight of one or two swords), but do not occur so frequently. The degenerative signs from these two types of movement are located oppositely, and at a distance of 3-4 cm in the insertion. They offer clear evidence of the importance of the rotational position as to the distribution of load. Timber cutting will load the posterocaudal part of the insertion.

The four conclusions are dependent on each other; the loads are high, the end positions relieve the loads – but not in all positions – from the insertion of the short abductors, and give extra force at some exemplative sport functions: spear throwing and forehand drive in tennis. The degenerative changes have developed in a regular pattern, interpretable by elementary mechanical rules, where the highest and/or most frequently loaded parts of the insertion are carrying the most distinct signs of degeneration. These parts are not protected from overload by the mechanism of the skeletal end positions.

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ADDITIVE LIST OF REFERENCES FOR ILLUSTRATIONS,
PHOTOGRAPHS, AND SKETCHES

There are four sources: Benninghoff 1949 as to illustrations (anatomical). Photographer Lars Wiklund and the author as to the photographs. Lars Wiklund made all copies. Kurt Simons created the sketches after my advice, as well as the diagram (in Part I).

So that are all the sources. Regrettably they have not been given in the text to all illustrations. That is why the missing follow here:

- Fig. 16. Photo the author, copy Lars Wiklund.
- Fig. 17. Benninghoff 1949.
- Fig. 18. Photo Lars Wiklund, set up by the author.
- Fig. 19-21. Photo the author, copy Lars Wiklund.
- Fig. 22-23, diagram etc. Kurt Simons.
- Fig. 26. Photo Lars Wiklund.
- Fig. 29-30. Photo Statens rättsläkarstation, Stockholm.
- Fig. 31. Photo Lars Wiklund, mounting the author.
- Fig. 32. Benninghoff 1949.
- Fig. 34-39. Photo Lars Wiklund.

APPENDICES

To avoid tabulations of angular values in the text, as for skeletal measurements, they have been gathered in the appendices as far as angular skeletal measures are concerned. Means and standard deviations are given in Part II (p. 63, Table 5) for the skeletal material used for the statistical calculations.

The angular values for abduction clinically are listed in Appendix I (60 joints). In Appendix II all the skeletal measurements for 92 joints are tabulated (abduction-forward, backwards-rotation). They have not all been used, as the clinical joints were 60 and just 60 were needed to make the materials equal, allowing for age and sex.

In the 92-joint table values of abduction, forward-backwards conduction and rotation, totalling almost 5 000 measurements (4 968). In the 60-joints table are listed just the abduction angular values as they constitute the material for the statistical calculation (total values given in Part II, pp. 66-67, Table 6).

The clinical values have all been given in the text of Part II. The joints are not listed in the same order in the 60-list as in the 92-list. The complete list, consequently, gives all angular values to define the orientation of the humerus versus the tangential plane of the glenoid cavity, skeletally. The forward-backwards values reflect a certain constancy, the rotational values are set to 80° for forehand, and 90° for spear throwing. The abduction level is chosen to be $80-90^{\circ}$ for spear throwing from reasons related in Part II pp. 58-59. The rotational degrees were mentioned in Part II pp. 60-61.

APPENDIX I

Skeletal angular abduction values to define skeletal end positions

Skeletal material, 30 subjects, 60 joints, three age groups, 51-70, 36-50, and 21-35 years, 5 females and 5 males in each group. 90° abduction (Henke 1863), spear throwing, and forehand drive, only abduction levels for the statistical analysis. Westerhus No. below 95-100 mostly females, above 95-100 mostly males. The table gives the angular values for computing the statistics of abduction levels in the skeletal material.

Abduction 90°

No. 32	dx	90	91	93	96	93	92
	sin	87.5	87.5	97	94	95	97
No. 62	dx	93	92	91	95	94	96
	sin	91.5	96	93	93	95	93
No. 44	dx	86	97	93	91	93	94
	sin	96	98	90	97	95	98
No. 71	dx	103	101	88	97	95	98
	sin	98.5	96	90	95	96	96
No. 52	dx	95	94	96.5	95	95	94
	sin	92	97	98.5	98	97	94
No. 109a	dx	96.5	96	91	85	93	94
	sin	96	93	93.5	90	91	97
No. 111	dx	87	96	93	92	95	97
	sin	92	89	89	91	93	94
No. 213	dx	91	97	97	95	93	93
	sin	90	97	97.5	97	93.5	91
No. 156	dx	94	93	90	93	98	95
	sin	97	96	94	95	98	99
No. 201	dx	92	95	97	93	97	93
	sin	86	96.5	94.5	94	91	93
No. 15	dx	94	96	90	95	91	93
	sin	99	97	101	95	94	96
No. 21	dx	99	91	91	87.5	91	96
	sin	97	97	90	89	95	93
No. 63	dx	98.5	97.5	93	95	94	96
	sin	92	99	99	97	98	98
No. 84	dx	86	90.5	91	90	92	94
	sin	92	91.5	97.5	91	94	96
No. 72a	dx	107	97	91	90	93	97
	sin	100	97	96	91	93	93

No. 181	dx	96	86	86.5	90	93.5	93
	sin	94	95	97	93	96	95
No. 158	dx	98	101	96	98	90	92
	sin	97	102	93.5	96	95	93
No. 133a	dx	98	97	90	99	96	94
	sin	90	88.5	87	95	93	96
No. 159	dx	96.5	90	86	90	94	95
	sin	99	86	88	95	94	96
No. 131	dx	89	89	89	94	93	94
	sin	92.5	85	86	91	95	96
No. 55a	dx	85	92	98	93	93	94
	sin	97	94	94	93	94	93
No. 97b	dx	103.5	96	97	92	94	93
	sin	105	99	99	93	94	94
No. 1	dx	93	96	94	97	97	94
	sin	97	102	96	93	93	95
No. 60	dx	92	91	94	93	93	95
	sin	96	92.5	93	97	94	99
No. 94a	dx	90	91	93	91	94	93
	sin	90	87.5	94.5	93	96	93
No. 116a	dx	97	91	93	92	93	93
	sin	97	90	93	96	93	97
No. 155	dx	98	97	94	94	95	99
	sin	101	99	97	94	93	94
No. 3	dx	91	91	90	95	93	96
	sin	89	87	89	94	94	94
No. 138	dx	98.5	97	91	95	93	94
	sin	97	88.5	93	93	94	94
No. 190	dx	96.5	87	91	95	94	94
	sin	96	93	97	96	93	93

Spear throwing

No. 32	dx	86.5	86.5	83	86	83	84
	sin	84	83	86	83	85	86
No. 62	dx	84	79	81	85	84	85
	sin	90.5	91	89	83	84	86
No. 44	dx	82	83	78	86	84	83
	sin	89	83	81	83	83	86
No. 71	dx	82	89	80	83	83	86
	sin	81	89	83	85	83	87
No. 52	dx	83	87	88.5	86	83	83
	sin	87	93	83.5	87	85	84

No. 109a	dx	89	87	83	80	85	84
	sin	91	93	84.5	80	84	86
No. 111	dx	83	91.5	87	86	85	84
	sin	88	87	83	83	83	84
No. 213	dx	87	91	87	87	83	85
	sin	78	91	90	91	84	84
No. 156	dx	86	83	81	87	87	85
	sin	87	85	83	87	87	88
No. 201	dx	89	93	89	87	84	84
	sin	87	87	80	87.5	86	83
No. 15	dx	93.5	92	90	83.5	81	84
	sin	91.5	91.5	90	87.5	88	85
No. 21	dx	88	79	83	83.5	86	84
	sin	91.5	81	78	84	87	86
No. 63	dx	94.5	94.5	87	83	83	82
	sin	84	94	85	86	85	87
No. 84	dx	92	81	87	85	88.5	84
	sin	98	84	90	83	83	83
No. 72a	dx	88.5	87	89	80	84	85
	sin	96	92	90	84	86	84
No. 181	dx	82.5	83	82	87	81	85
	sin	88.5	88	84	80	84	85
No. 158	dx	89	91	90	85	85	83
	sin	90	92	87	86	83	84
No. 133a	dx	96.5	93	83	87	85	85
	sin	96	83.5	83	85	85	86
No. 159	dx	83	87	80	85	83	86
	sin	81	86	83	90	87	87
No. 131	dx	81.5	99	86	89	83	82
	sin	97	91.5	87.5	85	85	83
No. 55a	dx	82	85.5	87	82	83	84
	sin	84	87	86	85	87	86
No. 97b	dx	78	88	89	83	83	84
	sin	91	89	91.5	82	83	83
No. 1	dx	85	87	83	86	83	83
	sin	90	93	84	85	85	85
No. 60	dx	85	94.5	82	83	84	83
	sin	85	94	82	85	85	86
No. 94a	dx	88	83	82	83	81	83
	sin	89	88.5	86.5	86	86	84

No. 116a	dx	83	81	87	86.5	84	83
	sin	81	92	83	85	83	86
No. 155	dx	86	85	83	87	85	87
	sin	87	89	84.5	88	87	86
No. 3	dx	78	81	78	85	86	86
	sin	84	85	84	85	87	83
No. 138	dx	84	85	84	85	83	86
	sin	96	87	84	83	84	83
No. 190	dx	92	78	87.5	87	87	86
	sin	86.5	81	86.5	85	86	84

Forehand drive

No. 32	dx	56	53.5	52	52	56	54
	sin	55.5	54.5	52.5	55	53	55
No. 62	dx	53	57	54	52	54	54
	sin	53	57	57	53	53	58
No. 44	dx	60	56	57	53	51	52
	sin	61	52.5	56.5	51	54	54
No. 71	dx	55	57	55	53	55	53
	sin	55	53	53	56	54	52
No. 52	dx	58	58	53	49	52	53
	sin	57	57	57	53	56	55
No. 109a	dx	54	51	53	55	53	53
	sin	53.5	53	53.5	52	52	57
No. 111	dx	56	56	53	52	53	57
	sin	57	52	53	55	53	52.5
No. 213	dx	54	60	55	54	52	53
	sin	59	54	54	56	53	52
No. 156	dx	55	56	57.5	52	57	57
	sin	56	55	57	57	56	58
No. 201	dx	57	57	54	57	52	53
	sin	49	52.5	52	53	51	51
No. 15	dx	56	58	58	52	53	53.5
	sin	57.5	59	57	57	58	57
No. 21	dx	53	53	53	53	52	57
	sin	58	56	53	54	54	54
No. 63	dx	56	54	53	55	56	56
	sin	57	56	53	56	54	57
No. 84	dx	55	57	55	53	52	53
	sin	54	52	53	55	52	57
No. 72a	dx	56.5	52	57	51	53	54
	sin	54	53	54	54	54	53

No. 181	dx	58	60	57	54	52	52
	sin	56	54	53	58	52	55
No. 158	dx	53	54	54	52	53	54
	sin	54	53.5	57.5	55	58	53
No. 133a	dx	53.5	58	57	60	52	50
	sin	63	50	57	58	52	55
No. 159	dx	54	53	52	55	52	52
	sin	55.5	54	53.5	55	55	56
No. 131	dx	56	57.5	52	54	55	56
	sin	55.5	58.5	56	57	57	57
No. 55a	dx	56	58	57	54	53	52
	sin	56	57	57	53	52	53
No. 97b	dx	54.5	53	54	53	56	58
	sin	55.5	54	50	52	52	57
No. 1	dx	58	54	57	52	52	54
	sin	59	55	57	52.5	57	53
No. 60	dx	57.5	53	53	53	52	53
	sin	57	53	52.5	54	53	56
No. 94a	dx	51	56	53	52.5	52	54
	sin	50	58	53	54	54	56
No. 116a	dx	55	54	57	53	53	52
	sin	54	55	53	54	57	58
No. 155	dx	56	55	53	56	57	57
	sin	57	56	53	58	53	58
No. 3	dx	56	56	57	56	56	58
	sin	54	58	56	57	58	58
No. 138	dx	55.5	52	57	54	56	57
	sin	56.5	53	54	55	53	52
No. 190	dx	56	53	57	54	56	57
	sin	57	56	56	53	53	52

Skeletal angular values to define skeletal end positions, including forward-backwards rotational position. Total skeletal material

46 subjects, 92 joints, two values for the inclination humeral shaft versus the tangential plane of the cavity, and one rotational for each position, measured 6 times = 1104 measurements. The measurements have been made without support, the skeletal preparation in one hand-arm, the other measuring.

Rotational positions are not measurable by routine methods; forward and backwards conduction do not vary much and can not be conclusive for the question if a mechanism is at hand or not. That leaves the abduction position to be statistically analysed.

Abduction 90° is defined to occur at 10° forward conducted position (anteversion), rotational position = 0°.

Rotational position at spear throwing = 90°. Rotational position of the forehand-drive = 80°. Both postures occur at outwards rotated position and backwards conduction. They have their ergonomic importance at forward conduction (locking humerus-scapula, adding thoraco-scapular muscles).

Values are given in the order: abduction level - forwards or backwards conduction - rotation. Each subject identified by a Westerhus No., sex and age. Abduction 90°, spear throwing, forehand-drive; right and left arm.

No 32, woman, 50-60 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	90 - 11 - 0	91 - 10 - 0	93 - 10 - 0	96 - 9 - 0	93 - 6 - 0	92 - 7 - 0
	sin	87.5 - 9 - 0	87.5 - 13 - 0	97 - 9 - 0	94 - 7 - 0	95 - 8 - 0	97 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	86.5 - 12 - 90	86.5 - 9 - 90	83 - 11 - 90	86 - 9 - 90	83 - 12 - 90	84 - 11 - 90
	sin	84 - 14 - 90	83 - 14 - 90	86 - 9 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	85 - 13 - 90	86 - 12 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 48 - 80	53.5 - 46 - 80	52 - 43 - 80	52 - 47 - 80	56 - 45 - 80	54 - 47 - 80
	sin	55.5 - 46 - 80	54.5 - 47.5 - 80	52.5 - 47.5 - 80	55 - 48 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	55 - 47 - 80

No 56, woman, 25-30 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	101 - 13 - 0	113 - 10 - 0	93 - 13 - 0	93 - 6 - 0	92 - 7 - 0	93 - 10 - 0
	sin	91.5 - 9 - 0	93 - 7.5 - 0	95 - 9 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	100 - 15 - 0	99 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	83 - 7 - 90	93 - 14 - 90	83 - 12 - 90	85 - 15 - 90	87 - 12 - 90	85 - 13 - 90
	sin	86 - 12 - 90	87 - 17 - 90	83 - 16 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	92 - 13 - 90	87 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 47 - 80	58 - 48 - 80	54 - 45 - 80	52 - 43 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	56 - 47 - 80
	sin	57 - 48 - 80	56 - 46.5 - 80	57 - 44 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	51 - 42 - 80

No. 55a, woman, 25-30 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	85 - 9 - 0	92 - 7 - 0	98 - 9 - 0	93 - 13 - 0	93 - 10 - 0	94 - 12 - 0
	sin	97 - 13 - 0	94 - 14 - 0	94 - 15 - 0	93 - 10 - 0	94 - 11 - 0	93 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	82 - 10 - 90	85.5 - 13 - 90	87 - 6 - 90	82 - 14 - 90	83 - 15 - 90	84 - 13 - 90
	sin	84 - 16 - 90	87 - 6 - 90	86 - 13 - 90	85 - 12 - 90	87 - 10 - 90	86 - 12 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 43 - 80	58 - 48 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	54 - 45 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	52 - 47 - 80
	sin	56 - 45 - 80	57 - 45 - 80	57 - 47 - 80	53 - 45 - 80	52 - 43 - 80	53 - 46 - 80

No. 15, woman, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	94 - 8 - 0	96 - 12 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	95 - 8 - 0	91 - 7 - 0	93 - 9 - 0
	sin	99 - 11 - 0	97 - 10 - 0	101 - 8 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	94 - 10 - 0	96 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	93.5 - 6 - 90	92 - 6 - 90	90 - 6 - 90	83.5 - 6 - 90	81 - 11 - 90	84 - 11 - 90
	sin	91.5 - 9 - 90	91.5 - 6 - 90	90 - 13 - 90	87.5 - 10 - 90	88 - 12 - 90	85 - 9 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 46 - 80	58 - 43.5 - 80	58 - 43 - 80	52 - 45 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	53 - 47 - 80
	sin	57.5 - 44 - 80	59 - 42 - 80	57 - 46 - 80	57 - 46 - 80	58 - 42 - 80	57 - 44 - 80

No. 116a, man, 30-35 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	97 - 15 - 0	91 - 6 - 0	93 - 8 - 0	92 - 6 - 0	93 - 10 - 0	93 - 8 - 0
	sin	97 - 13.5 - 0	90 - 12 - 0	93 - 10 - 0	96 - 8 - 0	93 - 7 - 0	97 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	83 - 19 - 90	81 - 16 - 90	87 - 11.5 - 90	86.5 - 11 - 90	84 - 86 - 90	83 - 11 - 90
	sin	81 - 21 - 90	92 - 17 - 90	83 - 17 - 90	85 - 13 - 90	83 - 7 - 90	86 - 9 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	55 - 49 - 80	54 - 45 - 80	57 - 45 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	52 - 48 - 80
	sin	54 - 51 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	53 - 46 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	58 - 42 - 80

No. 62, woman, 50-60 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	93 - 9 - 0	92 - 10 - 0	91 - 13.5 - 0	95 - 15 - 0	94 - 16 - 0	96 - 9 - 0
	sin	91.5 - 11 - 0	96 - 12 - 0	93 - 7 - 0	93 - 15 - 0	95 - 13 - 0	93 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	84 - 6 - 90	79 - 18 - 90	81 - 16 - 90	85 - 15 - 90	84 - 13 - 90	85 - 12 - 90
	sin	90.5 - 5 - 90	91 - 7 - 90	89 - 8 - 90	83 - 12 - 90	84 - 16 - 90	86 - 14 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	53 - 45 - 80	57 - 55 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	52 - 46 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	54 - 47 - 80
	sin	53 - 44 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	57 - 44 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	53 - 45 - 80	58 - 42 - 80

No. 21, woman, 35-40 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	99 - 6 - 0	91 - 10 - 0	91 - 9 - 0	87.5 - 8 - 0	91 - 10 - 0	96 - 11 - 0
	sin	97 - 3 - 0	97 - 8 - 0	90 - 11 - 0	89 - 9 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	93 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	88 - 7 - 90	79 - 11 - 90	83 - 11 - 90	83.5 - 7 - 90	86 - 12 - 90	84 - 12 - 90
	sin	91.5 - 12 - 90	81 - 13 - 90	78 - 16 - 90	84 - 13 - 90	87 - 10 - 90	86 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	53 - 47 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	52 - 43 - 80	57 - 47 - 80
	sin	56 - 42 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	57 - 44 - 80	57 - 46 - 80	57 - 48 - 80

No. 73, woman, 20-25 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	98 - 12 - 0	106 - 9 - 0	93 - 8 - 0	101 - 8.5 - 0	98.5 - 8 - 0	97.5 - 7 - 0
	sin	96.5 - 14 - 0	98 - 16 - 0	94 - 9 - 0	99 - 9 - 0	96 - 10 - 0	98 - 6 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	84.5 - 5 - 90	96 - 13 - 90	88 - 12 - 90	89 - 9 - 90	89 - 12 - 90	86 - 14 - 90
	sin	85 - 13 - 90	88 - 13 - 90	86 - 9 - 90	89 - 8.5 - 90	88 - 13 - 90	87 - 12 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	57 - 47 - 80	54 - 42 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	58 - 43 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	52 - 44 - 80
	sin	56 - 42 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	57 - 44 - 80	57 - 46 - 80	57 - 48 - 80

No. 156, man, 35-40 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	94 - 13 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	90 - 16 - 0	93 - 10 - 0	98 - 10 - 0	95 - 10 - 0
	sin	97 - 11 - 0	96 - 13 - 0	94 - 14 - 0	95 - 13 - 0	98 - 9 - 0	99 - 10 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	86 - 14 - 90	83 - 11 - 90	81 - 16 - 90	87 - 12 - 90	87 - 9 - 90	85 - 15 - 90
	sin	87 - 13 - 90	85 - 11 - 90	83 - 14 - 90	87 - 6 - 90	87 - 11 - 90	88 - 9 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	55 - 45 - 80	56 - 42 - 80	57.5 - 42 - 80	57.5 - 42.5 - 80	57 - 48 - 80	57 - 47 - 80
	sin	56 - 45 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	57 - 46 - 80	57 - 48 - 80	56 - 47 - 80	58 - 48 - 80

No. 155, man, 30-35 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	98 - 9 - 0	97 - 8 - 0	94 - 10 - 0	94 - 11 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	99 - 9 - 0
	sin	101 - 10 - 0	99 - 10 - 0	97 - 13 - 0	94 - 8 - 0	93 - 9 - 0	94 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	86 - 12 - 90	85 - 14 - 90	83 - 15 - 90	87 - 13 - 90	85 - 15 - 90	87 - 16 - 90
	sin	87 - 13 - 90	89 - 15 - 90	84.5 - 14.5 - 90	88 - 12 - 90	87 - 13 - 90	86 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 43 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	53 - 46 - 80	56 - 44 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	57 - 43 - 80
	sin	57 - 44 - 80	56 - 44 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	58 - 42 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	58 - 48 - 80

No. 121, man, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	109 - 10.5 - 0	98 - 8.5 - 0	95 - 17 - 0	99 - 6 - 0	93 - 13 - 0	93.5 - 12.5 -
	sin	90 - 10.5 - 0	92 - 11 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	95 - 5 - 0	97 - 5 - 0	99 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	88 - 8 - 90	89 - 5 - 90	86 - 6 - 90	91 - 8.5 - 90	84 - 7 - 90	84 - 9 - 90
	sin	89 - 8 - 90	81.5 - 7 - 90	86 - 7 - 90	85 - 5 - 90	87 - 4 - 90	86 - 5 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	58.5 - 41 - 80	56 - 41 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	54 - 43 - 80	57 - 47 - 80	54 - 47 - 80
	sin	59 - 41.5 - 80	56 - 41.5 - 80	55 - 43 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	58 - 48 - 80	57 - 47 - 80

No. 44, woman, 50-60 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	86 - 9 - 0	97 - 11 - 0	93 - 7 - 0	96 - 9 - 0	96 - 9 - 0	95 - 11 - 0
	sin	96 - 8 - 0	98 - 11 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	91 - 11 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	94 - 6 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	82 - 11.5 - 90	83 - 9 - 90	78 - 12 - 90	86 - 11 - 90	84 - 11 - 90	83 - 13 - 90
	sin	89 - 10 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	81 - 10 - 90	83 - 09 - 90	83 - 09 - 90	86 - 11 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	60 - 45 - 80	56 - 45 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	51 - 48 - 80	52 - 47 - 80
	sin	61 - 46 - 80	52.5 - 43 - 80	56.5 - 41 - 80	51 - 43 - 80	54 - 45 - 80	54 - 48 - 80

No. 140, man, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	102 - 7.5 - 0	100 - 7 - 0	93 - 12 - 0	96 - 9 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	96 - 9 - 0
	sin	97 - 7 - 0	97.5 - 13.5 - 0	97 - 9 - 0	100 - 10 - 0	94 - 13 - 0	94 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	84 - 11 - 90	97 - 7 - 90	87 - 13 - 90	86 - 8 - 90	86 - 16 - 90	85 - 16 - 90
	sin	93 - 8 - 90	92 - 13 - 90	85 - 10 - 90	92.5 - 16 - 90	87 - 14 - 90	86 - 15 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	57.5 - 43 - 80	57 - 40 - 80	56 - 44 - 80	57 - 47 - 80	54 - 47 - 80	52 - 44 - 80
	sin	57 - 42 - 80	57 - 42 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	53 - 46 - 80	57 - 42 - 80	58 - 47 - 80

No. 38, woman, 25-30 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	100 - 7.5 - 0	103 - 8 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	99 - 11 - 0	97 - 10 - 0
	sin	96 - 10 - 0	101 - 9 - 0	89 - 6.5 - 0	100 - 8 - 0	97.5 - 9 - 0	96 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	97 - 13 - 90	87.5 - 9 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	83 - 15 - 90	85 - 15 - 90	85 - 15 - 90
	sin	91 - 6 - 90	87.5 - 13 - 90	89 - 6.5 - 90	87 - 14 - 90	91 - 16 - 90	87 - 12 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	53 - 44 - 80	53 - 46 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	52 - 47 - 80	49 - 47 - 80	52 - 45 - 80
	sin						

No. 72a, woman, 35-40 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	107 - 12 - 0	97 - 12 - 0	91 - 13 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	97 - 11 - 0
	sin	100 - 10 - 0	97 - 9 - 0	96 - 12 - 0	91 - 8 - 0	93 - 9 - 0	93 - 6 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	88.5 - 10 - 90	87 - 12 - 90	89 - 12 - 90	80 - 13 - 90	84 - 12 - 90	85 - 07 - 90
	sin	96 - 13 - 90	92 - 12 - 90	90 - 10 - 90	84 - 9 - 90	86 - 11 - 90	84 - 11 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56.5 - 42 - 80	52 - 44 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	51 - 43 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	54 - 43 - 80
	sin	54 - 42.5 - 80	53 - 45 - 80	54 - 47 - 80	54 - 13 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	53 - 47 - 80

No. 158, man, 35-40 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	99 - 9 - 0	101 - 8 - 0	96 - 6 - 0	98 - 8 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	92 - 11 - 0
	sin	97 - 8 - 0	102 - 7.5 - 0	93.5 - 8.5 - 0	96 - 7.5 - 0	95 - 9 - 0	93 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	89 - 9 - 90	91 - 9 - 90	90 - 7 - 90	85 - 8 - 90	85 - 15 - 90	83 - 15 - 0
	sin	90 - 14 - 90	92 - 15 - 90	87 - 13 - 90	86 - 14 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	84 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	53 - 45 - 80	54 - 42 - 80	54 - 45 - 80	52 - 44 - 80	53 - 46 - 80	54 - 45 - 80
	sin	54 - 43 - 80	53.5 - 44.5 - 80	57.5 - 42.5 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	58 - 44 - 80	53 - 43 - 80

No. 34, woman, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	101 - 10 - 0	100 - 9 - 0	91 - 16 - 0	91 - 6 - 0	93 - 13 - 0	94 - 9 - 0
	sin	96 - 11 - 0	96.5 - 13 - 0	90 - 13 - 0	95 - 12.5 - 0	93.5 - 12 - 0	94 - 12 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	94 - 9 - 90	96.5 - 8 - 90	84 - 10 - 90	86.5 - 9 - 90	87 - 8.5 - 90	82 - 6 - 90
	sin	87 - 8 - 90	89 - 11.5 - 90	83 - 10 - 90	85 - 10 - 90	87 - 15 - 90	83 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	52 - 47 - 80	50 - 46.5 - 80	51 - 47 - 80	52 - 47.5 - 80	52 - 48 - 80	51 - 47 - 80
	sin	53 - 44 - 80	51 - 43 - 80	50 - 48 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	51 - 47 - 80	53 - 45 - 80

No. 97b, woman, 25-30 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	103.5 - 13.5 - 0	96 - 9 - 0	97 - 7.5 - 0	92 - 9 - 0	94 - 8 - 0	93 - 9 - 0
	sin	105 - 11.5 - 0	99 - 8 - 0	99.5 - 9 - 0	93 - 9 - 0	94 - 8 - 0	94 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	78 - 10.5 - 90	88 - 8 - 90	89 - 9 - 90	83 - 9 - 90	83 - 11 - 90	84 - 13 - 90
	sin	91 - 4 - 90	89 - 13 - 90	91.5 - 8.5 - 90	82 - 9.5 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	83 - 15 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	54.5 - 41 - 80	53 - 41 - 80	54 - 47 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	56 - 47 - 80	58 - 47 - 80
	sin	55.5 - 42 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	50 - 48 - 80	52 - 44 - 80	52 - 42 - 80	57 - 43 - 80

No. 57, woman, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	107.5 - 13 - 0	91 - 9 - 0	94.5 - 7.5 - 0	95 - 9 - 0	96 - 16 - 0	93 - 15 - 0
	sin	94.5 - 11 - 0	96 - 9 - 0	96 - 8 - 0	86 - 13.5 - 0	95 - 14 - 0	94 - 13 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	93 - 5 - 90	81 - 6 - 90	87 - 11 - 90	89 - 12 - 90	80 - 14 - 90	83 - 13 - 90
	sin	95 - 4 - 90	93 - 6 - 90	89 - 13.5 - 90	86 - 13.5 - 90	84 - 10 - 90	84 - 12 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	59 - 41 - 80	57.5 - 47 - 80	56 - 43 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	52 - 45 - 80	57 - 47 - 80
	sin	57 - 41 - 80	55 - 41.5 - 80	59 - 42 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	54 - 45 - 80	58 - 44 - 80

No. 53, woman, 25-30 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	107.5 - 18.5 - 0	97 - 13 - 0	91 - 7.5 - 0	92 - 9 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	93 - 11 - 0
	sin	94.5 - 11 - 0	97 - 15 - 0	92 - 11 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	93 - 13 - 0	92 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	90.5 - 17 - 90	83 - 8 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	87 - 15 - 90	85 - 10 - 90	82 - 13 - 90
	sin	85 - 9 - 90	87 - 9 - 90	85 - 11 - 90	82.5 - 12 - 90	84 - 11 - 90	85 - 14 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	67.5 - 41 - 80	57 - 43.5 - 80	53 - 44 - 80	53 - 46 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	53 - 48 - 80
	sin	68.5 - 43 - 80	55 - 41.5 - 80	56 - 43 - 80	54 - 47 - 80	56 - 46 - 80	53 - 47 - 80

No. 1, woman, 20-25 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	93 - 18 - 0	96 - 11 - 0	94 - 12 - 0	96 - 8 - 0	96 - 10 - 0	93 - 11 - 0
	sin	97 - 9.5 - 0	102 - 13 - 0	96 - 8 - 0	97 - 8.5 - 0	97 - 9 - 0	94 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	85 - 10 - 90	87 - 13 - 90	83 - 8 - 90	86 - 7.5 - 90	83 - 9 - 0	83 - 13 - 0
	sin	90 - 3 - 90	93 - 12 - 90	84 - 13 - 90	85 - 15 - 90	85 - 13 - 90	85 - 9 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	58 - 42 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	57 - 47 - 80	52 - 45 - 80	52 - 45 - 80	54 - 45 - 80
	sin	59 - 43 - 80	55 - 46 - 80	57 - 46 - 80	52.5 - 43 - 80	57 - 47 - 80	53 - 47 - 80

No. 3, man, 20-25 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	91 - 13 - 0	91 - 12 - 0	90 - 11 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	96 - 9 - 0
	sin	89 - 15 - 0	87 - 13 - 0	89 - 14 - 0	94 - 11 - 0	94 - 13 - 0	94 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	78 - 13 - 90	81 - 12 - 90	78 - 13 - 90	85 - 13 - 90	86 - 6.5 - 90	86 - 11 - 90
	sin	84 - 18 - 90	85 - 15 - 90	84 - 18 - 90	85 - 19 - 90	87 - 11 - 90	83 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 46 - 80	56 - 46 - 80	57 - 45 - 80	56 - 47 - 80	56 - 46 - 80	58 - 47 - 80
	sin	54 - 45 - 80	58 - 44 - 80	56 - 43 - 80	57 - 47 - 80	58 - 47 - 80	58 - 47 - 80

Abduction 90°	dx	98 - 8.5 - 0	97 - 6 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	99 - 10 - 0	96 - 5 - 0	94 - 6 - 0
	sin	90 - 8.5 - 0	88.5 - 12.5 - 0	87 - 13 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	93 - 10 - 0	96 - 10 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	96.5 - 7.5 - 90	93 - 6 - 90	83 - 6 - 90	87 - 9 - 90	85 - 7 - 90	84 - 6 - 90
	sin	96 - 11 - 90	83.5 - 12.5 - 90	83 - 9 - 90	85 - 9 - 90	85 - 13 - 90	85 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	53.5 - 46 - 80	58 - 54 - 80	57 - 45 - 80	60 - 50 - 80	52 - 47 - 80	50 - 45 - 80
	sin	63 - 48 - 80	50 - 65 - 80	57 - 54 - 80	58 - 46 - 80	52 - 43 - 80	55 - 45 - 80

No. 159, man, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	96.5 - 9.5 - 0	90 - 16.5 - 0	89 - 11 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	94 - 9 - 0	95 - 10 - 0
	sin	99 - 10.5 - 0	86 - 13 - 0	88 - 13 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	94 - 8 - 0	96 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	83 - 6 - 90	87 - 6 - 90	80 - 12 - 90	85 - 5 - 90	83 - 11 - 90	86 - 7 - 90
	sin	81 - 6 - 90	86 - 7.5 - 90	83 - 9 - 90	90 - 5 - 90	87 - 8 - 90	87 - 8 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	54 - 43.5 - 80	53 - 44 - 80	52 - 47 - 80	55 - 5 - 80	52 - 48 - 80	52 - 48 - 80
	sin	55.5 - 46 - 80	54 - 48 - 80	53.5 - 46.5 - 80	55 - 43 - 80	55 - 47 - 80	56 - 47 - 80

No. 138, man, 30-35 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	98.5 - 7.5 - 0	97 - 13 - 0	91 - 12 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	94 - 12 - 0
	sin	97 - 7 - 0	88.5 - 11 - 0	93 - 13 - 0	93 - 10 - 0	94 - 8 - 0	94 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	84 - 8 - 90	85 - 4.5 - 90	84 - 8 - 90	85 - 10 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	86 - 12 - 90
	sin	96 - 6.5 - 90	87 - 4.5 - 90	84 - 11 - 90	83 - 7 - 90	84 - 8 - 90	83 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	55.5 - 45 - 80	52 - 41.5 - 80	57 - 44 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	52 - 42 - 80	51 - 42 - 80
	sin	56.5 - 45 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	54 - 45 - 80	54 - 43 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	52 - 44 - 80

No. 139, man, 30-35 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	100 - 10 - 0	91 - 10.5 - 0	93 - 8 - 0	94 - 6 - 0	93.5 - 9.5 - 0	97 - 5 - 0
	sin	97 - 10 - 0	97 - 4.5 - 0	97 - 11 - 0	96 - 7 - 0	95 - 6 - 0	98 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	89 - 8 - 90	91 - 8.5 - 90	85 - 15 - 90	86 - 9 - 90	84.5 - 10 - 90	86 - 7 - 90
	sin	88 - 12 - 90	91 - 10.5 - 90	87 - 13 - 90	87 - 11 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	87 - 8 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	54 - 43 - 80	54 - 43 - 80	54 - 45 - 80	52 - 44 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	57 - 47 - 80
	sin	57 - 46 - 80	52 - 43 - 80	56 - 46 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	56 - 44 - 80	54 - 44 - 80

No. 120, man, 30-35 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	96.5 - 4.5 - 0	87 - 16 - 0	91 - 16 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	97 - 8 - 0	94 - 6 - 0
	sin	96 - 8.5 - 0	93 - 16 - 0	97 - 13 - 0	96 - 10 - 0	91 - 11 - 0	93 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	88 - 13 - 90	81 - 13 - 90	83 - 8 - 90	85.5 - 12 - 90	83 - 7 - 90	86 - 11 - 90
	sin	93 - 6.5 - 90	86 - 10 - 90	87 - 16 - 90	84 - 13 - 90	87 - 13 - 90	83 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	55 - 47 - 80	54 - 43 - 80	45 - 48 - 80	48 - 40 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	52 - 47 - 80
	sin	56.5 - 48 - 80	52 - 43 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	51 - 43 - 80	53 - 41 - 80	51 - 43 - 80

No. 71, woman, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	103 - 10 - 0	101 - 9 - 0	88 - 10 - 0	97 - 10 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	98 - 12 - 0
	sin	98.5 - 6 - 0	96 - 12 - 0	90 - 8.5 - 0	95 - 15 - 0	96 - 12 - 0	96 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	82 - 11 - 90	89 - 6 - 90	80 - 13 - 90	83 - 9 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	87 - 13 - 90
	sin	81 - 13 - 90	89 - 8.5 - 90	83 - 7 - 90	85 - 13 - 90	84 - 11 - 90	85 - 12 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	55 - 45.5 - 80	57 - 42 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	53 - 46 - 80	55 - 46 - 80	53 - 45 - 80
	sin	55 - 45.5 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	53 - 46 - 80	56 - 45 - 80	54 - 45 - 80	52 - 47 - 80

No. 60, woman, 25-30 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	92 - 7.5 - 0	91 - 13 - 0	94 - 9 - 0	93 - 10 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	95 - 14 - 0
	sin	96 - 11 - 0	92.5 - 12.5 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	97 - 9 - 0	94 - 12 - 0	99 - 13 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	85 - 18 - 90	94.5 - 16 - 90	82 - 16 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	84 - 14 - 90	83 - 16 - 90
	sin	85 - 13 - 90	94 - 16 - 90	82 - 19 - 90	85 - 12 - 90	85 - 12 - 90	86 - 16 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	57.5 - 43.5 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	53 - 46 - 80	52 - 45 - 80	53 - 47 - 80
	sin	57 - 42 - 80	53 - 41 - 80	52.5 - 47 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	56 - 48 - 80

No. 109a, man, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	96.5 - 9 - 0	96 - 8 - 0	91 - 13 - 0	85 - 10 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	94 - 9 - 0
	sin	96 - 9 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	93.5 - 13 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	91 - 12 - 0	97 - 13 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	89 - 6 - 90	87 - 7 - 90	83 - 12.5 - 90	80 - 10 - 90	85 - 10 - 90	84 - 9 - 90
	sin	91 - 16 - 90	93 - 11 - 90	84.5 - 11 - 90	80 - 10 - 90	84 - 13 - 90	86 - 8.5 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	54 - 43 - 80	51 - 43 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	53 - 48 - 80	55 - 45 - 80
	sin	53.5 - 45.5 - 80	53 - 44 - 80	53.5 - 47.5 - 80	52 - 47 - 80	52 - 47 - 80	53 - 45.5 - 80

No. 63, woman, 35-40 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	98.5 - 8.5 - 0	97.5 - 9 - 0	93 - 13 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	94 - 11 - 0	96 - 13 - 0
	sin	92 - 6 - 0	99 - 8 - 0	99 - 12.5 - 0	97 - 12 - 0	98 - 15 - 0	98 - 14 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	94.5 - 6 - 90	94.5 - 16 - 90	87 - 12 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	83 - 15 - 90	82 - 13 - 90
	sin	84 - 8 - 90	94 - 16 - 90	85 - 7.5 - 90	86 - 15 - 90	85 - 13 - 90	87 - 16 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 48 - 80	54 - 47 - 80	53 - 46 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	56 - 42 - 80	56 - 44 - 80
	sin	57 - 42.5 - 80	56 - 41.5 - 80	53 - 45.5 - 80	56 - 47 - 80	54 - 45 - 80	57 - 43 - 80

No. 52, woman, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	95 - 6.5 - 0	94 - 13 - 0	96.5 - 12 - 0	95 - 5 - 0	95 - 5 - 0	94 - 7 - 0
	sin	92 - 6 - 0	97 - 7 - 0	98.5 - 13 - 0	98 - 8 - 0	97 - 10 - 0	94 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	83 - 16 - 90	87 - 7 - 90	88.5 - 11 - 90	86 - 9 - 90	83 - 10 - 90	83 - 12 - 90
	sin	87 - 13 - 90	93 - 11 - 90	83.5 - 12 - 90	87 - 12 - 90	85 - 13 - 90	84 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	58 - 45 - 80	58 - 43 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	49 - 42 - 80	52 - 45 - 80	52 - 47 - 80
	sin	57 - 42.5 - 80	57 - 47 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	56 - 47 - 80	53 - 47 - 80

No. 111, man, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	87 - 8.5 - 0	98 - 10 - 0	93 - 8 - 0	92 - 8 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	97 - 13 - 0
	sin	92 - 9 - 0	89 - 9 - 0	89 - 10 - 0	91 - 9 - 0	93 - 9 - 0	94 - 8 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	83 - 7 - 90	91.5 - 10 - 90	87 - 10 - 90	86 - 4 - 90	85 - 10 - 90	84 - 12 - 90
	sin	88 - 17 - 90	87 - 7.5 - 90	83 - 11 - 90	83 - 11.5 - 90	83 - 11 - 90	84 - 11 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 41.5 - 80	57 - 48 - 80	52 - 41 - 80	53 - 45 - 80	56 - 42 - 80	53 - 43 - 80
	sin	57 - 42.5 - 80	52 - 43.5 - 80	53 - 48 - 80	55 - 44 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	52.5 - 44 - 80

No. 122, man, 20-25 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	95.5 - 13 - 0	90 - 13 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	93 - 9 - 0	93 - 13 - 0	94 - 12 - 0
	sin	100 - 11 - 0	91 - 12 - 0	96 - 13 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	96 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	87.5 - 6 - 0	85 - 4 - 90	83 - 9 - 90	83 - 12 - 90	83 - 11 - 90	83 - 7 - 90
	sin	94 - 3 - 90	87 - 9 - 90	87 - 12 - 90	85 - 9 - 90	85 - 10 - 90	84 - 6 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 41.5 - 80	54 - 42 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	52 - 45 - 80	54 - 47 - 80
	sin	57 - 42 - 80	52 - 45 - 80	56 - 44 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	52 - 46 - 80	53 - 47 - 80

No. 94a, woman, 30-35 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	90 - 8 - 0	91 - 13 - 0	93 - 12 - 0	91 - 5 - 0	94 - 13 - 0	93 - 13 - 0
	sin	90 - 10 - 0	87.5 - 13 - 0	94.5 - 7 - 0	93 - 7 - 0	95 - 11 - 0	93 - 6 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	88 - 13 - 90	83 - 9 - 90	82 - 9 - 90	83 - 11 - 90	81 - 11 - 90	83 - 11 - 90
	sin	89 - 12.5 - 90	88.5 - 9 - 90	86.5 - 12 - 90	86 - 7.5 - 90	86 - 9 - 90	84 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	51 - 45 - 80	56 - 46 - 80	53 - 47.5 - 80	52.5 - 43 - 80	52 - 43 - 80	54 - 44 - 80
	sin	50 - 44 - 80	58 - 47 - 80	53 - 44 - 80	54 - 48 - 80	54 - 43 - 80	56 - 43 - 80

No. 213, man, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	91 - 10 - 0	97 - 9 - 0	97 - 11 - 0	95 - 9 - 0	93 - 9 - 0	93 - 13 - 0
	sin	90 - 8 - 0	97 - 16 - 0	97.5 - 8 - 0	97 - 8 - 0	93.5 - 9 - 0	91 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	87 - 13 - 90	91 - 11 - 90	87 - 12 - 90	87 - 8 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	85 - 13 - 90
	sin	78 - 21 - 90	91 - 9 - 90	90 - 13 - 90	91 - 8 - 90	84 - 11 - 90	84 - 14 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	54 - 45 - 80	60 - 48 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	54 - 48 - 80	52 - 48 - 90	53 - 42 - 80
	sin	59 - 48 - 80	54 - 49 - 80	56 - 44 - 80	56 - 44 - 80	53 - 49 - 80	52 - 43 - 80

No. 84, woman, 35-40 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	86 - 9 - 0	90.5 - 11 - 0	91 - 12 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	92 - 9 - 0	94 - 6 - 0
	sin	92 - 11 - 0	91.5 - 11.5 - 0	97.5 - 13 - 0	91 - 15 - 0	94 - 13 - 0	96 - 13 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	92 - 18 - 90	81 - 13 - 90	87 - 12 - 90	85 - 11 - 90	85 - 11 - 90	84 - 6 - 90
	sin	98 - 21 - 90	84 - 11.5 - 90	90 - 13 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	83 - 14 - 90	83 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	55 - 42 - 80	57 - 44 - 80	55 - 47 - 80	53 - 45 - 80	52 - 48 - 80	53 - 43 - 80
	sin	54 - 43 - 80	52 - 46 - 80	53 - 48 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	52 - 43 - 80	53 - 43 - 80

No. 189, man, 25-30 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	89 - 8 - 0	87 - 9 - 0	86 - 13 - 0	93 - 11 - 0	93 - 9 - 0	93 - 7 - 0
	sin	93 - 11 - 0	89 - 12.5 - 0	90 - 7 - 0	91 - 10 - 0	94 - 7 - 0	94 - 13 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	88 - 8.5 - 90	83 - 4.5 - 90	87 - 9 - 90	86 - 9 - 90	84 - 11 - 90	84 - 9 - 90
	sin	88.5 - 18.5 - 90	86.5 - 10 - 90	89 - 9 - 90	83 - 10 - 90	82 - 11 - 90	86 - 12 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 43 - 80	57 - 46 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	58 - 43 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	56 - 47 - 80
	sin	56.5 - 45 - 80	56 - 47.5 - 80	54 - 43 - 80	57 - 42 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	58 - 47 - 80

No. 181, man, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	96 - 10 - 0	86 - 9 - 0	88 - 12 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	93 - 10 - 0	95 - 10 - 0
	sin	94 - 7 - 0	89 - 8.5 - 0	86.5 - 9 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	93.5 - 9 - 0	93 - 6 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	82.5 - 11.5 - 90	83 - 4.5 - 90	82 - 9 - 90	87 - 15 - 90	81 - 10 - 90	85 - 6 - 90
	sin	88.5 - 18.5 - 90	88 - 9 - 90	84 - 9 - 90	80 - 15 - 90	84 - 11 - 90	85 - 11 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	58 - 42 - 80	60 - 48 - 80	57 - 47 - 80	54 - 43 - 80	52 - 47 - 80	52 - 43 - 80
	sin	56 - 43 - 80	54 - 43 - 80	53 - 44.5 - 80	58 - 45 - 80	52 - 48 - 80	55 - 43 - 80

No. 201, man, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	92 - 10 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	97 - 7 - 0	93 - 13 - 0	96 - 9 - 0	95 - 10 - 0
	sin	86 - 9 - 0	96.5 - 8 - 0	94.5 - 7 - 0	94 - 12 - 0	97 - 11 - 0	93 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	89 - 15 - 90	93 - 9 - 90	89 - 9 - 90	87 - 6 - 90	84 - 11 - 90	84 - 11 - 90
	sin	87 - 18 - 90	87 - 11 - 90	80 - 10 - 90	87.5 - 9 - 90	86 - 12 - 90	83 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	57 - 46 - 80	57 - 45 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	57 - 44 - 80	52 - 43 - 80	53 - 43 - 80
	sin	49 - 45 - 80	52.5 - 48 - 80	52 - 47 - 80	53 - 48 - 80	51 - 47 - 80	51 - 41 - 80

No. 171, man, 18-20 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	97 - 11 - 0	97 - 11 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	99 - 10 - 0	95 - 10 - 0	93 - 9 - 0
	sin	94 - 11 - 0	93 - 9 - 0	94 - 12 - 0	96 - 9 - 0	96 - 9 - 0	94 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	87.5 - 11 - 80	93 - 9 - 90	85 - 12 - 90	82.5 - 15 - 90	85 - 15 - 90	83 - 13 - 90
	sin	87 - 11 - 90	87 - 11 - 90	84 - 8 - 90	84 - 13 - 90	87 - 16 - 90	84 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	57 - 46 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	53 - 47 - 80	52 - 43 - 80	52 - 44 - 80
	sin	55 - 48 - 80	57.5 - 45 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	57 - 42.5 - 80	57 - 43 - 80	57 - 46 - 80

No. 195a, man, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	87 - 12 - 0	96 - 14 - 0	95 - 16 - 0	89 - 8 - 0	91 - 7.5 - 0	93 - 11 - 0
	sin	97 - 9 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	94 - 15 - 0	93 - 9 - 0	92 - 11 - 0	91.5 - 13 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	94.5 - 13.5 - 90	94 - 6 - 90	86 - 13 - 90	84 - 8 - 90	84 - 12 - 90	84 - 12 - 90
	sin	87.5 - 11.5 - 90	91 - 9 - 90	87 - 11 - 90	86 - 7 - 90	82 - 12 - 90	83 - 13 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	57.5 - 44 - 80	54 - 41 - 80	53 - 42 - 80	57 - 47 - 80	52 - 44 - 80	53 - 43 - 80
	sin	57 - 47 - 80	58 - 43 - 80	57 - 45 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	56 - 47 - 80	58 - 46 - 80

No. 104, man, 40-50 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	88 - 8 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	90 - 10 - 0	93 - 8 - 0	92 - 11 - 0	95 - 10 - 0
	sin	92.5 - 6 - 0	90 - 9 - 0	90 - 7 - 0	91 - 9 - 0	91 - 12 - 0	94 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	89.5 - 11 - 90	86.5 - 11 - 90	86 - 7 - 90	91 - 6 - 90	84 - 12 - 90	84 - 11 - 90
	sin	87 - 14.5 - 90	84 - 9 - 90	81 - 13 - 90	87 - 15 - 90	84 - 9 - 90	86 - 12 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 46 - 80	57 - 46 - 80	55 - 45 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	56 - 43 - 80	57 - 43 - 80
	sin	58 - 46.5 - 80	56 - 43 - 80	58 - 43 - 80	53 - 45 - 80	53 - 44 - 80	57 - 43 - 80

No. 131, man, 35-40 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	89 - 9 - 0	89 - 9 - 0	89 - 13 - 0	94 - 12 - 0	93 - 9 - 0	94 - 8 - 0
	sin	92.5 - 6 - 0	85 - 9 - 0	86 - 12 - 0	91 - 13 - 0	95 - 11 - 0	96 - 9 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	81.5 - 11.5 - 90	90 - 9 - 90	86 - 4 - 90	89 - 13 - 90	83 - 11 - 90	82 - 14 - 90
	sin	97 - 12.5 - 90	91.5 - 5 - 90	87.5 - 5 - 90	85 - 9 - 90	85 - 12 - 90	83 - 10 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 45 - 80	57.5 - 43.5 - 80	52 - 47 - 80	54 - 43 - 80	55 - 47 - 80	56 - 47 - 80
	sin	55.5 - 42.5 - 80	58.5 - 41 - 80	56 - 48 - 80	57 - 45 - 80	57 - 45 - 80	57 - 45 - 80

No. 190, man, 20-25 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	96 - 6 - 0	89 - 12 - 0	97 - 9 - 0	95 - 15 - 0	99 - 8 - 0	98 - 9 - 0
	sin	90 - 12 - 0	90 - 11 - 0	93 - 7.5 - 0	90 - 6 - 0	94 - 10 - 0	93 - 11 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	92 - 13 - 90	78 - 13 - 90	87.5 - 6.5 - 90	87 - 5 - 90	87 - 16 - 90	86 - 14 - 90
	sin	86.5 - 11.5 - 90	81 - 10 - 90	86.5 - 9 - 90	85 - 10 - 90	86 - 13 - 90	84 - 9 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	56 - 43 - 80	53 - 43 - 80	57 - 44 - 80	54 - 47 - 80	56 - 47 - 80	57 - 46 - 80
	sin	57 - 46.5 - 80	56 - 43 - 80	56 - 42.5 - 80	55 - 47 - 80	53 - 44 - 80	52 - 43 - 80

No. 166b, man, 30-35 yrs.

Abduction 90°	dx	93 - 11 - 0	91 - 11 - 0	97 - 13 - 0	92 - 16 - 0	96 - 8 - 0	94.5 - 11 - 0
	sin	88.5 - 12 - 0	97.5 - 9.5 - 0	103 - 12 - 0	97 - 8 - 0	94 - 8 - 0	98 - 16 - 0
Spear throwing	dx	88 - 13.5 - 90	96 - 9 - 90	87 - 13 - 90	85 - 10 - 90	83 - 13 - 90	82.5 - 16 - 90
	sin	85.5 - 12 - 90	85 - 10 - 90	85 - 11 - 90	87 - 12.5 - 90	86 - 13 - 90	87 - 14 - 90
Forehand-drive	dx	64 - 46 - 80	52 - 43.5 - 80	55.5 - 45 - 80	60 - 50 - 80	58 - 43 - 80	53 - 45 - 80
	sin	59 - 43 - 80	54 - 46 - 80	54 - 46.5 - 80	57 - 43.5 - 80	56 - 47 - 80	53 - 42 - 80

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